

UNIVERSITY OF THE WEST OF SCOTLAND

School of Business and Enterprise

CRITICAL EVALUATION OF USING TECHNOLOGY AND INFORMATION
COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGY AS A STRATEGIC TOOL FOR PROMOTION IN
THE TOURISM INDUSTRY IN ALBANIA.

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COHORT 3

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DECLARATION

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ABSTRACT

Advanced information technology systems and rapid changes in customer demand have driven Albanian tourist organisations to attain other ways of reaching and communicating with customers that are faster and less expensive. Levels of technology usage in Albania are low compared to neighbouring countries, accompanied by a lack of skilled staff and inadequate customer care.

When conducting research in this area, it was deemed important to investigate how levels of technological usage in this industry could be used as a strategic tool for promotion and give advice as how tourism in Albania could enhance its performance to secure competitive advantage in the global tourism marketplace, and on how effects of technology impact overall development in the Albanian tourism industry.

Both primary and secondary data was collected and analysed from both qualitative and quantitative sources. Primary data was collected through tour operators in two different cities in Albania using questionnaires and interviews. SPSS software was used to analyse data, and qualitative data was examined using thematic analyses. Secondary data included appraisal of data from appropriate books, journals, and articles.

This research has contributed to the body of knowledge by presenting models that should help tour operators and destinations in Albania to improve developments through technological enhancement. Models presented consist of enhancement of website design and content, increasing customer satisfaction as well as levels of security, trust, and reliability.

This practical contribution involves an improved awareness related of the influence of technology in the Albanian tourism Industry.

Further research areas have been identified and suggestions made, including an evaluation of aspects of outcomes of technology in customer retention and customer satisfaction and loyalty.

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CHAPTER 1 INTRODUCTION

'The decade where we are living now is going to be remembered as a decade from where tourism started to appear as one of the most important sectors and human activities by contributing in economic development and a better life' (T. Rifai, 2012).

The tourism industry is one of the industries that has been progressing speedily during the past decades. New destinations, beautiful and natural landscapes, cultural and historical sites have been discovered for the world to visit. For a destination to be discovered there is the need to adapt the most appropriate tools and network to reach a competitive advantage in the market. The impact and contribution that this sector provides globally is more important for developing countries to focus on in their development. In terms of destinations, it is important to mention that image and reputation should be maintained and continuously improved to be competitive in the market. Adaptation of the latest developments and applications is crucial in the tourism industry due to intense competition. Interaction with new communication technologies brings a better understanding for the industry and services for customers and tourists. The tourist sector is highly perceptive towards information. Tourist behaviour is usually shaped by information provided and they are always eager for updated information. New technologies, especially the internet and ICT have impacted on the tourism industry and particularly destinations in terms of promotional and advertising campaigns to enter a new market dimension and attract potential tourists by providing relevant information.

1.1 Background of the study

Nowadays, tourism is one of the most important industries globally for many social, economic, technological, and geopolitical reasons (Argyropoulou, *et al.* 2012). Tourism is characterized from continuous development and high sensitivity which comes as a result of different internal or external factors whilst at the same time it attracts the world's attention (UNWTO, 2016). This is a consequence of choosing strategic development plans which are adaptable because of geopolitical, social, economic, technological, and natural changes.

According to UNWTO (2010) the word tourism itself, for most citizens in different countries is understood as walking and visiting to relax and enjoy good, beautiful natural surroundings that are built by hand and sophisticated machines yet are man directed. UNWTO (2010) Innovations and developments in different areas that interact with tourism make this sector one of the most complex sectors in the today's society. Development of Information of communication technologies ICT plays an important role in the Tourism

industry as there are many similarities between the two. It is important that both the internet and ICT are adapted by organizations and businesses operating in the tourism industry due to the impact and information channels that are provided (Sevrani et al. 2011). Information is crucial and important in the tourism industry as it is the first contact that potential customers have about destination and tourism products (Buhalis,2003). Considering the connection and interaction between technology, ICT, and the tourism industry, it is tourism sector that mostly benefits from this interaction, through businesses and customers due to advances in communication, services and information provided and distributed globally.

1.1.1 Tourism Today

Tourism bestows a great contribution to the global economy through provision of employment, as it is the largest job provider (UNWTO, 2017). The travel and tourism sector is a large global industry, whose revenues support a significant proportion of country's economies and is one of the largest job creators worldwide. Its contribution to GDP, employment, regional development, social support, unlike many other sectors, is forecast to grow in importance in the coming years as leisure time increases (UNWTO, 2017).

According to the World Tourism Organisation, (2016-2020) the tourism sector is one of the industries that have been contributing towards sustained development in the world's economy since the 2009 economic crisis. However, with the pandemic, this contribution has decreased significantly around the world. Data from 2020 takes into consideration the period from January to May 2020. Furthermore, tourism shows strength towards safety and security which leads to a continuous growth of international travel. Considering the figures, international travel has increased considerably compared to previous years. Moreover, in relation to rapid development of the tourism sector, experts predict a positive growth.

Area / Zone	Total Arrivals in millions (2016)	Total Arrivals in millions (2017)	Total Arrivals in millions (2018)	Total Arrivals in millions (2019)	Total Arrivals in % (2020)
Europe	620million(+2%) or 12 m more than 2015	671	713	744	- 58%
Asia & Pacific	303million(+8%) or 24m more than 2015	324	343	361	-60%
Middle East	54million (+4%)	58	64	64	-52%
Africa	58million(8%) or 4m more than 2015	63	67	73	-47%
America	201million(+4%) or 8m more than 2015	207	217	220	-47%

Table 1.1 – Global Tourism growth (Statistics)

Source: World Tourism Organisation (2020) The Author

Tourism Industries is one of the most important industries of developing countries, because it interacts with industries such as economic, politics, culture, telecommunication and other activities and functions to develop the country (UNWTO, 2019). Over past last decades, the tourism industry has been continuously growing and diversifying by becoming one of fastest sectors of the economy.

Figure 1.1: Tourism Contribution

Source: World Tourism Organisation (2019)

Considering the data for 2019, it is obvious that the pandemic has affected mostly the tourism industry global Research from WTTC (2019) has shown that there was a decline in the

tourism contribution to GDP for 2020. The effect of the pandemic has been obvious in employment as well as 62 million jobs were lost.

	Employment (in Millions)	GDP in %	GDP in US Dollars (Trillion)
2019	334	10.4%	9.3
2020	272(-18.5%)	5.5%	4.7(-49.1%)

Table 1.2: Global Tourism Contribution.

Source: WTTC (2019), The Author

Tourism development in a country's economy may have different impacts. Most important impacts are among social and economic activities, national income, development of economic activities that make up the economy (catering, transportation, trade, cultural institutions, in the growth of employment, raising standards of living standards, increasing investment) and so on. By considering data and statistics provided by tourism organisations it is important to mention that tourism sectors are not only interacting with other industries but is contributing to country development, GDP growth and increase of wealth (UNWTO, 2016). By being globally spread, the tourism industry has become a major player for international commerce which makes the tourism sector the main income for several developing countries. Due to its importance and contribution, the tourism sector during the last decade has increased employment and well-being. This is strongly related to the country's tourism capabilities for tourist destinations and offers.

1.1.2 Importance of technology and ICT in Tourism Sector.

Tourism is acknowledged to be very information intensive. Information is important in tourism due to its intangible activities. Tourists need new sources of information to help them in their decision-making process, plan their trips and choose between alternative tourist destinations. Because it is one of the industries where information is crucial that depends on finding and developing new means to distribute travel and hospitality products and services, marketing information to consumers and provide comfort and convenience to customers.

Information Technology has primarily increased the speed and ease of buying for customers, and has significantly reduced the cost of access, provided by businesses. According to Parson and Oja, (2013) and Dudovskiy, (2014) the internet is the biggest

network where information is distributed quickly, as a low cost and high value service that is widely used to promote tourism products and services. Furthermore, Schneiger, (2010) stated that the internet has a strong impact, not only on the tourism industry but on other sectors as well as being a tool that facilitates communication, sales, management, and so on.

Tourism is mainly based on information from tourism suppliers and businesses to potential consumers. Technology and ICT play an important role for the competitiveness of tourism destinations as it is easier to reach customers and share with them by advertising products and services.

According to Buhalis and Connor,(2005) it is stated that there is not any official definition for Information Communication Technology, but it can be considered as a combination of tools, devices, applications, and network systems that allow businesses and individuals that operate in tourism sector, to interact globally on a continuous basis. According to Ivanovska (2008) ICT is one of the applications that have found wide usage in the tourism industry since the first reservation system was applied in the 1960's. This is related to the importance of information in this sector in terms of customers and organisations. On one hand, due to information that is provided, customers and potential tourist are directly affected, and this influences their decision-making processes as well as their satisfaction and loyalty. In their work (Chen & Tsai, 2007) and (Rial &Verela,2008) state that tourists consider every kind of information about destinations or organisations which in most cases affect their destination decisions.

According to UNWTO (2010) and Mihalic & Buhalis (2013) it is stated that ICT plays an important role in terms of competition between organisations and destinations. Furthermore, it is important to note that organisational and destination competitive advantage can be reached only when this application is combined with proper development plans, strategies, communications, and promotional campaigns. In some case there is a lack of understanding regarding the importance of this combination and interaction between ICT and strategies that can lead to failure if not applied correctly.

The use of ICT in the Albanian tourism enterprises is relatively low compared to other European countries (Noti,2016). A considerable number of small and medium tourism enterprises do not understand the importance of investing in technology and for its use as a marketing function to increase customers. Such research is important. By considering literature it can be understood that there is hardly any data or studies on the use of technology in tourism from various aspects, although there are a few valuable initiatives in the Albanian

context. It is important to note that demand in the market dictates that business is more than necessary to use modern information technology to survive and be competitive.

The importance of using technology, internet and ICT is closely related to promotional and marketing strategies which are vital to succeed in tourism. Mohammadi, et.al, (2015) state that marketing and promotion of products and services through technology in tourism industry is an important element in fulfilling the desires and needs of tourists that visit a touristic destination, but difficulties and the misunderstanding of the concepts that already exist make marketing in the tourism industry ineffective. A lack of proper marketing and strategic tools makes it more difficult for a destination to update customers with products and services. Mitra,(2005) stated that only promoting the destination sometimes is not enough and this is a concern in the tourism industry as the destination should create and maintain a positive image(Yilmaz et al.2007) to be competitive in the market. However, it is more important that this positive image is needed to be presented to potential customers. Nowadays destinations consider promotional activities and promotional campaign as a main source for development and success.

1.2 Tourism industry in Albania(Research Context)

Albania is one of the countries that in the last decades has been paying more attention to tourism industry as a social, cultural and economic indicator by influencing this positively in the country. Albanian Tour agencies and other businesses have benefited from the geographical position of Albania to bring a variety of products and services. Such variety gives the possibility for the touristic destination to be a potential destination. Albania is a country that has lots of touristic potentials to consider from wonderful landscapes, cultural and historical buildings as well as tradition that is unique on its own.

1.2.1 Overview of Albania as a touristic destination

a. Tourism during and post Communism in Albania.

Albania, as a country has long history in promotion of tourism, but still there are cases of unsuccessful marketing plans and promotional campaign. During the Communist period, the tourism industry was not developed at all and it was available only for people of reputation. According to Pojani,(2009) after the communist system fell, the country started to pay attention to the industry, and the progress and development of their marketing plans and promotion techniques have led to attract tourists to this destination. In the 1990-1991 year of change, Albania abandoned the system of long-standing Communist isolation and was

involved in a period of political, economic, and social transition to a democratic system. From that time Albania's economy has experienced a difficult transition phase from being planned and centralized to a market economy.

Considering this transition phase of the economy sector, in general, the importance of tourism was underestimated, and its development was not recognized due to the conditions of the country. In that sense, tourism was a full monopoly of the state, ruled and organized only by a state tourism institution 'Albturizmi'. This general economic, political, and social situation that was created in Albania after 1990, and this had a strong influence on tourism development. New conditions created after 1990 are good for the promotion of tourism in Albania such as:

- The discovery of the country after its long isolation,
- Membership of Albania in different world organizations,
- The appreciation of tourism as one of the most prosperous branches of the Albanian economy,
- Development of other sectors of the economy closely related to tourism (trade, services, transport, construction),
- Domestic and foreign investments in the field of tourism.

However, the situation for Albania has changed since then.

b. Tourism Today in Albania

According to the Albanian Minister of Tourism (2013) it is stated that the tourism industry is seen as the main indicator for a future sustainable development not only for the sector, but for other industries. The Albanian Ministry of Tourism, Culture, Youth and Sport (MTCYS) is responsible in putting different regulations in terms of the tourism industry in co-operation with government bodies. There are the National Tourism Agency of Albania and Albanian Tourism Association who are responsible for the development of tourism by promoting in national and international markets Albania's tourism products/services. In the tourism sector the country has applied different marketing strategies aimed mostly the international market of tourists as it brings money into the country.

Tourism in Albania still holds and maintains traditions but is going forward to combine it with current trends that tourists are looking for. There is close collaboration of tourism organisations with state and private tour operators sharing common objectives to attract more tourists in destination by taking into consideration seasonality and a variety and type of products or holiday packages.

c. Future plans for Albania

The Albanian tourism industry has a strategic draft on tourism which experts have been considering since 2014 to the present. According to the Ministry of Tourism in Albania, (2013) it is stated that government is working towards the development of tourism and introducing a draft strategy which covers a six-year time-period. The National Tourism Strategy 2014-2020 is an important document for the development of tourism in Albania in future years, as the main platform related to policies, reforms, and measures in the tourism sector not only for the Government and ministry responsible for tourism, but also for other stakeholders, such as local government and the private sector. According to Government's instructions (2014) the National Tourism Strategy has been prepared in the framework of sector strategies for the period after 2013. This strategy represents and reflects Government initiatives, policies, and objectives, and underlines the importance of tourism as the main sector for economy, employment, and exports, defining the focus and resources needed for it. This strategy reflects the program of reforms in all sectors, with the aim of putting tourism in the direction of sustainable development and cutting off chaotic, unplanned, and unmanaged tourism development. This strategy reflects the demand of all stakeholders who have high expectations regarding tourism contributions and the need for a leading role of the ministry responsible for tourism.

1.2.2 Current situation of Tourism in Albania

The tourism sector in Albania in recent years is presenting many opportunities, both for business that is involved in various activities in the service of the tourists as well as for the public sector which benefits from the increase of revenues from tourism and investments. In recent years, the number of foreign visitors, as well as of non-resident Albanians living in emigration, is increasing considerably due to numerous tourists and diversified potential existing in Albania, both natural and cultural, as well as competitive prices. Moreover, tourism in Albania is contributing the country's economy and employment in a continuous way. Albania is part of the third world, which means the country is still in a development period. Most of the industries that operate in the country are slowly developing and these

makes it slow for the economy and the country. Tourism in Albania has continuously grown over the last decade and contributes to the country's GDP, employment and improvement of services and products. According to Kotherja (2013) Albania is one of the countries that is rich with its natural, cultural, and historical cities, plus extraordinary welcoming communities.

However, this is not enough for the tourism industry to be successful due to its lack of promotion and strategies. The lack of investment and poor political reforms from the Governments over many years have degraded tourism. Nowadays, tourism is a priority for the Albanian government, but this priority gets lost on electoral promises from parties and this is demonstrated by slow improvements that take place in tourism. According to WTO (2013) tourism is one of the most important industries, considering its impact on population, and job creation. Considering improvement in the Albanian tourism industry it is necessary that this issue is given more attention.

According to Lonely Planet (2015) it is not understandable why this destination needed more than 20 years to introduce itself as a touristic destination, when it can offer much more to tourists rather than other destinations. Strategies and development plans that have been lacking for many years have left tourism sector poor and slowly developed and since the fall of Communism, tourism has been applied only inside the country. It could bring its name more to the fore as most of the world still does not know where Albania is and its ability to offer to the nature lovers, breath-taking views, alpine settings, hiking, canoeing, etc.

Albania has a favourable geographic position in the region, making it easily accessible from European markets. It is important to emphasize that tourist services that are attractive to consumers should bring innovation and creativity, particularly by exploiting human and technological potential. Albania's tourism industry during the last decade has increased its contribution to the country's economy in monetary terms and employment. This increase in indicators is attributed to a favourable investment climate, active marketing, quality of hotel services, and low taxes. According to the Bank of Albania (2015), it stated that for a 9-month period, the number of tourists increased by about 12% compared to the same period in the previous year. In the last few years according to the (WTTC, 2017) it is stated that Albania is one of the countries whose tourism sector is continuously growing and has ranked Albania in the 96th position in between 185 countries. For the Year 2016 Tourism contributed into the Albanian economy by 26% of GDP (\$US 3.2million) which was expected to increase to 33% during 2017. In terms of employment, considering data from WTTC for the year 2016 in the tourism sector there were 85.000 job positioned which is

7.7% of total jobs in Albania. This is expected to increase by 3.2% reaching 10.9 % of jobs in Albania (World Data Atlas,2016).

During 2015, there was also a change in the geography of origins of tourist inflows. A few years ago, arrivals were mainly from the region (Macedonia, Kosovo). Then there was more of an influx from Slovenia, Slovakia, Czech Republic, Poland, Norway, Sweden, Italy, Austria, Denmark, Germany, and France and for 2017 there was a plan to expand international tourist achievements. The challenge for the Government means opening of the Asian market, principally to China.

However, for the government, during the period of 2016 until present, there have been major challenges. The first was the quality of service which is negative. The second was the capacity within the hospitality industry, and this has to do with the attractiveness of the country for foreign and domestic investment.

Considering that Albania and neighbouring countries such as Croatia, Macedonia Montenegro, Greece, and Italy share similar touristic characteristics, it is important to mention that Albania needs to follow some of these countries to improve progress and to be a competitive destination in this market and beyond. This information has been compiled for data for the year 2019 in different perspectives.

Countries	Tourism contribution to GDP in (billion \$US)	Tourism direct contribution to GDP in (billion \$US)	Tourism contribution to GDP in %	Number of tourists(2019)
Albania	4.8	1.5	27.0%	6,406,000
Croatia	15.9	7.0	25.1%	60,021,000
Montenegro	1.2	0.6	21.7%	758,000
Macedonia	1.0	0.3	7.4%	758,000
Italy	279.4	119.7	19.3%	95,399,000
Greece	47.0	19.5	21.2%	34,005,000

Table 1.3 Comparison of the Albanian tourism Industry

Source: World Data Atlas(2019)

Tourism in Albania is receiving attention from government and private sectors due to the influence it has on the community and contribution to the state economy. Nowadays, tourist agencies have ideas of what tourism is and needs, but it becomes difficult when it

comes to practice and application. Tourism now has more than 15,000 beds in hotels, tour agencies and a huge variety of tourism services and products that are continuously growing and improving due to customer requirements. Albania tourism is separated into different categories based on the nature of the type of the tourism, geographic position, uniqueness of a destination, culture, and tradition. Albanian tourism embraces products such as seaside, mountains, adventures like parachuting, hiking, alpinism, exploration, sports, culture and more lately culinary tourism that is taking a crucial role in tourism.

However, customers do not have much information about these products. By being separated on both government jurisdiction and private sector, tourism in Albania still lacks a level of cohesion. Untrained staff, inappropriate plans for development and strategies for improvement have led to the slow development of tourism in Albania. Another reason is the lack of laws that regulate policy of service in tourism.

A few private organisations and tour agencies that provide services and products of tourism have been initiators and take part in different exhibitions and events in Europe and beyond by promoting their name as a business along with products that are offered. However, there is a need and demand from customers to be updated and adapt new technologies to be competitive in the market not only in Europe, but also beyond. The adoption of a new law on tourism is expected to bring about discipline of this industry, with the beginning of the implementation of standards and classifications. It was not possible to adopt a Fiscal Package in 2016, but a reduction of VAT has helped, and such a package can only be achieved after 2017.

Regarding investments in the field of tourism, the Ministry of Economy, Tourism, Trade and Entrepreneurship has pronounced the interest of foreigners. The name of the company is still unknown, but it is about an investment offer from a popular hospitality company, estimated at around 330 million Euros in investment, integrated with the low-cost tourist airport in southern Albania.

1.2.3 Trends of Tourism Industry in Albania

Tourism in Albania is moving towards what customers were looking when it started to promote to Albanian people who had not seen cultural and historical buildings and sites. Due to the lack of information most tourist come just for one reason and then go. Nowadays tourism in Albania creates great opportunities for customers whatever their reasons for

visiting. Albania, because of its geographical position can offer a variety of tourism products and services not only for the people who live in Albania but mostly for international tourists. Tourist agencies are trying to expand their market covering not only the Balkan area or Europe but nowadays countries like China, Australia, America, New Zealand, Africa, and Asia are in the focus for tourism promotions. According to Bedalli (2016) it is stated that in some cases reasons that international tourists like to visit Albania is because is because:

- a) Albania has an interesting culture and history,
- b) It is rich in natural landscapes and nice seaside,
- c) It is cheaper to spend holidays in Albania rather than in other neighbouring countries to buy the tourist products.

Tourist products vary from snowboarding, skiing to seaside and beach, adventures, diving, skydiving, health tourism, cultural and historical tourism, folk and traditions, culinary tourism. By having a variety of products in tourism it is sometimes difficult to aim at the right market as each type of products is meant to reach a target market. Albanian tourism started late and took a long time promote and introduce itself to potential tourists, globally, to stand where it is today. This time-period is longer compared to neighbouring countries.

According to the Albanian Institute of Statistics, (2016) there has been an increase in numbers of tourists for the period up to June (2017) by 10.8% compared to the same period the previous year. Considering these statistics, reasons for travelling are different but most of them are personal reasons which are mentioned by family and friends who have previously visited. There is a small percentage of international tourists coming into the country for other reason such as health, culture and business. Factors increase if there is interaction between the organisations in the destination with international ones. According to Tema (2017) Albania is one of the countries in the Balkans that is mostly visited for fun, holidays, adventures, and unforgettable experiences. This is supported by the report of WTTC (2017). Tourism infrastructures have been missing such as roads and transportation. There have been initiatives from both private sector and government to create basic conditions for tourists, mostly for those who explore.

According to Ora News (2017) there is new trends in the tourism industry by introducing new products such as culinary tourism. According to Milva Ekonomi, Minister of Tourism, this new product of tourism was introduced around 2016 and 2017 was the second year that the province of Lezha created a culinary exhibition where more than 50 businesses took part. However, participants were mostly from Albania, and there were a few businesses from neighbouring countries that found it interesting. Culinary tourism is increasing, but it

needs to be promoted and advertised as the culture and traditions of Albania are unique and old. Another service that has come to attention in Albania, according to Donald Hysi, dental surgery services, and stated in Ora News, 2017 that it is important for tourism agencies and organisations to include this service in the list of tourist products as it is already offered to tourists who have heard about it somewhere else. Dental services even though it is not officially included by tourism organisations as touristic products, are applied and most people come to receive dental services in Albania due to lower prices and quality of service.

1.2.4 Challenges of the Albanian Tourism Industry

In the context of Albania, challenges in tourism are related directly to problems that this sector is facing. Tourism in Albania is affected by challenges of information and awareness about tourism sectors and sites, to investors, tourists, and the public. Even tourist packets of full holidays, all-inclusive holidays are missing, even though this is offered to customers in Albania. By sharing similar characteristics with its neighbouring countries, it is important for Albania to have right promotional tools and companies and technologies to do this. According to Topi (2014), tourism in Albania is characterized by a variety of challenges and problems. Secondly, there is a lack of information about politics, initiatives and projects that take place in this sector. This makes it more difficult for interaction and collaboration, in terms of the investments and projects which are not solved and sometimes misunderstood. Moreover, there is a lack of clarity towards draft strategies in local communities which are the main strategies for destinations. Furthermore, there is great attention given to seaside areas of Albania due to its high potential for tourism development. These issues have impacted most of the Albanian seaside and this has been followed by the environmental disasters and issues for hotels, resorts, and tourist services.

1.3 . Role of Technology in Albanian tourism industry.

Although Albania has a considerable tourist potential, at the same time there has been an increasing trend in numbers of visitors over the past 10 years, the level of tourist services is still low compared to countries of the region, generally due to a lack of professionalism of the

staff involved who lack of a vision of what to do to be successful and competitive in the market. One of the most important elements in the day-to-day operations of tourist enterprises is information technology they use in marketing, sales, reservations, etc. But is this technology at the right level? Do Albanian ICT entrepreneurs understand the importance of ICT? This study will provide a response to these questions and many others related to information technology.

According to a study conducted by GIZ, ATA and GOPA Consultants in 2010 on assessing the use of ICT in the tourism sector in Albania, in the cities of Tirana, Durrës, Vlora, Shkodra and Korca, resulted in:

- Hotels and restaurants have use of Broader IT in their operations compared to travel agencies,
- Generally, companies have good knowledge of computers and the internet,
- The presence and use of the internet for different purposes of activity is not good,
- 67% of interviewed companies were present on the internet, presenting mainly only the company's name and its offers on the homepage,
- Online reservations were limited especially for bars and restaurants and travel agencies. Only 28% of respondents stated that they can make automatic bookings through their website,
- 47% of companies stated they use a specific program on finance, taxes, accounts etc. while the rest use MS Office programs such as excel and word,
- While 36% of hotels declare that they use an integrated system to accomplish at least one of the functions (offline or online) such as: bookings, entrance/exit/room use, restaurant, bar, laundry, laundry, parking, pool, payment, list of prices, reports, etc.
- Tourist travel agencies use more ICT to carry out functions such as booking flights, tourist packages and hotel reservations, which are realized through computer programs such as: Amadeus, Galileo, etc.
- Companies generally do not have sufficient online presence to promote their activity, but at the same time to provide various services for business and consumers. Other options such as online reservations through websites of companies are low, which is a major disadvantage for these ventures, as the international market today extensively applies this service.

1.3.1 Internet usage in Albania (technology and internet as tools for planning and organising holidays)

The internet has become important in peoples' lives. During the last decade usage of internet has increased significantly. According to the International telecommunication Union it shows that in 2000 internet was used only 0.1% of the population but after 10 years is used by 48.1% of Albanian people. The government is making it possible to expand infrastructure of internet access, and it is noted that younger people use the internet frequently.

According to Internet World Stats, March 2017, internet usage reached 62.6% of the population. There were 1.4 million Facebook users in June 2016. Albania has a lower internet rate than the average for Europe but compared with some countries of the region such as Montenegro, Turkey, Romania Albania has a higher penetration rate of the internet. Nowadays there are a lot of companies that offer the internet such as, Tring, AlbTelecom, Abissnet and more organisations or branches that are dependent on the main ones. However, considering the statistics provided it is demonstrated that the use of the internet in Albania has been quickly increasing. Still in most of the cases according to INSTAT the internet in Albanian businesses and companies is used only on work related issues. Privately, only a few Albanian businesses have a web page where they promote and advertise the company and what they offer. Except for the reasons already mentioned there is no data available about usage of internet in terms of electronic commerce. The biggest numbers of internet user in Albanian, are those of a young age and such social media as Facebook, Instagram, and mostly YouTube, are the applications that attract more individuals into the internet world. Recently, the internet and technology has changed the nature of working, shopping, planning and so on. In terms of holidays internet and technology is mostly used for information. Usually, the information that is researched on the online portals or social media is mostly about products or services that start from health to beauty services, tourist products or offers and hotels. However, this is just a brief investigation, because for Albanians, the idea that there the need to reserve or book accommodation before travelling is strange. This only happens when travelling inside the country. In most cases the application of technology and internet in Albania for tourism industry is covered only by airline bookings and tickets. There are cases when the individual chooses traditional ways to book a ticket by going to agencies due to the lack of information about technology and lack of knowledge of how to use the application.

As it is a late invention, most middle age and above people hardly use any services of technology or internet.

Social media

In case of Albania, social media has found a great usage in most sectors. The tourism sector being private, and state administrated organizations use social media for promotion and improvement of their business and what they offer. Through social media, tourist destinations promote their name, products, services and obviously target potential customers. In terms of tourist organizations, most of them have an account on social media. As a destination, Albania has been promoted through social media by different platforms, and examples are: Albanian tourism, welcome to Albania, visit Albania, Albanian beauty.

1.4 Significance of the study

Nowadays the whole world relies on the tourism industry as a main indicator and contributor for the development and certain destinations survive only by development of this sector by bringing about marketing a full range of activities, services, and different strategies through technology and its advances in to attract tourists not only inside the country, or neighbouring countries but worldwide as well.

Information of technology is an important tool in tourism industry as for years it has been an appropriate communications channel between the customers/tourists and supply. This electronic communication channel is a great help for supply to give information about what they sell and on the other side for customers to receive the information of what is offered to them.

Considering the improvements on the tourism sector it clearly needs to be said that technology and its advances have been contributing in improvements of the sector and as well being successful in different undertakings. This leads into the thought that technology is a key determinant on the continuous interchange communication between the two supply and tourists. Being considered as invisible services which you cannot touch, try, or feel it is difficult for customers to decide about a destination or a holiday without know anything about a place they have never heard about or its tourist activities. Here is where technology and its means come into play and its importance is that customers can easily access information about the place, services, activities, and tourist events. At this stage technology plays the role of the believable interpreter because its products/services are more reliable

clearer and trustful which leads potential tourists/customers to check and buy services and products and travel.

This study also creates awareness on different types of technology infrastructures used in tourism industries today and helps organisations to understand technology-based facilities as a tool that will provide greater competitive advantage enjoyed by competitors, increase profits, decrease costs and improve delivery of the service and ease employees work loads. Once tourist organisations understand the importance of technological infrastructures, it will in return increase opportunities for employment of graduates in IT, who can handle, install manage and train users of these infrastructures in various tourism industries that will adopt it.

By considering the technological invention and applications as well as their usage it is important to mention to note that it has become easier to search and obtain different information about tourist destinations as well as organisations/agencies. Such information includes information about the geographical position, offers regarding products and services, as well as political and social situations in the destination. In terms of organisations that operate in the tourism industry, usage of technology and internet to promote their businesses and products but as well technology is used as a strategic tool to reflect on performance to improve where and when it is needed.

Furthermore, technology usage and its tools allow interactive communication between customers, as well because by using internet and this means customers can share their experience and opinions so both sides can benefit.

1.5 Rationale of the Research

The researcher decided to research this topic due to personal tourism interests. Being born and growing up in the case study destination it is in the researcher's interest to investigate the ways and strategic tools used for promotional activities that are used in this country and its results from promotional activity and sector development. As a future person working in the tourism industry, it is important that the researcher understands the importance of using proper promotional strategies, tools, and marketing plans to have a successful industry including the creation of a positive image by representing the destination's uniqueness and features that make it a preferred destination.

This study shows the extent technology infrastructure utilization in the hospitality industry to gain an understanding of the relationship existing between technological advancement and economic development trends. This study will benefit the tourism industry

by providing critical information to organisations and tour operators in deciding on the areas which ICT should be adopted, such as room, or food and beverage division, as well as specific technologies that could improve tourist organisational performance.

Furthermore, this research should contribute to existing literature in terms of new strategies of managing and marketing the destination, the organizations that are responsible for their marketing, including promotional activities and strategies used by destinations to achieve a successful image and attraction to tourists. This research is conducted to understand the importance of using technology and its variety of means in the tourism industry and beyond to better represent and promote destinations. Use of technology to advertise Albania is a perfect example as it is a developing country, and it has some experience in promoting tourism and its products including success and failure, but still attracting a high number of tourists each year.

1.6 Statement of the Problem

Albania is a small country which due to different circumstances has been actively developing compared to neighbouring countries in terms of several area or sectors. One of these industries is travel and tourism industry which has been facing several difficulties to succeed in the market. By taking into consideration the slow development of Albania in the last two decades there is the need to mention difficulties that the sector has been finding such as lack of investment, regulations, and marketing activity (Bejtja, 2009). These reasons are followed by social and cultural obstacles such as bad associations in Albania since the Communism period and as such it continues to be presented to the world with the same connotation as a Communist country. This is because Albanians in many cases have been part of activities and events that have been attracting worldwide attention on a bad way.

Secondly, most tourism organisations are part of the private sector and for them is more important to gain a good reputation. This is a straight-line connection because as the name of company is well known it should be because of what is offered or sold to customers to be a favoured company to choose. However, the most important problem is technological advances that most of private sector would not like to invest due to the high costs. This also requires trained and professional staff which brings new technological strategies and improvement to the sector. The use of technology is a different perspective for social media or sharing pictures would be a better choice for companies to promote their company and the

destination. There is also the need for more trained personnel and managers to work in the tourism sector as most of the time, people who are dealing with it are not graduates in related subjects or just simply be owners of the destination or facility. A small percentage of individuals that work in tourism sector understand the importance of delivering a satisfactory customer service, whether face to face or not, and high performance to be loyal to customers. Due to the lack of education and training it is important to mention that performance and the quality of service depends on these issues.

1.7 Main Research Questions, Aims, and Objectives of the Research

17.1 Main Research Question

The main research question of this study focuses on factors that make technology an appropriate strategic tool for further development of the sector.

- What are the key factors that render the usage of technology and ICT effective in the tourism industry and how can Albania use technology as a strategic tool for promotion of its destinations?

Research Sub questions

- What is the current scenario of the Albanian tourism industry?
- What is the level of technology usage in the Albanian tourism industry?
- What are factors that render the effective usage of technology in the tourism industry?
- How can these technology factors be used as a strategic tool for promotion?

1.7.2 Aim of the research

- The aim of this research is to examine and identify factors which render the effective usage of IT and ICT in Tourism Industry and to recommend how these factors can be used by Albania to promote its tourist destinations.

1.7.3 Objectives of the Research

- To evaluate the current scenario in the tourism industry.
- To identify the levels of technology usage in the Albanian tourism industry.
- To examine and identify the key factors that render the effective usage if technology in the tourism Industry.
- To recommend how these factors of IT and ICT can be used as a strategic tool to promote its destination.

1.8 Methodology

This elaborates the methodology of the research that is going to be applied during research execution. This part includes analysis of concepts and techniques used in completion of the research. In terms of the methodology, the researcher planned to use a pragmatism philosophy which allows the researcher to have the freedom of choosing different tools and techniques to collect the data. It was planned to use a mixed method of data collection, both qualitative and quantitative to cover all the areas and issues of the chosen topic. A case study strategy and a deductive approach which includes planning to collect data from questionnaires in Albania.

1.9 Structure of the Research

This research is structured in a scientific way, so each section includes a separate issue that is related to the main topic chosen for this research. The research is separated into five different chapters: Introduction, Literature Review, Methodology, Findings and Discussions and Conclusions.

This first chapter has outlined how researcher introduces the topic of the study that includes the background of the study, background information regarding tourism in Albania, the use of technology in tourism and its functions in this field, including information about the destination, as well as the importance and significance and why the author decided to investigate this topic including as well aims of the study, objectives, and research questions.

Chapter 2 is the Literature Review. In this chapter the researcher includes a depth investigation and analysis of previous research on specific issues such as usage of technology and ICT in the tourism industry, its impact on promotional activities and determinant factors that make technology appropriate for destination development.

Chapter 3 concerns Methodology. In this chapter the researcher elaborates ways that the research is designed in terms of methods and techniques used in fulfilment of the study, such as the philosophy used, strategy, design, data collection methods and procedures, ethics, and reliability and validity, and its limitations.

Chapter 4 concerns data analysis and findings. This is the chapter where the researcher analyses the primary findings and how these are going to be collected through conducting questionnaires and interviews.

Chapter 5 relates to discussion of the data that has been collected.

Chapter 6 is conclusions and recommendations, that includes recommendation for further research.

1.10 Chapter Summary

This research focuses on the development of tourism industry through technology and ICT in Albania by identifying factors that make technology and Information Communication Technology appropriate for promotional activities and improving the tourism sector in Albania and the image of Albania as a tourist destination. Distribution of information and appropriate promotional campaigns through appropriate means of technology has become crucial for the industry and this needs a combination of appropriate tools, communication, and promotion to reach customers and be competitive in the market. This affects the destination used for the research as there is a need for the destination to understand importance of technology and ICT in terms of the Albanian tourism sector.

CHAPTER 2 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.0 Introduction

Tourism industry has become one of the sectors that gives a great contribution to countries globally. Different strategies, development plans and new innovations and technological advances all influence in a continuous way the tourism sector. These factors have enabled the sector to be accompanied by continuous development and growth. One of the most crucial issues that goes with tourism growth is the importance of proper promotional activities that destinations choose to apply.

Adaptation of latest strategies and plans especially in terms of technology have made the tourism sector provide better services and introduce a variety of products and services to customers. The use of technology has several impacts on the tourism industry, but by combining it in promotional activities it has become clear that information about destinations, services and products that it is now easier than before. Promotional activities can vary depending on the destination, but by considering that today's world is becoming digitalised it is important for destinations to be up to date with the market and potential customers.

2.1 Overview of the Global Tourism Industry.

Tourism industry is one of those sectors which date early and since then it has been continuously growing and developing. According to Gyr (2010) the roots of Tourism and Travel lead back to the 17th century where not a lot of people could travel or have holidays, as they could not afford or enjoy it. The only people who could travel at that time were the Royals, and first-class people and sometimes merchants who traded goods in different places.

However, events that have taken place during later centuries and decades such as World Wars brought new prospects and inventions in tourism sectors and since then people started to consider the sector as a life provider by securing better incomes. Such innovations were followed by the continuous growth in the tourism sectors and becoming one of the most important sectors in the world. During the past decade, the tourism industry has been attracting more attention from potential tourist destinations as an escape from poor performance in other industries.

The tourism industry consists of various components which include the process of travel and leisure. Components which are important to consider when individual plans for tourist purposes are now discussed. All components need to be updated with the latest

innovations and follow certain strategies in order to fulfil the process of travelling and create a positive travelling experience. By adapting and combining several strategies, plans and development tools this sector's continuous increase in productivity is good not only for the sector, but other sectors as well.

2.1.1 Impact of the Tourism Industry

Being considered as a major and important industry, the tourism sector is continuously impacting and affecting other sectors of a destination such as economy, telecommunications, and infrastructure. Due to this impact, there is an improvement on the conditions of the other sectors as well. According to the WTTC (2017) there are three major branches where the tourism sector has been impacting and influencing mostly, such as in economic, social, and environmental impact.

a. Economic Impact

Considering the report from WTTC (2017) it is stated that tourism is a strong and major sector that contributes to global Direct GDP. Continuously, is one of the sectors that gave priority to the employment by creating and supporting millions of jobs worldwide. Taking account of the statistics from the WTTC (2017) report about the year 2017 it is demonstrated that tourism industry contributes 10.2% to the global GDP and has created 109 million jobs in the whole world which means that 1 in 10 job positions is in the tourism sector. In terms of economic aspects, this growth is continuing to increase up to 11.4 % for 2017 and the course tourism sector supports more than 309 million jobs worldwide which means that 1 in 9 jobs created in 2017 is in the tourism industry. According to Vladi (2014) even though the tourism sector has a positive impact there are some issues that come to attention such as tourism can increase the cost of everyday living, increasing the price of properties, goods and services, cost of infrastructure and other sectors for maintenance, as well as some of the salaries in the sector may be considered as seasonal.

b. Environmental impact

According to Mathieson and Wall (2006) it is stated that 'tourism has the power to change and modifying the environment'. Tourism sector has given continuously a great contribution to the environment. During the past decade the tourism industry has introduced a variety of tourist destinations worldwide. According to Aguay (2011) the development of tourism leads to an improved environment. This comes because of different marketing and promotional activities that promote and advertise natural, historical, cultural sites and beauty

which are considered unique for a destination. This is related to the protection of sites that become attractive to tourists. Furthermore, the protection and maintenance of these sites or environments brings more tourism to the destination which is converted to higher income and better standards of living.

On the other hand, it cannot be left aside the impact that tourism sector has on the social and cultural life. The tourism sector impacts negatively to the environment as well. Issues such as pollution and littering, overuse, and the possibility to lose the natural landscapes and cultural and historical sites, exposure and destruction of flora and fauna which makes the environment lose its values and uniqueness.

c. Social and Cultural Impact

According to Kreag, (2001) it is stated that the impact of tourism sector on the community it is stronger than in other categories. Continuously, what is more important is that a community has to maximise the positive impacts of tourism by the time it minimises negative aspects. This comes because of the impact of changes of attitudes and perspectives (Kread,2001).It is important to have a close interaction between both tourists and the community to benefit from new opportunities.

Tourism mostly impacts on the social life of a community by improving the quality of life, making new friends, sharing, and learning from different experiences, meeting new people who can be interesting and share information within a community who can benefit from the growth of tourism because of cultural and educational exchange, which means a better understanding of the values and traditions that a community holds. In terms of the negative aspect or influence that tourism has upon society and community are closely related to the impact on economy and environment, issues such as seasonal jobs, changes of lifestyle. Negative impact on traditions and values, Exposure to drinking, drugs and other habits are a concern for society and local community because of the adaptation of such habits and some of community values and traditions become lost.

Negative effects from the tourism impact are not new as whenever there is movement there are influences and impacts, but as Kreag (2001)has stated that it is more important to develop the tourism sector for the community by increasing the positive influence while reducing or assimilating the negative impact. However, as the coin has two sides, the impact of tourism has its negative aspects as well in terms of economy, environment, and social-cultural categories. These negative aspects do not decrease the levels of tourism growth, but it is the community who faces the consequences rather than the industry itself.

2.1.2 Trends of the Tourism Industry

According to Quantanilla, (2017) tourism is shifting its trends and looking forwards, tourism not only as a holiday destination but take into consideration factors that demonstrate safety. In terms of global tourism, the shift in trends of tourists has already started to be present on the choices of destinations. Tourists are tending to look to wellness travel which focuses on maintaining a healthy life of tourists to balance it with everyday routine. Sustainable tourism is where tourists are focusing towards destinations that are safe and sustainable and friendly destinations. This is mostly aiming to promote the adventures in nature and friendly environments. Travelling alone is the last tendency that is predicted for 2017 as individuals can enjoy freedom and experience of travelling, but some travel solo in terms to get stronger and feel more confident.

2.1.3 Challenges of the Tourism Industry

Tourism is one of the fastest developing sectors globally, and it has lots to face. In terms of global challenges in tourism, these have been identified by Martin Lohamm for Tourism Review (2012). He stated that there is a need for individuals and organisations operating in the tourism industry to know what is challenging it and how to fix it. He identified four major challenges that need to be considered in the tourism sector in the coming years.

- a) Globalization in terms of how it is going to be dealt with the four challenges and environmental issues that are directly affected by globalization.
- b) Cost and Benefits is about the interaction between the profits of business from tourists and so the tourists can gain their relaxing and enjoyable stay. According to Lohamm (2012), there should be control of negative aspects of tourism promotion otherwise tourism will be in danger and so would the environment.
- c) Adaptation is mostly to do with the change of demographics and other changes that might occur in tourism industry. Changes that are needed to be accepted and adapted by operators or businesses in the tourism industry. This change occurs in demographics needs to be adapted by tourists.
- d) Self-control is where it is understood that the destinations should avoid over capacity and keep safe their values and uniqueness of the destination by controlling the sector and by introducing tourism products in the right period to avoid over-capacity. This is

also related with businesses that operate in tourism industry to keep the level where it stands and improve it without losing values.

However, every destination is different, and challenges are different considering the level of development, types of tourism, politics and plans of developments and so on.

2.2 Role of technology in the tourism industry

The tourism sector is one of biggest sectors where technology has found a wide usage. According to Pease and Rowe (2007) technology is one of the few sectors that has shown and will show dominance in the tourism industry because of fast and useful information for customers. One of the most important components of technology is the internet and this is considered as a key requirement for the tourism sector. It helps to improve activity and progress of tourism organisations. There is an interaction between customers and tourist organisations in terms of communication and demand of touristic products Buhalis (2006) states that technology is used as a technique that makes possible the exchange of information, by creating the appropriate channel of communications between customers and tourist agencies of a destination. Customers can identify and fulfil the needs and requirements in terms of tourist products. On the other hand, are the tourism suppliers that deal with the complexity of tourist demands and requirements. According to Vong (2012) application of technology is influencing and changing the tourism industry because of the facilities that are provided for the sector.

Most tourism destinations use technology as a tool to promote the destination and improve the experience of travelling. If before the travel experience started, by the time a person reaches the destination, this might have changed. Twist (2016) states that technology advances have made possible that travel experience starts by the time tourists plan and organize their holidays. Due to information provided in the tourism sector, nowadays tourists do not consider any longer promotion through word of mouth as it is not based on facts and decide to consider information provided online. Information that in most of the cases shapes and affects the process of taking decisions towards a destination. According to Tourism and More,(2011) it is stated that technology has brought facilities in terms of time saving, such as easy of online reservation and bookings, airline reservations and so on, which makes it easier for the business to control through online systems rather deal personally and face to face with each tourist. However, this is affected on two sides. First, this leads on a reduction of human power which can be used somewhere else where computers cannot substitute manpower and

on the other hand is the way organisations use the information that is collected to keep in contact with customers and target new potential tourists and become more aware of demands and needs.

The internet is one of the components of technology which is mostly used by tourism organisations and business to communicate, promote, distribute, and sell tourist products to potential customers through the online tool. According to e-Business (2004) this states that a large number of tourism organisations have an online page where customers can interact with other organisations for collaboration, get involved in transactions, provide information about offers and sell the product.

Electronic business has an impact not only on the tourism sector but lately is affecting other sectors as well as it is considered as a time saver and in most cases, there is no need to buy in shops as it is just delivered to you. Dreakins and Mochrie,(2004) have pointed out the significance impact of using technology in function of communications, and interactions between customers and suppliers. In the tourism industry electronic business focuses mostly on the promotional and marketing campaigns and selling products of tourism online. However. having an online page for a destination does not necessarily mean that a company is successful in the market. According to Buhalis (2003) for customers to reach competitiveness in the market adaptation of ICT is the right technology and method for collection and distribution of information for the organisation to benefit from it. This is supported by Sevrani and Elmazi,(2008) who state that although the cost of adaptation of ICT might be high for some small business in tourism sector it is also important to be competitive in the tourism market. Noti and Llazo, (2016) note that it is customers who would benefit from use and adaptation of technological improvements as there is more information provided about activities and products and there is a variety of products from where tourists can make choices.

ICT applications consist of the use of mobiles, internet, wireless services, and other digital devices that are usually used by tourists, organisations, and companies for promotional and marketing services. Use of these devices consists of making it easy for both customers and organisations to deal with their everyday duties. Since the growth of the tourism industry, there is an expectation that customer demands are going to increase as well.

Furthermore, adaptation of ICT leads in competitive advantage when it is combined with the proper marketing and promotional strategies. According to Sevrani *et. al* (2011)it is stated that here is a crucial need to understand customer needs and have sufficient knowledge of technology to be competitive and not fail. This is supported by Noti and Llazi (2016) as

the need for staff educated towards technology is required on tourism industry to deal with the job in the tourism industry. However, this requires continuous trainings and technical skills as the nature of jobs is different in each situation.

2.2.1 Impact of technology in the tourism sector.

According to the Tourism Embassy (2013) technology is one of the main indicators of tourism industry and as such it has a great impact and influence on the sector itself, but individuals as well. In terms of the sector impact is related with the usage and accuracy of information provided, services and tourist products. Continuously, the impact of technology is present in the marketing and promotion field as it changes the way of promoting, where and when to promote compare to before. It also indicates that the tourism sector needs to advertise to increase the understanding and awareness about tourist sites and buildings to protected these. This is related with social media activity in promotion focusing on new potential tourists. Ferreira, (2016) states that technology impact in tourism is crucial and cannot be avoided as it gives freedom of information not only to the sector but to customers as well and indicates that technology effects an increase of facilities on the tourism sector, and makes it possible that data is distributed faster, particularly an increase in facilities on mobile phones. Furthermore, advances on technology affect the way of living and the way business progress by using several apps on mobile phones. This is supported by Twist (2016) who states that technology makes it easier for individuals and organisation to do their everyday duties. Use of online software, booking sites, email, reservations, ensures that individuals choose easy ways to get in touch or collect information. Furthermore, the Guardian, (2016) indicates that the biggest impact technology has brought is globalisation. This impacts all sectors including tourism activity. On the other hand, Belcher,(2017) states that the impact of technology is not only positive but negative as well. Considering the information, negative impacts of technology consist in two major issues such as dependency and decrease of human work value. Dependency comes in terms of massive usage of internet, apps, and social media for different reasons such as food, travel, updates, and innovations. In other cases, there are people that are obsessed with technology as much and can hardly wait for new inventions to be available for individuals. In terms of decrease and loss of value in human work comes at a time when most of sectors are computerised and substituted by machines and less individual work is required.

2.2.1.1. Information and communication technology.

Nowadays technology interacts with and affects different sectors and industries that are closely related with the progress of a country. During the past decades, technology has been shaping the tourism industry worldwide by the introduction and adaptation of new innovations and tools by different businesses and organisations in this sector. Considering that internet and Information and Communication Technologies are both important tools of technology as they can bring continuous improvements and developments in the tourism industry. In some cases, ICT is relatively confused with the internet and is defined as an online platform. According to Ryssels *et, al.* (2004) ICT consists of different technological forms that make it easier for individuals and organisations to create, to communicate, to use and share the information in different methods and ways that can impact on increasing the progress of an organisation or destination.

Literature and the research area regarding ICT are broad and many researchers have been conducting research. Several studies consist in the use of ICT in relation with internet, as key determinant factors for promotional activities and improvements in the tourism sector Chung and Law, (2003) and Galloway,(2007). Zehrer and Hobbahn, (2007) consider ICT as a tool that improves information, and the usage of ICT has improved the techniques and ways about how information is collected, managed, and distributed to potential tourists.

Furthermore, Jadhav and Mundhe, (2011) state that ICT usage in the tourism industry consists of managing and inventorying the destination resources, sites, and attractions, identifying new tourist destinations for tourists, as well as managing and maintaining statistics regarding this sector. Considering levels of demands and requirements by tourists nowadays, ICT has become a great helper for businesses and organisations, especially those operating in tourism, to use information provided by customers/tourists through several online platforms to improve their image, performance and expanding business towards a new market as well as towards new products. In this case it is important to state that ICT in collaboration with internet helps destinations modify and improve their products or services when it is needed depending on the customer/tourists demands and requirements. This is also supported by a study from Buhalis *et al* (2004) in which analyses the contribution and impact that ICT has upon tourist destinations and organisations by considering ICT as a technique to communicate, promote and sell the tourist products through online platforms. What is of high importance on the tourism sector and usage of ICT is the identification of appropriate

communication channels that provide an increase of interaction between tourists and organisations which leads on identification and improvements of products and services.

According to Sevrani *et al.* (2011) it is stated that the interaction between the organisation and customers/tourists is a key factor that may change based on the type of destination or business. This directly impacts the usage of internet and ICT which is closely related and depends on characteristics of a destination or organisation. The usage of ICT influences the commitment and progress of a business or destination. In the same way this progress can influence the ICT usage when it is adapted and used by different organisations and sectors means that ICT should be closely related to strategies and promotional activities.

However, this should be compatible with the nature of the organisation. According to Rodoula *et al.* (2012), there are analyses of indicators that influence the usage of ICT. Such indicators include both sides of supply and demand interaction. As tourist destinations depend on the information that is provided for their customers it is important to mention that this information must be accurate and continuously updated. Tourists or the demand side is always on the hunt for updated information and collect all necessary information and details that concern them to come up with a decision to travel or to buy the products.

On the other side stands the supply indicator, which in this case is either a tourist destination or organisation, is responsible to provide and promote suitable and valuable information which ends up as profits. Information that is provided consists of different issues such as image, products/services, activities and offers which is communicated to customers through communication channels and influences both tourist perceptions and tourists' decision-making processes.

ICT is considered as a strong strategic tool that with internet collaboration motivates and creates new opportunities for organisations and destinations to increase their progress towards communication and promotion to increase numbers of tourists and widen tourist targeting maps. In the case of influences ICT is also influenced by online platforms, especially from the social media which many businesses have found help to increase their productivity.

According to Hays *et al.* (2012) and WTO(2001)state that the online promotional techniques and strategies has given organisations in the tourism sector the opportunity to use ICT as a technique to improve and increase the progress of a business through digital means. Through social media, there exist a stronger communication channel which allows tourists to exchange information between them, not including the supply. This interaction includes the feedback information based on self -experience regarding different issues and in this case

mostly regarding tourist products/services and touristic destinations. In the tourism sector the use of ICT sometimes is considered as an advantage that is needed to be adapted strategic tools for further improvements and promotional activity indicators. According to Buhalis (2003) such advantage comes from the level of contribution that ICT brings to and such determinants consist of:

- a. Transforms the operational practices by providing more opportunities for tourist agencies and tour operators in order to improve and expand on their business,
- b. Value adding through use of ICT and its right indicators by providing strategic tools in industries network that adds more value to the products that are presented to tourists as well as improving interactions between organisations,
- c. Competitive advantage by using ICT in tourism mostly in countries such as Albania where tourism sector is still in the development process, it protects the destinations and its components as they all compete in a market that is essential to have competition advantage and ICT combined with traditional ways of advertising, that means destinations have this advantage.
- d. Reduction of costs through use of ICT has an impact on the reduction of effective costs to help the tourism industry to take advantage through competitors as it offers great opportunities for further development of the destination by reducing costs and increasing profits and numbers of tourists that come and spend in the destination. This makes it possible that the sector of tourism itself creates advantages by being unique and creates different ways of promotion, presenting high value and unique products and activities that reduces cost and increases profits.

2.2.2 Use of technology

Nowadays, using smartphones, laptops and cameras is a luxury that everyone has adopted. Technology is in every aspect of everyday life. Technology has progressed and advanced over time and its impact has been different for every sector. Technology advances have influenced everyday life because it has been a facilitator. It has made each day more flexible and more practical in terms of medicine where technology advances have saved lives, in terms of education, technological advances have increased teaching and learning techniques which has led to enhancing knowledge for younger generations.

In terms of businesses, technology has become a crucial component in developing business and increasing productivity. The tourism sector has been one of the first sectors that have applied and adapted online businesses of this sector. Advances in technology fields have introduced to humanity a variety of software, hardware, machines, applications, programs, and tools that in one way or another are today part of the everyday life. As the main interest of this research is the tourism and travel sector, also it comes as the principal focus of usage of technology in this field.

According to Smith (2016) who stated that by taking into consideration the nature of the businesses and products and services that are offered in this sector it is important to mention that technology plays a crucial role in the development of this sector and well as giving opportunity for businesses to develop and expand. By giving this opportunity, technology has been the focus for tourist organisations because it allows a continuous communication channel with customers. This is available only through technological components such as the internet, reservation and computer systems and other tools that create the communication channels to be more vivid and accurate.

According to an article by the Tourism Embassy (2013) it states that both the tourism sector and technology have similarities and cannot do without each other. Tourism Embassy (2013) suggests that technology has been used and it is still in use in several areas which have modified or changed the sector. Technology is used widely in the tourism Industry in the sense that it takes the role of the communication channels, promotional devices, marketing tools and so on. However, most sectors in the travel and service industry have been impacted by the development of technology.

- The first sector that is impacted from the use of technology is the service sector. Without the application of technology and its usage, the tourism sector has been providing a poor and low standard services to customers due to traditional service ways.
- Secondly, the transportation sector and its service has been affected by technology usage. Due to competition in the market, transport companies have now introduced low costs and low prices which makes it easier for customers to compare prices and transportation services by choosing the most suitable and convenient trips and services for themselves.
- Thirdly, the communication sector is the main sector that is influenced by technology and its advancements. Communications channels that are created by

using technology and its means, are important because customers and suppliers exchange information regarding products, services and offers that organisation can provide.

In the tourism industry, technology is closely related with online sources and services, online promotion, selling, booking, and reserving. Another reason why use of technology is important in the tourism sector is because it is used for marketing and promotional activities through the internet, online websites, and social media. The internet is one of the main components that allows the industry to advance and create more opportunities for businesses to develop through online means. To be able to maintain this online connection and communication channel, businesses use technology and through their computer and reservations systems this allows collection and transfer of available information and personal data for and from customers. This process applies to information regarding products and services to let customers know of what is offered. Furthermore, reservation systems are systems that can easily be accessed by both supplier and customer without the need of being in front of each other. This system allows customers to match and contrast products and prices and allow businesses to be in touch and keep records of employees, work and keep branches of a business connected.

2.2.2.1 General trends of technology usage

Nowadays, being updated and informed has become a trend for humanity. Technology itself has become a trend not only for the younger generation but for all ages and professionals, businesses and so on. Adaptation and application of the latest inventions or buying the latest model of mobiles and laptops or televisions has become the focus for almost everyone. Having the latest versions of mobiles, cameras or computers makes technology a crucial component of peoples' lives. In terms of businesses, creating new ways to communicate, finding sites to promote their business and products, opportunities to sell goods and services and increasing profits makes technology a requirement for development and maintaining the business. Considering trends of the tourism industry, technology is following and adding more attention to the communication channels with customers. Similarly, it provides various facilities regarding access to tourist products and services. One of the main trends that technology in the tourism industry is going towards is mobile communication. The substitute of services provided by agencies, computers and laptops have recently been shifted and substituted by mobiles due to the advancements that technology has brought for such devices.

By improving services, smartphones, mobiles, and cloud phones are programmed to do similar services to those provided by computers. Services provided by laptops and computers are considered as services such as emailing, word typing, pictures, recording, collecting data and ability to store. A device which is lighter, smaller, and multi-functional, has made it easier for people to deal with everyday tasks. In terms of size, mobile phones are smaller and can fit into pockets. This makes it unnecessary to bring and use laptops to navigate online, check tickets, get notifications, receive email and reply to email, when this service can be provided by the mobiles. Furthermore, people currently use mobiles to buy and sell good through online processes.

Communication through the mobiles is a relatively recent trend because of the facilities it provides and services it offers, but one main issue is that through mobile communication, it is sure that customers can be reached. This is in comparison to emails or member accounts that people do not use that frequently during the day. Moreover, mobile communication is currently being used by organisations and agencies as a safe and quick way to promote and sell their goods or services, known as telemarketing.

According to Importance of Technology (2017) it suggests various trends that technology is going towards. Mobile communication, and social media continues to be a strong trend for technology and especially in the tourism sector due to the large number of users. Due to wide participation, businesses as well as individuals can use social media for marketing and promotional services. It helps organisations or suppliers to target different groups of people at the same time. Another reason why social media is used as a marketing and promotional campaign is due to its affordable and cheaper services.

2.2.2.2 Challenges that technology faces

Even though technology is expected to bring development and innovations, it is noted that technology itself faces several challenges. Considering both trends and uses of technology, it is important to mention that some cases are difficult for technology to be adopted and applied. As the world is competitive, it has many issues that can cause problems and has its advantages and negative aspects. Challenges that technology is facing is in terms of customer satisfaction and loyalty or other trust and of course this is related to customer behaviour. Customer behaviour is related to the idea that some types and kinds of businesses cannot control any longer loyalty towards their customers due to huge variety of businesses that sell similar products and services. Challenges regarding technology are related to the idea that

customers are shopping both online and stores and this creates confusion. This gives customers an ability to be flexible in buying and choosing the company where they buy from instead from only one source.

The second challenge that technology faces is customer trust or loyal customers. The complexity and variety of websites, the huge number of applications and sites where customers are required to add their personal information such as their identity, name, phone number, email address, home address and other details makes this system rather disturbing to customers. This is a result of increased number of online hackers and fake webpage that only work to misuse personal information of their customers. Because of such online pages, companies that seriously operate through online must be careful and consider information from their customer as crucial, of high importance and confidential. Another point in this stage are fake organisations that operate in the online system and do not deliver the service they say or the quality of products they make customers pay for. This makes customers lose their trust and belief, not only the company that sells the goods, but they lose trust in online shopping.

2.3 Theoretical Aspects of Information Technology

Nowadays, the world is facing rapid innovation of technology and this is changing the way that individuals perform their tasks. Considering that information technology is used in most of the development fields such as financial, hospitality, management, service and beyond it is important to mention that there has been a serious commitment in developing various theories and models about information technology, its usage and the customer behaviour or attitudes towards performance and development. Vantakeshet *al* (2016) indicate that to obtain a clearer understanding towards certain factors that signify the use of information technology, it is important to have a deeper understanding on the models and theories that are used to study the information technology usage.

Most theories are not developed especially for the tourism industry, but most of them can be applied so long as it includes issues of using information technology and customer behaviour. Some of these theories and models that are compatible and have found a wide application in tourism industry are:

- Technology Acceptance Model –TAM,
- Web Acceptance Model –WAM,

- Task Technology fit Model –TTF,
- Contingency Theory,
- The United Technology of Acceptance and use of Information Technology – UTAIA.

2.3.1 Technology Acceptance Model (TAM)

Considering that nowadays technology is used in most research fields, it is important to mention that there has been a great contribution towards developing different models and theories about the use of technology and its effects towards customers (organisations or individuals). The technology acceptance model was designed by Davis (1989) with the intention to understand the behaviour of internet users towards information technology. According to Sabena *et al* (2014) TAM has inspired other theories towards the use of information technology. This model consists in two main factors such as perceived usefulness (PU) and perceived ease of use (PEU). PU is determined as the belief of a person towards a certain application for a better work performance. Whereas PEU is determined based on the belief that a certain person has towards the use of a certain application without any difficulty or effort for a better work performance.

Source: Davis *et al.* (1989, p. 985)

Figure 2.1 Technology Acceptance Model

According to Surendran (2012), the study includes consideration regarding what influences PU and PEU and suggests that PU and PEU are influenced by social, cultural, and political factors. Social factors include issues such as language, skills facilitating conditions. Cultural factors include different cultures of individuals or organisations whereas political factors focus mainly on the use of the technology in politics or other similar situations.

TAM has been a model which many researchers have tried to modify to create more options for applications and to introduce new perspectives and improvements under the model. Considering the literature about TAM and its usage and application, it is important to mention that for many years it has been considered an important model in using information technology and adopting new technological innovations. The literature about TAM is broad including TAM importance, but similarly many articles consider certain limitations and criticism about the Technology Acceptance model.

According to Ajibade (2018) who has criticised TAM in the aspect of its available literature because it usually tends to define it as a dependent variable instead of an important factor which influences behaviour. On the other hand, Zahir and Asgraf (2013) refer to TAM as a not completed model because it does not take into consideration factors such as age, education which can influence the acceptance and use of the information technology. Hence, the Technology Acceptance Model has been continuously modified into TAM2 which is focused more in adding different variables that enrich technology acceptance.

According to Hoong *et al* (2016) Tam2 suggests that individuals are influenced by the relation of their work and the performance results of using the system. The last modification from TAM into TAM3 is where certain elements are used in order to explain the level of the belief of using computers and on the other hand TAM3 uses other elements to understand the level of belief that is influenced by existing experience towards using a certain technology.

2.3.2 Web Acceptance Model (WAM)

According to Castenada (2007) the web acceptance model(WAM) it is a new form of model that was retrieved by the original model of TAM to help organisations/businesses to predict individual perceptions on visiting a certain website. The web acceptance model is not a new discovery in the use of technology, but it is developed based on TAM, but considers different prospective of a technological model. The focus of the new model is to understand the usage of certain websites by applying the elements of the Technology Acceptance Model. In contrast to other models that focus on the individual or organisation level of predicting, the Web acceptance model focuses on the understanding the experience receive by using certain internet apps or websites. According to Castenada (2007) it is stated that perceived ease of use has resulted in it being more effective and it is an important factor in revisiting a certain website for those individuals who are less experienced in visiting websites. Whereas on the other side, its perceived usefulness results in it being more effective on those individuals that

have more experience in using websites. Hence, these elements help website designers to add on the website what is necessary and similarly they should remove extensive information from the website to present a more effective website.

2.3.3 Task technology fit model (TTF)

Task technology fit model (TTF) it is another theory which is widely used in the evaluation and the prediction of the Information Technology usage. As technology is nowadays highly connected and integrated within the tourism industry, this model together with TAM has found wide usage in the tourism industry especially in the field of electronic tourism. As a technological model it dates to 1995 developed by Goodhue and Thompson (1995) with the intention to evaluate an explain the use of the Information Technology from a certain perspective to the task level. Usoro, *et al* (2010) suggest that the TTF model was based on the evaluation of information technology usage to an individual level until the theory was redeveloped by Zilgurs and Buckland (1998) with the intention for it not to be used only at individual levels, but for groups and organisational evaluation.

Source: Goodhue and Thompson, (1995)

Figure 2.2 Task-Technology Fit Model

Usoro *et al* (2010), highlight another important point by comparing and evaluating both TAM and TTF. Respectively, TAM consists in individual perceptions of using a certain system which results to be the key factor towards usage and adaptation of that specific system whereas on the other hand is TTF consists of the point that a certain system is going to be adapted and used in order to fulfil successful objectives of a certain task without taking into consideration the individual perceptions, attitudes or behaviours.

Considering this combination, it is important to mention that both models consist of individual attitudes and perceptions towards the use of certain systems to fulfil tasks and increase their work performance.

2.3.4 Contingency Theory in the use of Information Technology

Contingency theory is another theory which contributes and helps in the technology field when applied to different businesses. The focus of using contingency theory, according to Baranyi (2001) is that this theory develops an effective solution for the organisation in any circumstances. Many researchers have studied contingency research as it dates early and has been used in business for a long time until new aspects were developed. According to Doban-Antal (2010) it is suggested that with new perspectives of contingency theory, organisations can apply different solutions depending on circumstances and other factors. Furthermore, the main components in contingency theory are technology and environment. Betts (2003) states that the way a business is organised is totally dependent on the environment where a business operates.

Figure 2.3 Structural Contingency Theory

Source: (Betts, 2003)

Other researchers such as: Pugh *et al* (1965), Woodward (1965), Perrow (1967), Thompson (1967), Child (1972) have studied contingency theory to present an easier and helpful model for organisational use. These researchers have considered the previous theory developed and then improved it where they think it should be seen from another perspective. According to Galbrouth (1973) and Scott (1992) who have studied the theory and have come up with various perspectives such as:

The study from Galbrouth (1973) consists of the point that there is no best way to organise and perform in a business. On the other hand, Scott (1992) asserts that the results of this study consider that not all the organisational methods are effective. Hence, considering the above aspects has resulted in the idea that by applying Contingency theory can define the

performance of the organisation. Weil and Olson(1989) concluded that for better performance in information systems, there is the need for a better fit between the structure of the organisation and technology. Furthermore, this is supported by Buttermann *et al.* (2008) who state that contingency theory tries to predict organisational performance based on the relation between structure, strategy, and information technology.

As contingency theory is supported by many authors, it is also criticised based on the theory imperfections. Kieser (1995) and Dobak (2006) think that the theory should consider and cover more aspect of the organisational structure or processes. Kieser (1995) feels that:

- Contingency theory does not consider new characteristics (based on the organisation situation or structure),
- Contingency theory does not use appropriate methods for certain statistics,
- The results from the theory does not convey any new information,
- The structure of the organisation is not defined by the situation,
- The relation between situation and the structure of the organisation can change based on the culture nature.

Similarly, Dobak (2006) criticises contingency theory because:

- Studies should be more flexible and not fixed,
- There should more emphasis related to the process of change,
- Various issues such as conflict or organisational processes should have a wider coverage.

However, although there have been criticisms about the theory, many authors support the theory based on the contribution it brings to organisations to more effective.

2.3.5 The United Theory of Acceptance and use of Information Technology (UTAUT)

Considering Vankatesh *et al.* (2016), UTAUT is one of the latest theories that has been developed through inspiration from previous models or theories. The modification of those theories has given way to the UTAUT for fast growth. As it is stated in the name of this theory, UTAUT has been developed in 2003 by Vankatesh (2003) and since then it has been used in the Technology field. Similarly, it can apply to other fields so long as it includes customers and organisational issues. Vankatesh *et al.* (2007) have stated that UTAUT is one of the most important and most established models that covers in deep the study regarding information systems(Saker and Volacich,2010). By considering previous methods and models used in predicting behaviours and predicting the use of the information technology.

As a founder of UTAUT model Vankatesh *et al.*(2003) have revised the results of the previous models and used only the positive components of those theories to bring them all in one model UTAUT, and indicate four components and moderators, which have not been included in previous theories:

- Performance expectancy is considered the level of technology usage to bring to customers when using certain systems,
- Effort expectancy is the level of difficulty of using the technology,
- Social influence is considered when others influence the decision of using certain technologies,
- Facilitating conditions are considered the support that is received to perform a certain behaviour.

These components and moderators are supposed to be used to understand the process of predicting certain behavioural and intentions to use technology and its systems. According to Chao (2019), Vankatesh used some of the limitations and weaknesses of TAM in order to bring a stronger and more efficient model. Continuously, Chao(2019) and Vankatesh et al (2003) finalise UTAUT, when they combine elements from other models such as: Theory of Reasoned Action, Innovative Diffusion Theory, Theory of the Planned Behaviour, Technology Acceptance Model, combined TAM, Motivational model and the Model of PC Utilisation Social Cognitive Theory with the main focus of being more informative or predictive towards the new adaptation of technology(Carter and Belonger, 2004). According to Chao(2019) the contribution of UTAUT goes beyond ‘only predictions’ but it also clarifies technological use.

There are various advantages why organisations should use UTAUT to have a clearer understanding and come to solutions when they adopt new technologies. Based on literature and the information regarding UTAUT it is important to mention that the theory is one of the mostly used related to acceptance of technology, its usage and application of different information systems. Waehama *et al.*(2014) state that there is a good reason why UTAUT has found a wide application (even though it was developed not long ago)is because the model creates a clearer understanding by using positive aspects from eight different models in one. Continuously, other advantages are suggested based on UTAUT growth and usage. Confirmation of the theory’s validity, stability, and viability in using technology has contributed to the development of UTAUT. One of the most important advantages of UTAUT consists in the ability of this model to explain behaviour towards technology at a

higher level than previous ones. Hence, its growth has been rapid, and it has found a wide application.

However, many studies criticise aspects of the UTAUT model. UTAUT limitations consists of the fit between intention and use of behaviour. On the other hand, Mayer-Schonberger (2009) suggests that the UTAUT limitation should not be considered in comparison to the advantages that this model provides. However, many authors consider that research on the model should be done again in order to eliminate the limitations of the United Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology.

2.3.6 Service Quality and Customer Satisfaction

Considering the nature of the tourism industry and its operation, it is important to mention that service quality is one of the key factors that indicate success (Hudson et al., 2004, Tamilselvi, 2016). Many researchers have defined service quality as a process of fulfilling the needs and requirements of customers and similarly, it is a process that measures if the provided service meets up to customer expectations for that particular service (Bateson and Hoffman, 2011; Yoo and Park, 2007; Zeithaml, Parasuramin and Berry, 1990; Solomon, 2009; Kotler and Keller, 2009).

Many researchers have attempted to find out the way customers evaluate service quality for the received service (Atilgan, Akinci and Aksoy, 2003; Hudson *et al.*, 2004; Baker and Cropton, 2000) but this still requires further research. Another study from Frochot (2004) found that the evaluation of service quality is complex to measure while customers are on holiday due to the nature of the tourism industry as well as the intangible services provided.

From a businesses point of view, Hoghkhah (2011) suggests that businesses in the tourism industry should focus their attention in improving the service quality and increase customer satisfaction to create competitive advantage as well as loyal customers (Tian-Cole and Crompton, 2003). Similarly, Hoghkhan (2011), Heri (2017) and Cudjoe *et al.* (2015) suggest that service quality and customer satisfaction are closely related in the tourism industry.

Different studies have been researched in order to evaluate the relation between service quality and customer satisfaction (Zhao and Di Benedetto, 2013). According to Kumar (2017) service quality can be measured by considering different dimensions such as usefulness, responsiveness, reliability, privacy, and security, whereas other studies that focus on electronic service quality identify four dimensions to measure quality, these being:

reliability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy (El Saghier,2015; Chow,2017; Hahn *et al.*,2017). On the other hand, satisfaction is considered as the judgment if a product/service can fulfil the requirements of customers related to that product(Oliver,2010). Greenwell *et al.*(2002) suggest that customers who are satisfied from the quality of the services are more likely to be loyal and repurchase. On the other hand, Gineson(2007) and Milbourne (1998) state the importance of understanding satisfaction combined with the tourism industry can be tricky as customers who are less satisfied with the quality of the services tend to switch company/purchase rather than complain or give feedback(Sparks and Westgate,2002).

2.3.7 Models of Service Quality

Many previous researchers have identified several theoretical models related to service quality being online or not. Such models have been considered by the researcher when proposing the conceptual framework. It is important to state that most electronic service quality models have been developed based on the general models of service quality which have been measuring the quality of the services in a physical environment(Ingaldi,2016). General service quality model SERVQUAL, was developed by Parasuraman, Zeithaml and Berry in 1988 while conduction research in the retail industry to measure the quality from the customer point of view. This model has undergone various changes due to its adaptation in different sectors/industries. The first model SERVQUAL involved ten dimensions which were reduced to five dimensions, these being: tangibles (Physical facilities or environments); Reliability(ability to provide the promised service in the most reliable and accurate form); Responsiveness (the will and desire to help customers and provide high quality service); Assurance (the ability to inspire trust and security for customers) and Empathy (knowledge about customers and attention provided to them). This research continues and there is identification of autocorrection between dimensions(Ingaldi,2016).

Some studies have criticised theServqual model and its evaluation if the dimensions can be applied to different industries or environments. Even though the dimensions have been reduced to five, different authors have found that not all the dimensions can be appropriate to evaluate the quality of the electronic services (Joghee,2017). In research conducted by Tood*et al.*(2016) it was found that only 3 dimensions such as reliability responsiveness and assurance can be considered to evaluate the quality of electronic services.

Due to such limitations, the Servqual model was modified to SERVPERF which focuses on the attitude of the customer towards the quality of services(Cronin and

Taylor,1992). Singh and Puri(2018) suggests that the Servperf model only focuses and examines the performance of the realised service. Researchers have found the modified model to be superior (Jauin and Gupa,2014; Adil *et al.*,2013) because it can be applied to more industries and because it focuses in measuring the performance of customer attitudes. However, it is important to mention that both models have been widely used in the tourism industry by researchers online or in a physical environment to measure service quality and customer satisfaction(Kansra and Jha,2016;Kitapci *et al.*,2014).

According to Rita *et al.*,(2019)is stated that to adopt Servqual model into the digital/online business, many other models were developed such as the Webqual model(Woilfinborger and Gilly, (2003) and the E-S-Qual model by Parasuraman *et al.*(2005) which was developed as a new version of e-service quality models due to criticism of the Servqual model. These new models were developed based on the service quality scale to provide possibilities for it to be measured. E-S-Qual focused on measuring the quality of electronic services through customer expectation and perceptions, whereas the E-Reco-qual was developed to deal with problems faced by customers(Parasuraman *et al.*,2005). However, Blunt *et al.*(2016) found that even though the E-S-Qual model was developed to measure electronic service quality, it still faces difficulty when measuring or analysing the customer dissatisfaction.

The other model developed to measure the service quality is Webqual and it focuses on the evaluation of website quality in the tourism industry. The model was developed by Loiacono *et al.*(2002) and was composed of four main dimensions: usefulness(also found in TAM)Entertainment, ease of use and complementary relationship(Loiacono et al.,2002). A US study has suggested that complementary relationship should be substituted by trust and response time (Anand *et al.*,2015). On the other hand, Puriten and Rosen (2004) state that the content of the website is one of the key determinants of the loyal customers. Similarly, Azevedo(2009) states that websites are now considered important tools of marketing strategies. Furthermore, Garcia(2001)suggests that website content in the tourism industry has a strong relationship with quality of content and services that websites provide to customers as it is the service quality that makes the difference and creates competitive advantage. It is important to mention that the Webqual model can be used to evaluate the quality of the website considering both content and services. However, there are studies that suggest Webqual might need to be modified or combined with other models to demonstrate how customers perceive the service quality. Arif.*et al.*, (2013), state that the Webqual model

focuses more on the technical aspect of the website design and less on the customer perception of the quality from electronic services.

The main objective of the Servqual model has been to measure the quality of services in the physical environment, but in many cases, researchers have been attempting to apply it in measuring electronic services. To support this, different models were developed in order to complete the gaps of each other. Models such as E-S-Qual measures service quality of the electronic means through customer expectation and perception and Webqual focuses more on the technicality of the website. Many studies have suggested different positions of application for models. According to Mihalovic(2017) this suggests that as Webqual considers the technical side of the website, it cannot be used to measure the quality of services, unlike the E-S-qual model. Furthermore, another study suggests that both models can complete each other's gaps and can be used as combined models with common objectives to measure the quality of electronic services by using Webqual to improve the website design and content quality and E-S-qual model can treat customer experience from online services(Zeithaml *et al.*,2002).

2.4 Types of Technology

As mentioned earlier, technology has been of significant influence in all sectors, especially in tourism and travel sectors worldwide. Due to its development and improvement, technology has found wide and huge adaptation, which means individuals and businesses are advantaged due to its facilities and benefits provided to tourism industries. Technology has been developed and adapted because of the need that people need to be updated which led technology being improved in several directions and aspects.

According to different authors and researchers, the term technology has various definitions considering the sector where it is applied. According to Zeheer (2011) states that definitions about technology vary and differentiate according to the sector where and why it is used and agrees that the perception of individuals and businesses regarding technology, and its usage is currently changing and shifting from its traditional perception such as new computer and mobile phones, television, games, play-stations, digital devices and so on to a deeper and convenient perception of technology as a source for information enhancing knowledge. Similarly, this is supported by Ramey (2013) who considers technology as a wide field full of knowledge which takes account of producing and developing new tools, systems, software and applications towards any issue or problem to improve or solve it. In terms of

perceptions of individuals Ramey (2013) suggests that this perception varies according to the knowledge background of individuals based on their previous personal experience.

In a general meaning, technology is used in different industries such as Education, Medicine, Telecommunication, Economy, Tourism and Hospitality and more with the reason to develop, improve and increase the services of these sectors. Considering the nature and characteristics of the tourism sector, technology has driven its advances according to these characteristics for businesses and customers at the same time. In global terms, the impact of technology in the development of this sector has been strong, and in some cases, has shaped the whole sector and is changing developments. The National Assistive Technology Research Institute suggests that, except the fact that technology effects and impact all the development sectors, technology is known as useful technique towards the next invention and improvement of services. There are five different types of technology that can be used in a variety of sectors and industries either mixed or individually. The types of technology normally follow the characteristics of the sector where they are applied.

1. Information technology is one of the most important and fundamental types of technology, not only because it provides full information of what is around us, but it allows individuals to become informed and enhance knowledge regarding several issues, problems, and places. Information technology techniques are important that are currently adapted by most businesses all around the world. This type of technology is applicable in many sectors such as telecommunication, education, medicine, and many other businesses, but mostly has been having huge impact in the tourism and hospitality sectors due to their nature and characteristics. Considering this, the best example of the information technology type is the internet and during the past decade, has found usage worldwide by increasing variety of services, productivity and developing businesses.
2. The second type of technology is applied in the Educational sector and it is known as the technology of teaching. According to Wolery,*et al* (1992) this type of technology is focused on dealing with approaches, methods and techniques that find usage in different educational institutions and requires a controlled environment. Teaching technology includes different tasks, objectives and model that influence and has a good impact on the performance of the students by attracting attention and increasing their performance and enhancing their knowledge. This comes because of teaching technology as it involves this techniques and software or applications to increase the performance of teachers by giving examples to their students. An example of this type of technology are projectors and slide shares of documents.

3. The third type of the technology is known as the Instructional technology, which according to the Commission on Instructional Technology (1970) is defined as a well organised process which includes designing, carrying out and evaluating the way it is needed to be done, through teaching and learning processes. It involves processes which are programmed to be under regulations and work under rules to be successfully. Examples of this type of technology are mostly electronic devices such as CD- Room, DVD- s, and recording devices.
4. Another type of technology t is the Assistive Technology which in a direct way finds a focus the tools and processes that help individuals with disabilities to learn and communicate. Examples of this type of technology are eye-glasses and eye lent and special keyboards for typing and communication aids.
5. Another type of technology is related to the medical sector and is known as Medical Technology. This is related and focuses on technological advances in this sector. Medical Technology is different from advances of the science which deals with cures and advancements in finding new cures. Medical technology is mostly focused on machines, devices, tools, and techniques that are used in medicine sector and contribute to this sector by improving devices, services, and performance. Examples of this technology are tube feeding and kidney dialysis machines.
6. The last type of the technology is related to the field of technology itself. Productivity tools of technology are those that focus on the development of software and database applications that contribute to the everyday life of businesses and employers by increasing their performance and productivity of business.

Considering all the types of the technology it is recognized that technology is always going to impact and improve in the development of business, improving everyday performance and is always going to enhance knowledge and information.

2.4.1 Web-Based Technology

Web-based technology is an important part of technology which deals with online sources and tasks. This is a part of technology which focuses on online resources to improve or even develop a place, tourist destination, issue or solve problems. Web-based technology includes the internet which is its main component and aims to facilitate everyday life for individuals, employers and business.

Considering the name, web-based technology, somehow it gives the idea of what it deals with or the field of study. Considering the bases of this technology, it is important to mention that such a type of technology has facilitated the overall business in everyday tasks. Different innovations such as electronic databases, applications and apps have increased the development that has led companies to differentiate and gain competitive advantage in the market. In this sector, web-based technology focuses not only on the development of applications, but it gives options that through these applications businesses can receive valuable feedback regarding perception of tourists towards development of destination, product or service. Customer feedback is important and crucial to maintain high customer service and improve when is necessary.

The main objective of services of improved applications in Tourism and Travel is tourist perceptions. Due to the high sensitivity and complexity of the tourism industry, it leads to the need to be supported by updated and improved applications. There is the need to mention that web-based technology does not include only the applications, but it includes software and programs that are in a coherent relation with the information technology to bring the deserved result.

According to Fericelli *et al.*(2013) it is stated that the tourism industry has been through precipitous changes in different aspects from customers, with perceptions and replacements, as well as on the supplier side. This leads to the understanding that products, services, marketing, and promotion campaigns have been improved due to information technology.

2.4.1.1 New application of technology and their usage in the tourism industry in general

Customers can now explore not only information but pictures and videos as well. Before, customers were able only to search for information, but this is recently changed due to Web 2.0 that allows customers not only to search but to change, comment, identify and buy different products and services. According to Hays *et al*, (2012) there is another stage of the application called Web3.0 which deals with information that is recognised by the computer to interact with other devices. According to Chabot,(2007) the most known applications of Web 2.0 are blogs, hotel ratings, forums, podcasting, social media and so. Most of these applications we face now can navigate everyday life activity.

- Blogs: online pages that give possibility to individual to write, post, comment, exchange and interact information about certain topics. Siagala, (2007) argues that

blogs not only exchange information, but they are important for organisations as they understand the power of promotional activity and find space for improvements and changes for future. Continuous forums give possibilities to discuss different topics.

- Hotel rating system give possibilities to individuals to give ratings to the hotels based on their experiences.
- Podcasting is an important application in most sectors not only in tourism. This is referred as uploading of videos, images, and audios in different online pages.
- Social media has large numbers of users and is becoming a main application in terms of promotion from tourist organisations because large numbers of participants, so it is easier for tourism organisation to reach customers.

According to UNWTO (2013) this method is not only used by individuals but from organisations that exchange valuable information through images, videos, and conferences. Considering all this information, it is important to indicate that the main focus for all applications are customers and as such it is obvious that nowadays customers have the power and the control of decision-making processes. Technology has always shaped tourism such as destinations and organisation operating in the sector need and must adopt new methods to create competitiveness in the market. We must consider that customers are interacting with information by looking for more flexible services, more common initiatives, specialised and continuous communication with suppliers.

2.4.1.2 Social Media

Interpersonal influence and word of mouth are classified as the most important sources of information when customers take a decision to buy a service. These influences are important in tourism; intangible products are difficult to assess prior to their consumption when oral word become digital, scaling, anonymity, etc promote new ways to analyse interpretation and management influences that consumers can have. (Litvin, Goldsmith and Pan, 2008)

Social media plays an important role on every aspect of travel and tourism. According to Koplou and Haenlein, (2010) social media is described as the use of digital means for different reasons. The main purpose of social media is communication, and it is widely used as advertising and promotional tools for tourism destination, organisations, and sites where individuals sell goods, tourism products and services.

Furthermore, nowadays social media makes it easier for individuals to search for information of any kind like employment sites, where you can see potential job positions.

Most importantly it is considered as a digital means that allows you to get in touch with people you might know. Heinonen (2011) states that being active in the online network has become a trend and an obsession for most individuals who most of the time are interacting with different activities, exchanging information and materials, as well as participating in different discussions and sharing opinions regarding different topics.

Online networks or social media is one of the networks that has the biggest number of users and still most of them do not fully recognize or define it (Hysi, *et al* 2015). Different authors and individuals bring various emphasis of social media definitions, but it is difficult to exactly define it. Social media, according to Safko and Brake (2009) is defined as a group of individuals who interact, participate and discuss on the online world by liking, tweeting, posting and sharing various information about different topics. As interaction and number of cases are large, social media has a great impact on businesses as well. However, it is important to mention that in most cases the impact of social media differs from one sector to another. In the case of the tourism sector, social media performs a key role in the development of organizations and destinations.

According to Hysi *et al* (2015), social media influences the way how tourism sector, organizations and destinations improve their sales. The online sale in the tourism sector has become important for the sector as it makes it increase the profitability and the performance of the destinations. Continuously, this performance in online networks, especially social media, has increased and improved the marketing activities of the destinations. Marketing and promotion through social media have become a trend today as it is easier for organizations and destinations to reach their customers through the online platform. This has become popular and affects the tourism sector as well. There are advantages and disadvantages of using social media for promotion of tourism products, services, or destinations.

According to Zimmerman and Sahlin (2011), advantages of using social media as a promotion consist of:

- reducing cost of advertising,
- targeting large numbers of social media users,
- increase business opportunities,
- improvement brand image and name.

On the other hand, disadvantages consist of trained staff needed to maintain the social platforms, and not every individual, potential customer is a user of social media which leads

on the need for further advertisements and of course it requires continuous time and commitment to maintain and update the information provided.

Furthermore, there are clues and pages that are specific to one type of product such as skiing or studying or adventurous products. In this case, it is important to mention that potential customers are influenced and stopped by this kind of promotion as it can affect their decision process.

According to Social media marketing for tourism industry (2012) more than 50% of people who decide to travel, post photos and comment about their experience in social media or in different blogs. These actions have a positive impact on people behaviour and thus the process of word mouth begins. Social media is attributed to low cost, that is the reason for large numbers of participants from both parts, different business area and customers (Irvine and Anderson, 2009). The key factor of success in this context is the constant need for people to be active in the social network.

Social media such as: Twitter, Facebook and Instagram are growing at a high rate in terms of numbers of users, as well as their role in terms of interoperability consumers. Social media are turning into important marketing tools for the management organizations of tourist destinations, having a great impact on tourism markets. Organizations and customers from all over the world can exchange valuable information, videos, images, consumer reviews, forums, and discussions. (UNWTO,2013).

2.4.1.3 Mobiles and Smartphones

Generally, every industry is affected by the massive use of 'smart' telephony. The definition is generally used to describe any mobile phone that combines communication with sophisticated technologies used as access to the internet and the options offered to download various applications. The latest generation was introduced by Apple, with its renowned iPhone brand. Since then, a wide range of smartphones with highly competitive brands are using these technologies. From this widespread growth in both the manufacturers and smartphone users and the many applications they contain, the tourism industry is heavily influenced.

Smartphone technology is becoming a most useful method and is working and performing the same functions as laptops, computers, and more. In general, every industry is affected from the massive use of the smart technology. The latest generation is introduced by companies like Apple, Android, and IOS which embrace a competitive market. From this

growth, in terms of producers and users, the smart technology of phones and many new applications they contain, have greatly influenced the tourism industry. According to Premchaiswodi, 2010 mobile phones are built and provide a high efficiency of cameras and GPRS to connect to the internet. Argyropoulou *et al* (2010) agree that mobile technology is one of the greatest technologies developed and introduced and provided to individuals. Mobile electronic devices will continue to provide tourism with new opportunities to attract consumers through many applications to help them to source cheap tickets, restaurants, museums, archaeological and zoological parks etc. There is a wealth of services that can fully aid travellers and facilitate anytime travelling at a low cost.

Benefits from smartphone options affect tourists directly during the process of gathering information, reading, comment on various services as they have a significant impact during and after holiday season, (Hannes, 2010). It is important to mention that mobile phones are currently being used for marketing and promotional activities as according to Karthikeyan and Balamurgan, (2012) promotion through mobile phones makes it easier for destinations and tourism organisations to reach their target customers without considering the place or time. Considering that nowadays, almost every adult individual possesses a modern mobile phone, such promotion is considered as a communication channel with two directions. Through this promotional channel is created an interaction between both tourists and destination where information and feedback exchange take place. Moreover, considering these continuous changes in the tourism sector it is important to mention that promotional activities are distributed through different devices and applications where it finds huge usage such as social media and mobiles which are major indicators of online promotion.

2.4.1.4 Uses of the internet for future development

According to Visser (2004), considering the variety of studies that have been conducted on the topic of importance of using internet in the tourism sector and elsewhere, it is clearly understood that the internet has been introduced to people and has impacted hugely in the everyday life of individuals as well as improving businesses and developing new ones.

Standing *et al* (2014) states that the internet has a two-sided impact, on both customers and the supply side. As mentioned in the literature review, the internet facilitates procedures and makes it easier for both customers and suppliers to obtain what they require. On the supply side the internet gives the opportunity to share information about products and services, and what they provide. It also allows suppliers to obtain feedback from potential

customers after they reach them through the internet. On the other side, potential customers are informed on what is available in the market. By being informed they can ascertain potential risks and securities and in touch with other customers who might have visited first.

Cristiana (2008) states that the tourism sector has been one of the first sectors to go online and use the internet for its services. This goes further by mentioning functions that the internet has brought into the travel industry, such as online booking, ticket reservations, accommodation and so on. What is most important to mention is the fact that communication is the crucial facility that is brought into the tourism sector by the internet and its online software and applications. Nowadays, most of organisations and businesses of every sector have a wider usage of the internet and databases. According to Batinic (2013), because of the internet, it is easier to transfer information through communication networks. Through communication via satellite, businesses find it easier and quicker to transfer data and information worldwide. Continuous development and advancements of technology and the internet allows information of everything to be accessed easier and faster from every corner of the world. Tourism has been the first sector to adapt internet. According to Batinic (2013) this has brought changes for the sector and customers which makes the internet a great component for further development. Considering that development starts from the organisations in the tourism sector, agencies and organisations are affected by the internet and benefit from this invention by:

- a) Creating an identity website or portal from where information is distributed from what is offered and collected in terms of customer requirement.
- b) The internet gives most organisations the ability to become bigger and expand the business based on websites and internet systems where data and information can be early transferred, and business can be more flexible.
- c) Expansion of business in the tourism industry in collaboration means the internet give opportunities to businesses and agencies to develop booking systems through accommodation, airline, car rental companies and so on.
- d) Decrease costs due to the internet in terms of distribution as it is cheaper through online means.
- e) The internet allows businesses to research their market and customers cheaply and through time saving processes.

By considering these changes, adaptation of the internet has brought about changes that affect not only the businesses, but customers as well. Customers gain from the change by being able to recognise what is the level of the services provided, what products are provided,

destinations and of course being able to find this information on the variety and competition in the tourism sector. Have competition between organizations brings better performance, service and updated and a variety of products at lower prices.(Buhalis, 2003).

Considering certain academic manuscripts and publications it can be appreciated that the internet plays an important role in the promotion of tourism products and services (Cristine, 2008;Batinic, 2013; Hall, 2014).By becoming crucial in promotional campaigns, the internet is seen as a tool for companies and organizations for improvement and development of organizations. This is due to the advantages that the internet has as a company/business developer and its importance in the last decade has increased (Avcikurt *et al.*,2011).The internet is seen as a business developer because it is considered as time saving, cutting costs and it is easier to share information and create proper communication channels between customers and suppliers.

At this point it is important to mention that extensive adaptation of the internet comes with certain negative impacts either to companies or customers themselves. These negative aspects are closely related to the design of the website, its purpose and the information provided for customers. Research from Noti (2012) affirms negative aspects of using the internet:

- Increase the awareness regarding a certain website purpose in order to understand the information provided for the customers. In some cases, business can be eager to promote their products including goods or touristic services and they forget to mention what is the purpose of their website. This is confusing for customers and destroys their confidence in the website.
- Internet users come from different cultures and their perception towards certain information is different. At some point businesses should classify the information they provide based on target customers. Being precise in given information can avoid confusion for customers.
- Extensive information is seen as a negative aspect. In many cases, business tend to include lots of information on their websites to provide as much information they can for potential customers. In this process it is forgotten that too much information gets customers lost, and in some cases, businesses forget the main issue of providing information.

Such issues have been discussed by Mathur *et al.*(2008) and at the same time are compared to traditional printed material. From their research it was revealed that the speed of reading a internet material is slower by 30% compared to printed materials.

This comes as a result that some webpage should allow themselves to have lower graphical and visual effect in order to allow a quicker download of the webpage. Furthermore, as suggested by Marthuret *al*(2008) most of webpages do not fulfil their objectives due to confusion and bad organisation of the website. Moreover, Patterson (2003) indicates the importance of understanding what is required in a well organised webpage which presents appropriate information for the reader.

Considering the literature review and information regarding website, the researcher came across two models which measure the quality of the website and identifies the key factors for the webpage to succeed. According to WTO (2008), AIDA and 2QCV3QVMeta Model are two of the most recommended models that help tourist destinations to identify key factors for a most effective webpage. In other articles by Buhalis and O'Connor(2005) and Hamilet *al*(2011), they evaluated the use of key factors that are covered by both models. According to them, both models consist of focusing technical issues such as performance, access and navigation and do not cover the identification of various technical uses or applications.

According to Meera *et al*(2019), AIDA model usage dates early and since then it continues to be used as an important model in the website evaluation. WTO (2008) and Li and Yo (2013) identify the definition of AIDA:

Figure 2.4The AIDA model

Source: *Li & Yu (2013)*

A- Attention

Information provided on the website should contain information (in the type of text or picture) that should attract the attention of potential customers. This phase should raise the awareness of certain information.

I- Interest

Information provided in the webpage should be interesting for the customer. The information provided should give new knowledge to the customer for a certain issue.

D- Desire

The webpage should attract attention, be interesting, and should create in customers an emotion or desire to be loyal to a brand or be more favourite towards a certain information.

A- Action

This is the phase where customers are happy and convinced with the information provided and are willing to take further action in the webpage. This can be through a purchase or shop for certain things in the webpage.

Similarly, is the other model 2QCV3QV Meta Model focuses on the evaluation of the website performance but through different aspects to the first model. This model includes aspects such as:

- Identity – The webpage should be trusted and create a safe feeling for customers.
- Content – of the webpage should be clear, and its purpose should consist of information to customers towards a certain issue.
- Service – relates to the criteria of service that is provided to customers.
- Location – relates to the location of a certain destination and is more visible as the destination becomes more accessible.
- Management – of a website should be accurate, and this is demonstrated by information that is provided and how often this information is updated.
- Use – is related to the way the webpage is used, its costs and how the information is treated.

These issues have been researched by Noti (2014) and its results are that tourist organisations that have had a better webpage performance result in attracting more international tourists compared to those with a lower performance.

2.4.1.5 Online booking systems

With advances of technology and the application of several apps and software in the tourism sector, it has partly changed the ways and processes of how individuals or customers reserve their holidays and vacations. According to Hasan and Jaboid (2014) there have been increased numbers of internet users. Usually, the use of online booking systems are applied to airlines and hotels and through this system customers can make their choices, in terms of the type of ticket or room or service, product they would prefer to reserve and whatever else they would like. This system is closely related and is part of the computer systems of reservation which records and keeps all the customers data safe and confident. By considering the above and what online marketing brings to its customers, it is important to mention and analyse benefits that online booking systems have already brought to customers worldwide and why this system is playing an important role in the tourism and hospitality industry.

- a) Satisfaction of modern customers or tourists becomes an important part for the benefits that online booking system brings. In this stage customers are more familiar and have gained knowledge by using the internet and this allows them to create more experience in reserving and booking by themselves because from the process they can check and find even more tourist destinations that they might find interesting.
- b) By reaching more customers, businesses can use their online platforms and websites as tools to receive feedback from their existing customers but at the same the time this process allows other customers to check and obtain connections and communicate with each other which is crucial for decision-making processes.
- c) Time and money saving. This stage is important for both businesses and customers. For customers it is more comfortable and safer to do the booking process from home which saves them time and money as they do not need to go to the agencies and check each booking or option. On the other hand, business benefit from the online booking system by saving time so they do not need to deal with each single customer. They save money as the online booking system is open 24/7 rather than employing people to do the same job.

At this stage it is important that customers be insured that while they make transactions the site has to be secure from frauds and thefts and companies should assure customers that their personal information is confidential and is not going to be shared with other individuals or institutions.

2.4.2 Traditional technology

Traditional technology is another side of technology which specifies and is characterised by the main functions of technology without any other intervention or invention. By main functions of technology, it is meant functions like using a computer and its basic functions such as writing/typing or emailing and getting in touch. This is only a part of technology but considering it in certain sectors it is understood or specified differently. In terms of tourism and travel agencies and organizations traditional technology has been specified as a new method to book tickets and holidays, and this new intervention has changed this sector.

In the tourism sector, what is meant by traditional technology is the way that tourism has been promoted. Not many options to get in touch with tourists, nationally or over the world were recognized apart from the host country. Promotion through books, magazines and newspapers are nowadays accompanied by many other methods, techniques, and options for a larger market in different countries.

Furthermore, traditional technology has been given this name due to services and options that have limited previous use in the tourism industry. This includes services such as difficulty in travelling and transportation which means that sometimes there have not been access to many destinations or difficulty in accessing them where there has been information about the existence of destinations.

However, it is important to mention that technology has been in advance by producing and inventing supplies, machines options and more opportunities for mankind. This change and advancement of technology has been in progress by becoming more advanced every year.

2.4.3 Innovative technology

Ficarelli *et al* (2013) support the idea that tourism and travel is continuously changing due to information technology and its new applications, software, and development has been considered as innovative technology. This leads to understanding that innovative technology is related and focused with new inventions that take place in technology and can be related and mixed with other sectors as well.

Innovative technology conveys meaning to new applications, new designs, new ideas, new projects, and techniques and is closely related to these inventions which brings positive

results and benefits to its customers. Nowadays, most people use technology for different reasons such as getting information, buying and so on. As the reasons to use technology are different, people's aim in doing so are different which means that their expectations are different even if the same information is searched. As a sector technology itself is characterised by inventions and it is continuously working towards inventions that facilitate everyday life.

This is the main purpose of technology and continuously looking for new inventions due to people and benefits it provides to the environment makes humans be more comfortable with inventions. Considering the nature of this world where we live and the steps that world and life is progressing there is the need for inventions that make world, people and businesses to look forward. It is important that an invention is useful, welcomed and accepted by people and businesses worldwide. In contrast to traditional technology, innovative technology always requires and urges brighter ideas and projects to develop and attract attention.

In terms of the tourism industry, innovative technology is crucial, and it plays an important role in development and as a tool to achieve competitive advantage. For the sector, innovative technology is understood as the inventions of applications and designs, to create a nicer, and more productive environment for customers. According to Joseph (2017) innovative technology is being used often for businesses so it is important to be updated with changes to maintain loyal clients and members to be updated. He also states that considering the variety and the nature of the innovative technology and characterises it is important that tour agencies and organisations consider benefit and at the same time to avoid negative sides that this invention might bring. This type of technology introduces to businesses different ways, but the benefits of adapting it are relatively similar for most businesses. Advantages consist in different points such as:

- Expansion of the market. Adaptation of the new advances in the technology field is more compatible in helping tourist agencies and organisations, such as booking agencies, hotels, renting car organisations, flight companies, bars, and restaurants, to expand the market where this business operates.

As the main component of information technology is internet or online services, innovative technology gives businesses the opportunity and possibility of products and services through online websites. Sites that are more common on targeting more customers and reaching them from wherever they are. Internet and social median can play the role of the shop but through online means and plays the mediator role which allows customers and suppliers another way of collaboration and communications.

- Reducing costs is another benefit while adapting technology and specially adapting the latest inventions and projects. Several business and companies require the help of humans in order to maintain the business. With the help of innovative technology, by substituting human help with machines or software, reduces costs and increases savings for the businesses.

However, this stage is considered as a negative aspect regarding innovative technology because due to the replacement of human work with machines or computers there is loss of work. Another negative side of innovative technology is upfront expenses. In the tourism sector, most organisations are small businesses and expenses most of time are not coverable but because of the competitive market this business they are willing to pay for new inventions. If businesses adapt to new applications or software or machines there is also the need for training which can increase clientele by increasing performance and services that are provided. These upfront expenses need to be carefully studied and used effectively to reach the goals.

2.5 Use of ICT as a Strategic Tool

2.5.1 E-Commerce and its impact on tourism industry

Web penetration is becoming a crucial factor to the success of travel, tourism and retail businesses and as well has revolutionised the way how products and services are bought or sold on the internet, and this has surpassed in some ways computer or laptops. E-commerce is defined as ‘sales activity takes place through electronic distribution channel’ (WTO,2001)E- commerce has become a way of exchanging information between business, keeping and creating business relationships as well as conducting business transaction through networks. Noti, (2016) stated that key elements of e-commerce are strongly related with the increase of tourism services through the use of mobiles which means that there is a need for adopting technological applications to remain competitive.

Electronic commerce creates facilities for customers and organisations to promote, sell and buy products or services well as target new groups of potential customers through online networks. According to Turban *et al*,(2001), Turban *et al* (2008), and Buhalis *et al*,(2003)it is stated that E-commerce and E-tourism basically represent the same issues except the fact that terminology is different when it is used on other sectors and industries. E-commerce is considered as the process from where individuals and organisations promote,

sell, and buy goods in general whereas the E-tourism consists of the process of promoting, selling, and buying tourism products and services. However, both terms consist of the same objective. The aim of E-commerce and E-tourism consists of processes to exchange information and data through computer networks. According to Buhalis, (2003) E-Tourism is considered as the digitalisation of all the processes in the tourism sector and consists of two different aspects that influence this sector, tactical and strategic aspect. In tactical aspects there is an interaction of E-commerce and the use of ICT to increase the effectiveness and efficiency of organisations in the tourism sector. This can be effective not only for organisations but destinations as well. On the other side is the strategic aspect tourism that includes the revolution and improvements of organisational processes and strategies that determine competitiveness of the organisation.

According to Sabio (2014) E-commerce is considered as an important tool for promotional activity and improves sales in the tourism sector. Moreover, E-commerce and online promotion, targeting and sales has increased the need in tourism industry for more accurate and effective online presence from destinations and organisations that provide tourist products/services. Considered as a framework for further developments, the interaction between e-commerce and internet creates several benefits for users who are likely to adapt such tools. According to Kim(2004) who states that after taking into consideration various studies on the e-commerce area, adaptation brings organisations benefits and advantage in the market. Such benefits consist of easy access of the information regarding products or services and tourist destinations, better and convenient information about tourism services. The adaptation of e-commerce also creates new markets and new interactions with potential customers, improves the service provided to customers as well as increasing business interaction with potential partners or branches. On the other hand, Buhalis, (2003) argues that e-commerce sometimes might be challenging and costly for several organisations and destinations as it requires network costs and expenses, changes of ICT and other innovations, Staff training and development of skills can make organisations face difficulties. However, considering the benefits and the importance of adopting it, most organisations and destinations invest in such frameworks for further development. This strong influence of E-commerce is also supported by Danmar, (2014) who states that there are three major reasons why e-commerce is important in tourism and travel: the internet has the lowest cost to be used for online bookings and reservation, most of tourism search about tourist destinations and products is online on the internet and lastly, use of social media combined with the travel reviews impacts on decision-making process.

E-commerce is considered as a distribution channels for hotels, tour operators and travel agents. An example is the hotel industry which applies a full process starting from promotion of their products, reservations of services and a most important financial transaction online.

2.5.2 Impact of online promotion in the tourism sector

The digitalisation of word and advances of technology have made possible that everything can be bought online because it can be promoted online. According to Linton (2017), it is suggested that almost every business operating either in tourism industry or elsewhere has website where they promote their name, create a brand that can be recognised and of course some site where they can promote and sell their products and services.

Moreover, the rate of promoting products and services through the internet is to help potential customers to make their decisions towards the products and purchases. Furthermore, this technique/method of promoting goods, is characterised by communication channels and the relation between the organisation and the customer has become personal, which means that sometimes organisations have special offers for their members and regular customers. According to Stipic (2014), most people have changed their way of buying. Considering that most of them suffer from the lack of time, online promotion is becoming one of the easiest ways to save time shopping. Continuous internet promotion creates more opportunities for companies, organisations to create and improve their products and services of distributing and marketing products and creating their name and brand. Nowadays organisations and business consider promotion and communication to be important process from pre-selling, selling, consuming and post consuming stages. What is mostly important is that is that customers are most important in the process and their convenience and loyalty is crucial to improve and benefit the business. Since numbers of internet users have increased, organisations gain profits and advantages from this rather than losing business and avoiding negative aspects through gaining customer satisfaction and loyalty. According to Andrew (2010), promotion through internet and online sites have several benefits such as: it being a cost-effective means by which an organisation can avoid paying high bills for traditional marketing campaigns and storage costs. This is important because costs are avoided,

companies give more attention to creating nicer portals where potential customers feel more comfortable, and people love to use it. Another advantage is exploration of the market. Organisations that promote through the internet can explore and expand their market, because customers can be targeted all at the same time from every part of the world and products can be sold in the same way. Continuous communication and lower costs create profits and benefits for organisations to communicate explain and recommend to customers. Through email, social media and so on it is easier and cheaper to keep customers updated and with whatever is needed even though they are close or worldwide.

Another advantage of promoting online is that organisations/tour agencies can have a clearer idea for their sites and customers which makes them understand how good they are performing and what do they need.

Aspects like convenience where organisations using online marketing and promotion are able not to worry about time limitations, in terms of opening and closing shops and storage by allowing the process to be 24/7 without concern about the customer location. Personalisation or creating more opportunities about members or loyal customer by bringing special offers and clearance makes online promotion benefit with more attention from worldwide customers. Whilst benefiting from this positive aspect of internet/online promotion it is important for business and customers to consider potential negative aspects which might be due to neglecting third parties that can affect customers and companies. Such negative aspects are characterised by:

- a) Attraction of customers is a process which is as easy and difficult at the same time. Reaching the market is a different issue, in terms that as an application or website you can reach many individual and customers, but to make these customers check your website and buy from it is a difficult one because competitive websites that might sell similar products and services.
- b) Difficulty of transactions is mentioned as the online world is endless and when purchasing, sometimes customers are not fully aware and there is no face-to-face communication, which in more cases creates a loss to a business.
- c) Another issue that is seen as a disadvantage of promoting through the online sources and internet is time and effort that comes because of the need to keep the website continuously updated. There needs to be knowledge about technology, techniques and methods of online marketing and promotion to create an effective website.

Considering both positive and negative aspects of online/internet marketing/promotion it is important to mention that business need to analyse steps and benefits by decreasing and

avoiding disadvantages and improve their profits by targeting and making new customers while keeping their loyal ones.

2.5.2.1 Market targeting and marketing information systems

In large businesses, which offer tourist services, the development of databases has brought great improvements in the quality of information made available to marketing managers. Also known by the term ‘data mining’, different research can provide detailed information about customer profiles and behaviours, as well as more accurate information about the different ways how consumers react to different forms of promotion and distribution. If enough information is gathered about levels of consumer satisfaction, then databases can provide a perfect tool for travel and tourism marketing managers to make the most attractive combinations of tourist products, prices, and innovations in communication, as well as evaluating at the same time relevant results. Electronic marketing strategies have become usable and the pressure on different businesses to invest in the production of applications in tourism service has increased. This trend is followed by numbers of mobile users who have increased, so the interest in mobile technology is growing.

2.5.2.2 Distribution and promotion

Considering the nature of tourism industry, it is important for destinations or organizations to have a competitive advantage in the market as well as maintaining a good connotation for their name. To have a better understanding of promotion and its role, it is important to evaluate the marketing mix which is widely studied and researched due to its impact and influence that it has upon tourist destinations and organizations. Marketing on its own is considered so the process of activities from where destinations and organizations produce their offers and best products for attracting tourists, according to the American Marketing Association 2013. The marketing mix, on the other hand, is a composition on four major components that contribute towards competitive advantages as well as successful development of destinations. According to Crotts *et al* (2009) the marketing mix is an important approach in the tourism industry. The marketing mix includes components like price, product, distribution and promotion which contribute towards the same objective of increasing development and success.

Figure 2.5 Marketing Mix Source: Singh(2012) Hasan and Islam (2020).

McCarthy (2005) assumes that the success is granted only when all components are active and are chosen in a fair way. This assumes the main role of marketing mix which is to increase the number of tourists towards a destination activity or organization to provide development.

Originally, the marketing mix was used in the tourism industry, but it was found that four components were not defining properly intangible products/services(Lamb *et al.* 2011). Hence, Philip Kotler introduced three more components to deal with the intangible services.

a. Product/services according to Sigh (2012) is considered as goods or services that are introduced to customers to sell and benefit from it. In the tourism industry product/services are considered as products or services that are related to travelling, accommodation, flying, activities, or services which most of the time are based on different issues. By considering the influences on tourism sector such as seasonality, weather, demands make this sector difficult. Destinations or organizations use this product or service to attract tourists, target new markets as well as introducing potential customers to what it is offered and promoted to them to attract their attention. Considering the nature of tourism sectors, most consider and buy products or services only by considering the image that is promoted to them.

b. Price is considered as an important indication in tourism which is closely related with tourist customers and destinations or organizations. Price is considered as the amount of

money tourists consider paying regarding products or tourist services. Price influences on tourists and destinations must consider it to be very precise when appointing the value of a product or service due in a competitive market. On the other hand, price as indication of value and services provided from organizations or destinations is important.

c. Distribution or place is a component of marketing mix and influences the whole industry. In our everyday life, buying normal products and services from shops and places makes the choice easier. In the case of tourism, the contrary products and services are not able to be touched or selected in shops. Everything is chosen, selected, and bought, based on the perceptions and feedback that comes from tourists themselves or tourist organizations.

d. According to Mulec (2015), promotion is important and powerful for tourist destinations to promote their attractiveness, sites, historical and cultural buildings and other products and tourist services. It is powerful due to the reality that is direct to potential customers to communicate offers, products, and services with the main goal to attract tourists to destinations. The increase of tourist destinations and competitive markets it is important for organizations to choose the right promotional activities and tools that contribute to development of the sector. Furthermore, one of the main characteristics of promotion is that by choosing strategies and tools for promoting tourism products and destinations may lead to an increase of sustainability in this sector. This is considered as a main indicator on tourist perceptions and beliefs that sustainable tourist destinations give the idea of a safe and secure travel and holidays.

e. Process, is one of the components that defines the variety of procedures and activities in the tourism industry. Kannan and Srinivasan (2009) and Kadhim *et al.* (2016), elaborate the processes that are included when tourism marketing applies and planning where and how to travel, destination, attractions, services, products and so on.

f. Physical evidence is the element which involves sellers and customers coming to the destination. This component of the marketing mix is related to the experiences of customers after the process of visiting/buying has taken place. Kadhim *et al.*(2016) explain that even though customers have a positive experience from a certain destination, it does not mean that their memories do not include any unpleasant experiences that might be related to infrastructure, transportation, or hosting people.

g. Customer satisfaction is another component that introduces deals with online services. It is the key for maintaining loyal customers. Sarker *et al.* (2009) suggest that marketing is considered as the process which includes the process of exchanging valuable information and products. By taking into consideration the nature of the tourism industry, it is

important to highlight the advantage that is achieved from the businesses when customer satisfaction levels are high. Hence, customer satisfaction is considered one of the key factors to achieving competitive advantage in the market.

2.5.2.3 Online Marketing and promotion

Considering modern day changes, innovations, and technological advancement there is continuous improvement in different industries and sectors. The tourism sector is one of the sectors that has been adopting and using technology advancements and innovations for further development and advancement. Marketing is influenced by these technological innovations. Most destinations nowadays have been finding it easier to use promotion through online means which provides a most accurate and quicker service to reach customers or tourists. Online marketing has gone through several steps by the time it came to be introduced in a structured form. The rapid growth and increase of internet accompanied by relevant technology and information has influenced every aspect of economic and social life.

Nowadays most businesses that operate in tourism have identified and understood the crucial importance of the internet on marketing and promotional campaigns. First, the internet is important for marketing. Secondly, successful marketing should be based on how it should combine traditional and new business principles into a coherent and appropriate online strategy. Thirdly, the presence of the internet in marketing and promotional activity is an improvement, compared to traditional ways of promoting; it comes as a new way to interact, communicate, and create relations with consumers and tourists. It is time that tourist destinations as well as other businesses understand the way how online promotion works, its potential and benefits that it can bring to be considered as a necessary approach to create competitive advantage and be competitive in the market.

Marketing, based on the traditional function operates at an organisational level by creating, communicating, and promoting valuable information for customers and managing the relation between the two based on the benefits for both sides. According to Mohammed *et al*(2009)online marketing and promotion is the product that comes from the combination modern of communication technology and the old marketing principles that tourist organizations have used. This definition emphasizes all activities through the worldwide web, which consist of issues such as:

- a. Build communities that have or share common values,
- b. Ensure strong ties with current and potential customers,

- c. Attract new businesses,
- d. Maintaining current business,
- e. Building brand identity,
- f. Ensure cooperation between organizations and their partners.

Online Marketing is the process that creates and maintains relationships with customers and tourist through on-line activities, to make it easier the exchange of ideas, products, services that satisfy the goals of both parties by increasing productivity and service provided to customers. Moreover, online marketing consists of the use of the web as well as traditional channels and can help to build a long-term positive relationship with customers, to create competitive advantage in the market.

On top of every process and activity is the customer who should keep close and in continuous communication from where organisations and destinations identify levels of customer satisfactions. Therefore, online marketing is intended to provide value to customers information and communications technologies. It provides additional tools for traditional marketing. Constant changes in the internet market have a direct impact not only on the instruments, but also on the objectives and goals that continuously require new applications and the use of new strategies. These factors (tools, goals, applications, strategies, and other similar instruments) can be used to distinguish the marketing tools through online means from traditional marketing tools. Not all traditional marketing tools can be considered as internet marketing tools, but most of them can be used.

In general, the main objective of marketing is to attract and retain consumers. For tourist destinations and organisations, it is important to reach this objective and that is why traditional marketers use different instruments of marketing such as price, advertising, distribution, and product to satisfy current and potential customers to create competitiveness among the market.

Marketing methods have changed and improved continuously, while organizations have become more efficient in delivering messages, information, and products. More recently, many organizations pay more attention and spend more time investing in the creation of web pages and become aware of the importance of transmitting an active online presence. Nowadays, applying marketing and promotion through the internet is considered as an interaction system that measures activities that are directed to customers and tourists.

Moreover, the customer can choose the time and place in which they want to interact with the online systems in researching destinations and touristic products. Online marketing or online promotion is closely related with the adoption of IT/ICT in the tourism sector.

According to Stitic, (2014) the role of online promotion is like traditional promotional activities such as to create communication channels between destinations or organisers and tourists. Benefits of using technology its tools such as the internet and ICT are:

- a. Quicker market targeting which allows tourist destinations and organisations to have easier access towards customers and due to the big number of internet users the impact of promoting online is higher than it was traditionally.
- b. Promoting tourism destinations, products, and services through online is considered as a procedure which takes less time to distribute and share the information regarding different products and services comparing to traditional ways of promotion.
- c. Online promotion gives the opportunity for tourist destinations and organisation to decrease their costs on promotion activities and campaigns as the publication and promotion of a certain destination or product can be reached on the same online page by lots of tourists and customers.
- d. Instant communication is available when destinations promote through the internet. Instant communication is understood to be when destinations and organisations that operate in the tourism industry can exchange deeper information about what is promoted, clarify any concerns, and identify demands from customers to improve where the destination stands and what is needed.
- e. Another benefit is that it can identify and measure improvements and success during the promotional campaign by keeping statistics of participants that interact regarding the nature of promotional activity.

However, promotion through the online means and tools is closely related to both private and state organisations which apply online promotion to increase productivity and success. There are different components that all contribute to promotional activity the reach the goal of attracting tourists, widening market targeting and achieving competitive advantage such as advertising, slogans and logos, guidebooks, brochures, and the printed press.

2.5.2.4 Advertisements and Public/Customer Relations

For many years advertising has been and still is one of the most common forms and techniques used to promote tourist destinations and products. Moradkhan, (2014), asserts that advertising consists of several aspects of promotion that impacts on destinations. First, it is important to define what advertising is. Advertising is considered as the sum of activities and events that introduce and present goods, names of companies, tourism destinations and

products or services. Secondly, advertising consists of competitive advantage and successful development of a destination only in cases when it is strategically combined with the needs of destination and demands of tourists. Furthermore, advertising is considered as an important indicator for developments in terms of the economy, social and cultural improvements.

This comes because of successful strategies that are combined in the advertisement activity. Salehi and Farohbakhsh (2014) suggests that the main role of advertising is to take advantage from media, send messages to tourists by aiming to obtain a fast response from the tourist market. According to Amarasinghe, (2017) advertising recognises different purposes depending on the nature of the organisation where it is taking place. In terms of the tourism industry, advertising recognises different purposes. It plays the role of a convincing framework or tool that attempts to attract the attention of potential customers and tourists. Advertising activities aim to improve and enhance the image of a destination or organisation, introduce new offers, new facilities, and innovations, introduce new products or new activities and so on. The purpose of advertising is always subject of change depending on the subject and research area.

Creativity of corporate websites and creation of links to search engines and other suitable sites are considered as an important part of achieving consumer awareness and motivation. The impact of advertisements reaches out to customers who are looking for the service/product being advertised, to match their requirements with an appropriate provider.

Considering that the focus of advertising in the tourism industry is to attract potential tourists and to increase the number of tourists visiting the destination, during the past few years the sector has created new ways that support the process of advertising and promotion. New techniques both slogans and logos are created to support the advertising activity of certain destinations and tourist organisations. Both techniques are based and depend on the visual effects and perceptions that is created from advertising. Slogans on one side are focused on the process of attracting the attention potential tourists and customers by using a few words or expressions that can affect tourist behaviour and of course it conveys a meaning about the destination or organisation so tourists can remember and create perceptions. On the other hand, it stands for destination logos that are considered as pictures, figures or images that contain destinations names, slogans and logos that are created to convey meanings and shape tourist perceptions towards a destination. The main objective of logos is to introduce the name of a destination to potential tourists and widen the market target from a global point of view. What is important about slogans and logos is that both techniques are easily adapted with new innovations in technology which is an advantage in creating proper logos and

slogans in tourism. The advances of technology and digitalisation has made it possible that both techniques are introduced to tourists and customers on different ways, shapes, colours and most importantly they convey interest and attract the attention of tourists to destination. The following different slogans and logos that are used in tourism industry:

Figure 2.5 Albania tourism logo Source: Google

Figure 2.6 International Tourism logos Source: Hardy, (2009)

2.5.2.5 Print media

Internet commerce developments in recent years has made the network a great instrument with relatively low costs for creating consumer awareness, using multimedia methods that can be supported through the provision of printed information to potential buyers who have shown interest in advance. At the same time, they may at least partially replace expensive brochures, providing the same information or another richer online with the download option.

Another important way of promotion is through guide books and brochures. Even though it feels like an old tradition of promotion, due to innovations in the tourism industry, guidebooks and brochures are still present in the tourism market as not every organisation is well adapted to rapid changes of technology.

Most of the time brochures have the same goal and role the in tourism industry which consists of informing the tourist about different landscapes, historical and cultural sites and buildings, activities, events, and so on. According to Zilinger, (2004) guidebooks may be found in different contexts, some of them have general information and others are more specific ones. Supported by Alipour *et al*, (2012) brochures on the other hand include less guidebooks about different and specific events and activities which include facilities to become better informed in the way, how, and when these events/activities can be reached and their costs. What is important to mention is that both techniques find wide usage and can have a direct influence on people who travel to communicate accurate information and of course creating interest towards what is advertised and promoted.

However, there are other ways than the traditional promotional activity which is still active, such as the printed promotion which refers to the promotion in magazines, newspapers, and similar media. This technique is like brochures is focused on communications and information regarding different activities, events and especially tourist offers which exist for a short period of time. This technique does not have a certain target of the market as it only aims to inform the customers about offers and potentials a destination possesses which might be interest certain individuals. The purpose is to attract tourists and customers towards the destination and what it offers not only when its advertised, but by creating security and a positive perception of the destination. Example of Travel Guidebooks and brochures are:

Source: Google.

Figure 2.7 Example of promotion on printed press

2.6 Literature Gap Identification

Most studies are focused on the impact of technology in the tourism industry in general terms by considering advantages or disadvantages. Regarding data collection, most of studies that the researcher came across have been used qualitative or quantitative analysis in their studies. There is less evidence of research conducted by using mixed method of data analysis in relation to the use of technology and its impact in promotion in the Albanian tourism industry.

To deal with the literature gap, the researcher has applied a mixed method to evaluate the relation between technology and the tourism industry and identified the effective usage of technology for successful promotional strategies. The researcher now introduces a research conceptual framework and strategies are suggested.

2.7 Development of the Conceptual Framework.

The conceptual framework is an important stage of the conducting research. According to different authors, the conceptual framework is considered as the path of conducting research based on an existing theory or model(Grant and Osanloo,2014; Adom,*et al.* 2018). The main objective in developing the framework while conducting research is to accept and give meaning to research findings.

The components, ‘perceived usefulness’ and ‘perceived ease of use’ found on the Technology Acceptance Model (Davis *et al.* 1989) and the WEBQUAL Model (Loiacono*et al.* 2002), have been used in the Tourism Industry to analyse the quality of services and

websites as well as to understand the behaviour of customers towards the acceptance of technology. Several studies have concluded that Perceived Usefulness and Ease of Use have a strong impact upon the performance of certain organisations in the tourism industry (Wu *et al.* 2011; El-Gohary,2012; Matikity*et al.* 2018). For Usefulness and Ease of use, WEBQUAL is characterised by three more components: Response time, trust, and entertainment. Through these components are measured the service quality of the website in the tourism industry.

Servqual is used to understand the quality of the services provided in the tourism industry, whether this be online or not. According to Parasuraman, *et al.*, 1988, there are five dimensions from the SERVQUAL model: Tangibles, Reliability, Responsiveness, Assurance and Empathy. However, various studies have found out that not all components of the SERVQUAL can be used to measure the quality of online service. Hence only three of the components, Reliability, Responsiveness and Assurance have been found to be more appropriate to analyse service quality and customers satisfaction in the tourism industry(Toor *et al.* 2016).

Furthermore, the researcher has found out that it is important to measure the performance of the online website in the tourism industry. Hence, two models have been considered in the research. Aida Model(Meera *at al.* 2019) and 2QCV3QV META Model (Noti,2014) has great importance in analysing and evaluating website performance in the Tourism Industry. The AIDA model consists in four components: Attention, Interest, Desire, Action, whereas the 2QCV3QV META model takes into consideration a wider range of components such as Identity, Content, Service, Location, Management and Use.

Based on the evaluation of both models, AIDA and 2QCV3Meta model, the researcher found that the components from both models are similar and aim to achieve the same objectives such as to measure web performance in the Tourism Industry. It is important to mention that both models have been used even in traditional promotion techniques, but the reaction is slower than the online website.

Considering the similarity in components from both models, the researcher is proposing a combination of both modes into one, ACIAS which stands for:

A-Awareness/Attention

C-Content

I-Identity

A-Action

S-Satisfaction/Feedback

Figure 2.8 Combined model of webpage performance.

Source: (The Author)

The combination of both models into one brings a facility for destinations/businesses to focus on only one model and covers the most important aspects from the two models. Furthermore, AIDA model and 2QCV3Meta model did not take into consideration the Satisfaction/Feedback component which is one the most important indicators of loyal customers and starting point for further developments of a business.

By taking into consideration the above proposal, the new model ACIAS will be combined with other technological models such as TAM, Webqual and Servqual to come up with a strategy to enhance development of the Albanian Tourism Industry.

Dimensions	The model	Reference
Usefulness	TAM WEBQUAL	Davies, et al., 1989 Loiacono, et al., 2002
Ease of use	TAM WEBQUAL	Davies, et al., 1989 Loiacono, et al., 2002
Reliability	SERVQUAL	Parasuraman, et al., 1988
Responsiveness	SERVQUAL	Parasuraman, et al., 1988
Assurance	SERVQUAL	Parasuraman, et al., 1988
Trust	WEBQUAL	Loiacono, et al., 2002
Response time	WEBQUAL	Loiacono, et al., 2002
Attention Action	AIDA model	Meera et al.2019
Identity Content	2QCV3QV META Model	Noti,2014
Satisfaction/ Feedback		

Table 2.1- Models considered for the conceptual framework.

Proposed conceptual framework for research

(Source: The Author)

Figure 2.9 Proposed conceptual framework.

The above dimensions and components have been used to understand the impact that Technology has upon the tourism industry and specifically the impact on electronic promotion. Based on the research findings, a strategy is then suggested to enhance overall development of the Albanian Tourism Industry.

2.8 Chapter Summary

In conclusion of the second chapter, literature review, it is important to mention that the adaptation and application of technology and information and communication technology in the tourism sector is crucial and key for the progress of this sector. By considering all information from studies and research that were necessary it was concluded that technology has made the tourism sector improve and increase overall performance of the sector, including service provided and products that are offered. By bringing the tourism and travel industry to another stage, technology plays the role of the determinant key in GDP growth, employment, education, and transportation. Models of technology acceptance such as TAM, UTAUT, Web Based have been evaluated and discussed.

Several technological theories and models have created strong connections for the tourism industry. The development of the e-commerce, development of websites and extensive use of the internet has facilitated overall productivity of the travel and service sector. Several models such as Aida Model and 2QCV3Meta model have been discussed and compared related to web performance., Moreover, various models that measure the service quality through online websites have been discussed and evaluated.

The use of social media and latest innovations in mobile technology have shaped the traditional way of tourism marketing and promotion. The opportunity to reach a wider market at the same time has given businesses the opportunity to be competitive in the global market. Businesses have an opportunity to be productive with lower costs and saving time. To benefit from such innovations, businesses need to understand how to maximise the benefits of using such technology. In the case of the tourism industry, it is important to note that successful businesses who adopt the latest technologies and operate in the online market, have created appropriate websites, with clear content and images. Due to intense competition, having a well-designed website means the first contact with any potential customers.

The final part of this chapter focused on introducing a conceptual framework for the research, and by considering and discussing appropriate literature and studies, the conceptual framework for the research has been proposed.

CHAPTER 3- RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Introduction

This chapter elaborates the methodology of the research that was applied during the research process. It includes the analysis of concept and techniques used in completion of the research. The covers different aspects of methodology including research philosophy, approach, design, data collection methods, sampling techniques, reliability and validity, ethics, and limitations of the research.

3.2 Research Paradigm and Philosophy

Research paradigm and philosophy are closely related and interact as one when conducting research. Many authors have researched on the bases of philosophy and paradigm which leads to different definitions of philosophy regarding the area and the nature of the study. According to Saunders and Thornhill, (2007) Research philosophy is considered as the evaluation of knowledge, background, and nature of knowledge from the research regarding certain topics. They go on to state that research philosophy refers to the way that information is planned, collected, selected, and used in relation to the research with the main purpose of developing the nature of the knowledge that is planned to be accomplished by conducting the research.

Cohen *et al.* (2000) pay attention on the relation between the paradigm and philosophy and in most of the cases the definition of philosophy comes from the interaction and embracement of the research paradigm which is considered as a wider system that involves various beliefs, recognitions and understanding of various theories regarding conduct of the research. Not only a system of conducting research, but a paradigm is also considered as a procedure that us used by the researcher in following several stages in order to find if there is a direct correlation between the research topic with the research aims and objectives to justify the research purpose.

Gliner and Morgan,(2000) consider the research paradigm as an important framework that helps the researcher organise the work and plan how to conduct relevant research by fulfilling the objectives of the research. According to Johnson and Christensen, (2005) one of the most important points is similarity of objective that both the paradigm and the philosophy in research is that both frameworks help the researcher to create valuable information and knowledge to control beliefs and perceptions as well as elucidating arguments regarding certain issues and results.

However, to understand research philosophy, it is important to mention research paradigm components through where the philosophical components take place and contribute to other methods of conducting research. Based on research conducted by Easterby-Smith *et al.* (2006) these are considered to be behavioural components of paradigms such as:

- a) Epistemology is the first component of the research paradigm and it is considered as the involvement of several perceptions and frameworks that are closely related and embrace to explore the nature of the real world or real situation.
- b) Ontology is the second component of the research paradigm. Ontology is considered as the perceptions and assumptions that are created and used to enhance knowledge and have a better understanding.
- c) Axiology has to do with the value's notion, and it is related with the opinion of the researcher about adding value in the research.
- d) Methodology is believed to be a research paradigm component due to its wide usage in research analysis. Methodology gives the opportunity to the researcher to combine different methods, approaches, designs, and strategies to critically analyse information collected for the research and fulfil objectives and reach the aim and purpose of the research. This includes the full process of conducting research from the planning of research, structuring it, choosing the topic, and choosing the methods and techniques to conduct the research.

The researcher needs to understand the importance of combining different techniques and methods in certain issues to better analyse and represent an issue. However, this combination of techniques and methods need to be in association with each other and represent the same type of research.

In terms of research philosophy according to McNabb, (2008) it is important to mention that as a sector it is a combination of four different components: positivism, interpretivism, realism and pragmatism philosophy which contribute to the research through the way that the researcher understands the nature of research and where it is based.

3.2.1 Positivism

Positivism is the first component of research philosophy. This philosophy is based on information that is supported by facts and it is collected through various observations and surveys. According to Davies and Davies (2007) and Easter by-Smith *et al.*(2006) positivism is related to knowledge that is a fact and is based on information, most of the time positive

impact, which is collected by the experience and it is conducted by observations and experiments that have a focus of gathering numeric information. In most cases positivism is considered as a philosophy which has to do with the theories that can be logically verified and proven.

According to Collins, (2010) positivism relies on observations which helps in analysing numerical data statistically. It is important to mention this part of research philosophy in the role of the researcher which according to Saunders, (2003) is explained as a role of the analyst who collects data and uses the results based on the topic with a positive perspective on the topic to reach positive goals and objectives. Furthermore, Crowther and Lancaster, (2008) state that in most cases positivism research philosophy adopts a deductive approach, and it adopts a descriptive strategy while conducting research.

3.2.2 Interpretivism

The second research philosophy the researcher considered is Interpretivism which is a philosophy that concentrates on personal experience and small sampling from where ideas or opinions are understood for a bigger community or group. Interpretivism is one of the philosophies that is related with the use of small sampling to understand the ideas of a bigger sized group from that of sampling(Kasi 2009). Individual perception of samples that are used in order to use that perception not as an individual, but as groups or community perceptions or a wider group. According to Johnson and Christensen,(2010) interpretivism philosophy is based on information regarding a certain fact that can be appropriate to be used in different situations.

Furthermore, interpretivism philosophy is mostly considered important for data collection methods such as interviews and observation as well as being supported by a variety of the secondary data. Considering several studies, interpretivism philosophy has been through positive and negative aspects of using whilst conducting this research. Positive aspects of interpretivism philosophy are related to the level of studying and collecting information. This can impact qualitative divisions of the research such as ethical considerations, and related issues. On the other hand, the disadvantage of using interpretivism philosophy is related with the bias regarding the research and this leads to a lack of generalising information as it is mostly based on personal perception and values.

3.2.3 Realism

Realism is another component of research philosophy which is widely used while conducting research. According to Hewitt *et al.*(2012) ‘The realist approach is a form of theory-driven evaluation developed to strengthen the explanatory power of evaluation studies and contribute to evidence-based policy and practice’.

Furthermore, realism philosophy is believed to be a powerful philosophy which is based on the freedom and independence of the reality and from the individual mind. Johnson and Christensen,(2010) consider realism philosophy as the way that behaviour of individuals is influenced and shaped and often changed towards a certain situation of the reality. This philosophy gets roots from the hypothesis of a theory based on science and ends up with the development and enhancement of knowledge and information. It is a generic approach that can be applied to many fields of research, including health, culture, educational, economic, travel and social care sectors.

According to different studies, realism philosophy is a combination of its own components which in most cases are known as direct realism which is considered as a direct connection with the real event, situation, and reality and what you see directly affects what you understand. According to Saunders (2012) and Novikov *et al.* (2013) the other component of realism is critical realism which is related to the experience of individuals (in this case tourists) from the reality which might be modified and changed by critics or demonstrate how it can be improved. In most cases this component analyses what is real and not all the time it is good and there might be areas for improvement.

3.2.4 Pragmatism

The final component of the research philosophy is pragmatism philosophy. According to Morgan (2007) pragmatics is one of the approaches that gives to the researcher the freedom and possibility to use different techniques and methods to analyse on the basis of qualitative and quantitative research. According to Saunders *et al.*(2012) This is one of those philosophies that take into consideration that there are different techniques and methods which individuals can use to interpret different situations of the real world while conducting research or study.

Pragmatism philosophy supports the idea that in the research field there are different and several angles from where the real world can be seen, understood, experienced, and afterwards interpreted or transmitted to others. However, this variety of points of view make

individuals have a personal understanding and interpretation about the real world. In terms of the tourism sector this philosophy is specified by tourists whose behaviour is sometimes shaped by the others' experience and points of view, but in most cases, tourists decide to consider a destination from a different stance of what is offered and if it is worthy, as well as considering several aspects such as accommodation, transport, and access. This is based on personal requirements and personal understanding of what is seen when the destination is reached.

Considering several studies where pragmatism philosophy is considered, it is stated that differences with other philosophies such as positivism and interpretivism, pragmatism do not operate as a totally different philosophies but as a combination of both positivism and interpretivism, which relies on combining positive aspects of the two such as combination of methods, techniques, strategies, and designs in one philosophy. According to Wilson (2010) there are differences between philosophies in terms of strategies, approaches, and advantages which pragmatic philosophy can make easier by providing the combination of different details and methods.

Philosophy	Approach	Ontology	Axiology	Strategy
Positivism	Deductive	Objective	Value –free	Quantitative
Interpretivism	Inductive	Subjective	Biased	Qualitative
Pragmatism	Deductive/Inductive or both	Objective/Subje ctive or both	Value- free/biased	Quantitative/quali tative or both

Table 3.1 Summary of the research paradigm and philosophy.

What is important to mention is that in pragmatic philosophy is the research question that determines the philosophy due to the combination of different methods and techniques during the research. It is important when choosing pragmatic philosophy, that the research results should always be in alliance with the aims and objectives of the research. This means that it is in the researcher's hands to use every possible tool, method, design, strategy, and technique and that by mixing and combining them together might benefit the researcher in terms of planning, collecting, analysing, and presenting information for the research itself.

3.3 Research Approach

In this section, the researcher faced two types of research approach that are widely used in this field: inductive and deductive. According to Wilson and Richard (2004) deductive is that type of approach that is based upon different hypothesis and previous theories. This is one of the theories that is called a 'top-down' approach as it goes from a most general hypothesis up to specific ones where the researcher confirms or rejects.

Wilson,(2010) suggests that a deductive approach is one of the approaches that is based and more concerned about the way of presenting the findings or conclusions that derive from different propositions. Furthermore, according to Snieder and Learner,(2009) the deductive approach is based on observations and the way that research takes place is from the hypothesis that the researcher takes into consideration, and from this process is where the results highlighted by the hypothesis can be accepted and become a particular issue or it can even be rejected. This leads to the information that a deductive approach derives from the most general information into a particular issue or topic.

However, it is important to take into consideration five steps that are suggested by Robson (2002) which are suggested to researchers to follow in cases when the researcher has decided to adapt a deductive approach during the research. Steps include the process of adapting and applying the deductive approach while researching a certain topic. Steps to follow while adapting deductive approach are:

- a. Develop hypothesis,
- b. Express the hypothesis,
- c. Test the hypothesis,
- d. Examine the results and it allows the researcher to slightly modify the theory depending on the findings.

In the inductive approach, according to Goddard and Melville (2004) it is stated that it is an approach that is the contrary of deductive and it is not based on hypothesis from general information, is based on the development of new theories that have not been researched before.

It is known as a bottom-up approach according to Ledico et al. (2010) as it goes from the most specific observations up to the most general and most of the time it is recognised through the ‘bottom- up’ theory. An inductive approach involves the process that starts from various observation which lead into patterns and after it becomes a theory by considering these first observations. Considering that every issue involves both positive and negative aspects, an inductive approach involves advantages to be adapted while conducting research. Such advantages include:

- Flexibility, which allows the researcher to be flexible and not to follow any information that has been prepared or determined earlier,
- Flexible, in terms of allowing the researcher to identify various theories appropriate for the research,
- It allows the researcher to create a cause-and-effect relationship between an issue or certain topic and the way this issue is interpreted by others,
- It helps the researcher to identify and explain why an event happen.

It is also important that while considering this approach that the researcher should take account of the negative aspects of inductive approach. Gratton and Jones (2009) suggest that the disadvantages of the inductive approach are closely related with the observation process that in case of an incorrect observation, it might lead the researcher to investigate irrelevant information and even come to incorrect conclusions. Other negative aspects are related to sampling size through which the inductive approach is more effective while using a smaller sized sample. It is also considered as a time-consuming approach as it takes longer for ideas to be explained into the data collection process.

Inductive and deductive approaches are closely related with the type of information collected be it qualitative or quantitative data. In terms of qualitative information, the usual the approach it is the deductive approach, and the reasoning is objective. Whereas, in terms of quantitative data collection methods, the most suitable approach is inductive, and the reasoning is mostly subjective, as it conveys meaning. In terms of the type of analyses that go

better with each approach, the deductive approach conveys numerical estimations and statistical inference whereas in terms of the inductive approach, analysis of the information is mostly narrative description and analysis is mostly in a continuous comparison during the research.

Abductive approach and reasoning is the newer definition in the research that is specified as a combination of deductive and inductive approaches with the only difference being that it avoids the weaknesses of other approaches and has brought together strengths and positive aspects into the abductive approach. In most cases this approach is suitable with pragmatic studies and philosophies.

Abductive reasoning processes start from incomplete observations which as a process may lead to true facts or be better articulated into predictions that sometimes realise true predictions. According to Bryman and Bell (2015), the research process starts from incomplete observations that are considered as puzzles or surprises which the researcher considers what to consider as the most appropriate explanation to explain such surprises and puzzles. What is important to mention on this approach is that an abductive approach allows the researcher to combine both numerical and cognitive reasoning at the same time during the research which other approaches does not allow.

In this research the researcher has decided to combine both deductive and inductive research approaches. The abductive approach it is one mentioned and is not a new theory, but it comes in another perspective and dimension of usage of technology and information communication technology to promote the tourism sector in Albania. This approach allows the researcher to analyse from the general theory up to the specific one as in this case is the usage of technology in different aspects in the tourism sector and use it as a tool for further development in the sector.

3.4 Research Design

Research design is another section that is important whilst and after conducting research. According to Bryman and Bell (2015) who have stated that research design is considered as plans or methods that researcher follows while planning the research and while conducting research on a certain topic by analysing how the researcher has planned to fulfil the research. The main focus and purpose of research design is the process of collecting data and the analysis what data is collected in order to direct the research problem and reach the objectives

to be able to make appropriate recommendation to institutions and tourist destination chosen for this research.

Furthermore, in most cases the research design is compared and treated in a similar way with methodology regarding the process of planning and creating a framework of development.

However, there is a difference between the two that research design is more concerned about planning the research whereas methodology shows the researcher how to do it and conduct the research.

Considering the above information about methodology and design and the relation with the researcher it is important for the researcher to follow several steps to choose the right and proper techniques and methods that are in accordance with the research aims and objectives.

Creswell (2005) states that there are several steps that the researcher might need to consider when choosing right and proper methods and designs during the period when planning the research. He says that steps that are needed to be followed are:

- a) It is important that the researcher considers the approaches, methods, techniques, and designs that need to be compatible and match the nature of the research problem, aims and objectives. In the case of a qualitative approach the problems are those that require more explanation whereas in the case of quantitative method used in research consider problems that require more clear knowledge to support certain logical explanations.
- b) The second step includes the choice of approach if it going to be research driven from theory to the main issue or the other way around. Here, it is important to consider who is going to be the audience for the research and there is a need to create a basic connection with what researcher chooses for research either deductive or inductive and what the audience expects to find in the research.
- c) Lastly, it is also important that research approaches should relate to the experience of the researcher. In terms of qualitative research, the researcher at this stage needs continuous training and courses in the related area of study. In quantitative research, the researcher uses personal experience to collect and analyse data.

According to these recommended steps it is important to mention that whatever the approaches, methods, techniques, and strategies that are chosen for the research it always requires hard work, serious attribution, effort, and continuous training in the subject.

3.4.1 Type of Research

Choosing the research type that will need to be adapted in the research is important because it is linked with aims and objectives of the research. Similarly, the research types give an idea of how the researcher answers the research questions. Three main types of research have been identified and each step should adapt one or more research types. The researcher has used both descriptive and explanatory research.

Descriptive research is widely found in tourism studies. Its definition and purpose are to find out and describe various event, objects, subjects and so on. Descriptive research usually describes certain issues and events of a certain situation or topic (Gall, *et al.*; Nassaji, 2015).

Exploratory research is defined and responsible in explaining and justifying events and issues by commenting and explaining the way things are done on a certain event or topic. Exploratory research is mostly used to clarify a certain problem and the researcher might need to review existing information to obtain a clearer understanding of the problem (Mainardes, *et al.*, 2010).

Explanatory research has to do with the development and improvement of various patterns and programs during the research (Rahi, 2017).

The researcher has applied a combination of both descriptive and explanatory research and has a clear understanding of the use of technology and its impact in the Albanian tourism industry. Even though the research covers a full industry it can be classified as a case study as it aims to solve issues related to a particular destination and answer research questions by evaluating both qualitative and quantitative data.

3.4.2 Research Strategy

Research strategy is considered as process on how to collect and analyse data by taking into consideration the research objectives (Rahi, 2017). Similarly, research strategy is perceived as a plan which helps to answer questions that have been set previously (Easterby-Smith, *et al.*, 2012). According to different research that has been conducted in the tourism industry it has been suggested that there are different strategies to undertake research such as a survey, experiment, grounded theory, case study, and so on. Veal (2006) suggests several types of research that are considered as strategies:

- Survey research strategy is managed and information is collected through the survey and ways to conduct the surveys. The main purpose of a survey is to collect data through different means such as phone and email survey, online surveys, paper surveys (Mark, *et al.*, 2009). Wyse, (2012) suggests that benefits of using survey research are closely related to costs through use of online surveys which are less costly than printed surveys. Higher numbers of participants can contribute to the survey. Flexibility is another benefit of using a survey due to varieties and types of surveys. By having various methods such as online, phone, social media, paper, and face to face surveys creates an opportunity to target more participants, and in most cases, gain superior information that is relevant and more reliable. Considering that in most cases surveys do not require any personal information it can be characterised by anonymity, and this allows the participants to be clear and direct and honest when answering survey questions.
- Grounded theory research is a strategy that involves the development of a theory based on the analysis of the data. It is a strategy that is usually used with an inductive approach and focuses on certain issues rather many.
- Ethnography research is a strategic study that in most cases involves humans and culture based on observation of the society, event, and tradition of certain interest or topic.
- Action research strategy is closely related to the action that is taken or planned to be taken individually or in a team to quickly solve a certain problem or topic.
- Case study research refers to the focus towards a certain issue or problem and attempts to solve the problem or research about this certain issue (Rahi, 2017).

In this research, the researcher has applied a case study strategy which evaluates processes, events, and programmes. In this way it justifies the purpose of the research and makes possible the focus of the research. According to Davies (2007) there are several advantages of using case study strategy. It gives you the opportunity of observing a single case and analysing it in different aspects and even there is a possibility to compare and analyse different aspects of observing to make it easier for the researcher to achieve results. In addition, by using this strategy the researcher can identify different effective ways and usages of technology and ICT in order to promote the tourism industry in Albania and how this framework can effectively develop the sector in terms of development as a destination, as well as improvement and development for organisations and agencies operating in the tourism sector.

Furthermore, the researcher has used several frameworks such as descriptive approach followed by critical analysis to analyse and present collected information.

3.4.3 Research Choice

Research choice is understood as methods and techniques that researchers adapt when collecting qualitative and quantitative data to answer the research questions and come up with solutions. Saunders *et al.* (2007), state that there are two main research choices such as mono-choice and multi-methods which is split into multi-method and mixed method. This research has applied a mixed method to collect qualitative and quantitative data.

Both qualitative and quantitative methods are important when conducting research. However, as with any other issue or topic, mixed method has its advantages and weaknesses that can affect the research. It is important to mention that what makes mixed method a good choice for study is to be able and adapt the best positive aspects of both qualitative and quantitative method of research, combining the two into one method that can be adopted by the researcher. Furthermore, mixed methods of research have been suggested that can be adapted in different research areas such as education, information technology, management and health (Powell *et al.* [2008](#); Molina-Azorin and Lopez-Gamero, [2016](#); Bishop [2015](#); Venkatesh *et al.* [2013](#)). Madrigal and McClain (2012) suggest that by the time that quantitative and qualitative research approaches have been considered, there are other methods that embrace their strengths and weaknesses which can be effective while researching and collecting information as well as analysing the findings. Bryman, (2001) agrees that using mixed methods while conducting research not only brings a combination of several strategies, methods, and approaches, but as well this combination supports the research by improving information that is collected.

By using mixed method research, the researcher does not follow a structured approach regarding design, methods, strategies, and approaches, but bring several various ones together to help the researcher enhance and provide a deeper perspective of information that needs to be collected, as well as improving the way the researcher analyses the collects data by bringing several techniques of analysing both qualitative and quantitative research issues. This data is collected and analysed and presented to the audience in a clearer and deeper way which might the enhance knowledge. A significant reason for applying this method is that as an approach it works out perfectly with pragmatism philosophy (Denscombe, 2007) and the other reason is that the research is includes both qualitative and quantitative analysis to

evaluate the effective usage of technology and ICT in the tourism industry as tools for promoting the sector of tourism in Albania.

3.4.4 Time Horizons

The time to complete a research study can vary on the fact of how the researcher has planned to collect data and answer the research questions. There two types of time completion of a research: cross-sectional research which focuses on certain topic/phenomena and aims to collect the data at a certain point of time. Whereas, longitudinal is the contrary. It aims to research about a problem longer and aims to understand the issue over the time.

By taking into consideration that this research is of an academic nature, means that there is a limited time, a starting date and finishing date, and the researcher has applied a cross sectional study.

3.4.5 Type of data

3.4.5.1 Qualitative Research

According to Atman *et al.* (2010) there are different research methods and design that a researcher can use while conducting research. The most common methods specify the nature and type of the data that the researcher plans to collect and to justify the research topic and aims and objectives. First, is a qualitative method of collecting data which is considered as a research method that focuses on the quality of the information that is to be collected for the research. This is a research method that focuses on theoretical aspects of the research on a certain topic or issue.

Bryman,(2008) assumes that as the method is based on a theoretical perspective the quality of information makes it possible that different groups and people have a better understanding on certain issues and problems. Moreover, Wyse (2011) agrees that as an exploratory research method, qualitative research focuses on providing insights of certain issues and problems to help individuals gain understanding on the topic, plus motives to improve and develop an idea that helps when conducting research. Creswell,(2014) states that qualitative research involves an inductive approach to collect the information about the study. Qualitative research studies can provide details about the human behaviour, emotions, and personality characteristics that are more difficult to collect in quantitative research. Most of the studies in the tourism and hospitality sector adopt a qualitative method of research that is

mostly focused on developing a new strategy or promotional activity for further development or even improving an innovation or framework in the study area for improvement on the destination or organisation where the study is conducted.

According to Watkins (2012) some of the characteristics of using qualitative research are that it is used to adapt results for a large audience and provide results which are understandable for all and convey the same information, so this is what makes qualitative methods important for conducting research.

3.4.5.2- Quantitative Research

The second type of research method is the quantitative method. Methods are separated due to the nature of the study and the nature of information that is going to be collected for the study. It is contrary to qualitative research; quantitative methods of data collection are considered as a method that helps the researcher to collect numerical and statistical data (Babbie Earl, 2010) and information through different approaches and tools like interviews, questionnaires, and surveys (Mujis, 2010).

Creswell (2014) suggests that quantitative research methods do not only collect statistical information, but it is considered to be a full process of collecting data, selecting, analysing, interpreting, and of course presenting data to the audience in a statistical and numerical way. Wyse (2011) argues that quantitative research can be used not only for reading, collecting numerical data but it can be used to count attitudes, behaviour, and opinions regarding a certain issue. Furthermore, quantitative research is used to understand the relation between two variables. Statistical analyses let the researcher release important facts from the research data including preference trends, differences between groups and demographics.

In most cases in the tourism sector, studies that adapt a quantitative method of research focus on statistics such as numbers of tourists in and out, number in accommodation, frequency of travelling, contribution to GDP in the destination preferences by using various numerical analyses.

By considering the nature of quantitative research, this involves different research approaches, designs, and strategies such as descriptive and experimental designs. A descriptive approach is measured only once and then it is analysed based on this measurement whereas the experimental approach is measured twice before the experiment and after finishing the experiment and the analysis of the information is based on both

measurements by highlighting the differences and coming out with results. Creswell(2014) states that in most cases quantitative research involves a deductive approach which includes the introduction of definitions at the beginning of the study. He goes on to say that there are indications of the most important characteristics about why quantitative research should be used to conduct research:

- a) Data is gathered and collected through structured research methods.
- b) Results are based on larger sampling sizes.
- c) Research can be repeated in case of misunderstanding of variables.
- d) All aspects of research are designed and planned before collecting data.
- e) Data is in a numerical and statistical form.
- f) The researcher uses different tools such as questionnaires, interviews, surveys, and computer software to collect the data.

All these characteristics that are involved in the quantitative research make it easier for the researcher to create an idea of what the research is going to be about and the ways of collecting the information hardly need to be modified.

3.4.6 Data collection instruments

This section includes information about procedures which the researcher has followed to collect the information and data to use in the research. As the research has adapted a deductive approach and a mixed method to collect data, this means that information is mixed and combined between both qualitative and quantitative research and information. The researcher has used different techniques to collect information needed for the research. First the researcher used sampling to conduct a questionnaire and interviews to cover all areas of the study, to answer the research question as well as to fulfil the aims and objectives of the research.

3.4.6.1 Sampling techniques

Sampling is an important stage when conducting research because it is one of the main contributions towards the end rationale of the research. Singh (2018) supports the idea that sampling is one of the main determinants of the research accuracy. The researcher had the possibility to conduct research and choose the sample size according to a variety of methods or techniques. There are two main types of sampling methods:

- Probability sampling which is characterised by the randomisation and where every person has an equal right and possibility to participate. This method includes four

different types of sampling: random sampling, systematic, stratified and cluster sampling.

- Probability sampling which targets certain people and not all the population could not be chosen as this would not be helpful for the research. This method includes four types of sampling: convenience, snowball, quota, and persuasive sampling.

3.4.6.2 - Sample size

The purpose of using a sample is to make it easier for the researcher to collect primary data and the characteristics of the population for certain issues, rather than conducting a census of the whole population. The researcher decided to conduct questionnaires and interviews.

The sample size for the interviews was anticipated be around 10-15 interviews on different organisations and tour agencies in two different towns (Elbasan and Tirana) in Albania (tour agencies/organisations).

For purposes of questionnaires sampling this was planned to be around 200 questionnaires to be split into two parts. 100 questionnaires to be used for travellers chosen randomly for the questionnaires to identify travel behaviour and how effective is the usage of technology in the tourism industry and benefits of its use. 100 questionnaires to be conducted on the staff of tourist agencies/organisations that deal everyday with the demands and requirements of customers/travellers. By conducting this through questionnaires, the main purpose was to understand how effective technology is and ICT for the staff in order to help tourists fulfil their demands and requirements, as well as improving image and overall departmental organisation.

Considering the information provided, primary data was collected regarding interviews and questionnaires collected in Albania. This includes different institutions that operate in the tourism sector as well as tourism agencies and organisations from where qualitative and quantitative information was collected. This information was supported by secondary data which the researcher decided to collect through several journals, articles, and books, as well as information provided by different authors who have previously conducted research on the area of the study or a similar subject area, to support and enhance information included and collected for this research.

3.5. Summary of the Data Collection Process

The data collection process is important. When conducting primary research, it is crucial that researchers consider what their aim is, and this should be evident while conducting research. When collecting primary data, the researcher should be considerate regarding the content and structure of questionnaires and ensure that this is in line with the participant's understanding. The researcher should deliver clear information/questions to achieve the research objectives. Similarly, participants should have a clear understanding regarding questions being in the same context with what the researcher is asking.

3.5.1 Development of the Research Questionnaire

The research questionnaire was revised several times making sure that questions will answer the research question and objectives. The help of an expert was received. The expert had several years of experience in the tourism industry and similarly was experienced in research. By reviewing the literature, the expert suggested few changes in terms of length of questions, structure and length of the questionnaire and making sure that questions were related to the research objectives.

The research questionnaire was designed in such a form that it could answer the main questions of the research and data collection based on demographics, use of technology in the tourism industry, and promotional activity to develop the industry. Data was collected considering different variables such as behaviour, opinions, and attributes. Behavioural variables consisted of providing data in what the tour agencies are using now and what are they planning to use in the future related to technological advances. Various opinions provided information regarding the use of technology in the tourism industry and respectively aiming to image development and promotion. Attribute variables refers demographic data or characteristics of tour agencies employers. The researcher used different typed of questions such as open, list category and rating questions which could be converted to quantitative data. However, a few questions were included to provide qualitative data so participants could elaborate more.

3.5.2 Interview Questions

Interview questions were designed to give a deeper understanding of the research. In other ways interview questions where a longer version of questionnaire with the option that

participants were able to elaborate more in chosen areas. Interview questions were revised in terms of content, information, and length. The participants (15 managers) were chosen among 100 tour agencies who participated in the survey and who were previously informed about the research and agreed to participate. The questionnaire focus was everyone who has worked in the agency for more than 6 months, whereas the interview criterion was that the participant should be part of the management team.

3.6 Validity and Reliability of the Research.

Patton (2002) confirms that reliability and validity are two factors that a researcher should be concerned about while designing a study, analysing results, and judging the quality of the study. It is important for the research to be reliable and valid. To reach both these important characteristics, there is a need that data collected to be recent and up-to date.

According to Middleton (2019), validity is understood to be as how a method measures what it is supposed to measure. Similarly, there are four different methods of how to measure validity (Drost, 2011):

First, internal validity has been considered by the researcher to understand that the questionnaire measures plus the objectives that are going to be achieved.

Secondly, content validity of the questionnaire should be evaluated by the researcher and the expert to make sure that all questions contain the right information.

Finally, construct validity refers to understanding if the composition of what the question measures, and indicates an opinion following the question. Furthermore, validity can be assessed by using a pilot study to understand if questions are understandable in relation to the tourism sector, promotional activity and use of technology in the Albanian Tourism Industry.

In terms of interviews and questionnaires these should be chosen in relation to their relationship with the area of study and the interviewer's experience in the tourism industry. Another issue to ensure that the research is reliable and valid is in-depth research that is completed in the literature review. Information and data collected through primary and secondary research should support both the interviews and questionnaires.

To ascertain that the questionnaire was reliable, a pilot study was conducted with seven tour agencies in Albania : a number of suggestions were made related to structure, length and misunderstanding of words.

Suggestions	Corrections
Size of fonts too small	Font size was made bigger From TNR 10 to TNR12
Use of technology was misunderstood relating to the use of the internet	Explanations were given when using technology terms
'If yes, from whom is it managed?'	The questions were a continuous part of previous questions and these were highlighted as earlier references.

Table 3.2 Correction of Pilot study

3.7 Access and Ethical Considerations

Considering interest in the tourism industry after consulting previous studies, the researcher decided to continue investigating this area through a formal researching process. This case study related to the researcher's home country and before starting the research, many tourism agencies were contacted and agreed orally that they would participate in the research. For the survey 100 questionnaires were completed in two cities in Albania, the capital Tirana and Elbasan. While conducting questionnaire research, the researcher requested to managers if they would like to participate in personal interviews which would be more comprehensive than the questionnaire. Even though participants initially agreed, some did change their minds to be interview but instead, provided written answers to interview questions. In fact, the interview question was sent to 50 tour agencies and only twelve interviews were returned to the researcher in a written format and were not recorded verbally.

3.7.1 Ethical Considerations

Being a student at UWS there are codes of ethics that researcher needs to follow while conducting research the significant ones being:

- The research should not have any intention to harm, but only to relate to matters of progress and improvement,
- All participants had the right to participate or withdraw at any time during the research,
- All participants were offered equal treatment,
- Personal information of participants was kept confidential. At the same time, the researcher considered several steps regarding ethics recommended by UWS,

- Privacy. Here, the researcher decided not to collect the names of the participants to maintain their privacy. However, few of them provided their names, although this was not necessarily used in the research, even with the participant's consent.
- Volunteer participation gave respondents the right to choose if they wanted to participate in this research. As volunteer participants, they had the right to give their opinions and withdraw from the research at any time.
- Confidentiality. In this context, information collected from participants was kept confidential and only used for research purposes. The data collected was kept in a drawer that no one could access, except the researcher.
- Participant information sheets were provided with all information regarding the research topic and the institutions and places where the research was taking place. For each participant who voluntarily participated was provided a copy of this information sheet with a number corresponding to their answer to the survey.
- The approved ethics form and participant information sheet is included in the Appendices.

3.8 Chapter Summary

In conclusion, methodology is an important chapter as it is where the researcher plans and chooses all methods and techniques to be used during the research to collect data needed to support the study related to effective usage of technology and ICT in the Albanian tourism industry and to improve and develop the sector by considering promotional activity through technological means. The researcher planned the research and decided to use a pragmatic philosophy which gives to the researcher some flexibility to mix and match methods and techniques to conduct the research. In terms of approach and strategy the researcher decided to use a mixed approach which allows the researcher to combine the positive aspects of both inductive and deductive approaches to applied to this research.

As the research is specifically concerned about the usage of technology and its effects on the tourism industry in Albanian, it is specified and considered as a case study strategy as it focuses mostly on a singular issue and destination and the data is a collected for the same issue and problem and destination.

The choice of research philosophy, approach, design, data collection methods, procedures, ethics, and reliability are aimed at making contributions to research knowledge in this area. It is contended that the research been planned and well organized to make it easier for the reader to comprehend certain issues that have been highlighted.

CHAPTER 4 - DATA ANALYSIS AND FINDINGS.

4.1 Introduction

This chapter elaborates primary data/information that has been collected by the author to support this research. As already mentioned, the researcher decided to use questionnaires and interviews to collect the data that was needed. This supports the end findings, as the researcher collected secondary data from appropriate literature.

This chapter also includes an overview of methodology that the researcher used while collecting data, data instruments, and elaborating the profile of participants. Another important point is data analysis which provided an overview of data and its presentation. Furthermore, this includes analysis of data through univariate means such as descriptive and exploratory analyses. The researcher presented data through graphs and tables plus an interpretation of data collected for each theme.

4.2 Research Methodology

As mentioned in earlier chapters the researcher used a mixed method approach to collect the data whose main purpose was to support the research. In this research, the researcher applied a case study strategy which evaluates processes, events, and programs. In this way it justifies the purpose of the research and highlights significant aspects of the research. The data collection process was a combination of interviews and 2 different types of questionnaires.

The researcher decided to conduct two different questionnaires to collect different information or data as well as interviews in Albania. The first questionnaire is called ‘tourism agencies and tour operators’. By administering this questionnaire. the researcher received information about agencies and tour operators in Albania, plus information regarding levels of technology usage and how tour operators promote tourism products for local and foreign tourists, in addition to different methods of promotion strategies that agencies use and what kind of difficulties they face during promotional activity.

The second questionnaire was a more general one and was conducted in different areas of London by choosing samples randomly. By administering this second questionnaire the researcher was able to collect information about travel behaviour from a sample of travellers and as well as understanding the effectiveness of technology and how useful it is for customers in their decision-making processes, and motivation and perception of tourists towards a particular destination.

4.2.1 Sample size

In terms of sample size, it was different between questionnaires and interviews.

Questionnaires were supposed to be completed by 200 participants but 190 were returned to the researcher. In terms of face-to-face interviews, the researcher planned to interview 20 people from different backgrounds related to tourism industry but in total 12 interviews were completed in a written form rather than recorded and then sent back to the researcher. From this total of 12 interviews, 5 of interviews took place through the phone and the rest were personal.

4.2.2 Data collection instruments

➤ Quantitative data

One questionnaire was a mix of both qualitative and quantitative information that took place in Albania and was designed for tour agencies and tour operator's staff regarding the technology usage and its effectiveness in connection with organisational performance. The sample was chosen randomly for the questionnaire in Albania, by asking organisations if they would like to participate in the questionnaire. The researcher chose two different cities for the questionnaire, to understand the variety and difference between the same organisations but in different cities. In most cases managers/owners were the ones who participated in the questionnaire so as not to stop the rest of the staff from fulfilling their everyday duties.

The second questionnaire was mostly designed to collect qualitative and quantitative mixed method information of both information regarding tourism behaviour and their travel frequency and how the internet and technology influences these stages. The sampling method regarding this questionnaire was again voluntary and participants are randomly chosen. This questionnaire took place around the Barnet area as the researcher lived near there.

➤ Qualitative data

As previously mentioned, the focus of this research was mostly on tour agencies and customers and how effective technology and ICT is in tourism industry globally and especially in Albania. The researcher planned to interview managers and business developers of tour agencies in Albania, but at the end none of the agencies accepted giving a recorded interview. Instead, they were happy to provide written responses to the interview questions. This was due to their busy schedules, as the time-period corresponded to the summer break as requirements for holidays from inside the country was high.

Interview questions focusing on tour agencies and especially managers located in two different cities, in the capital Tirana, where numbers of tour agencies are higher in and the second city is the researcher's hometown. There was a total of 12 written interviews which were sent back to the researcher and this information has been used in this research.

4.3 Profile of respondents

By taking into consideration that the topic is focused on a case study on the destination of Albania, it makes it difficult to conduct the research from the UK. As already mentioned, data has been collected through two main instruments, these being questionnaires and interviews. It is important to mention that participants for both instruments come from different organisations, but these operate in the tourism sector in Albania.

- **Interviews**

As mentioned, the researcher only received 12 interviews from a total of 20. The focus of these interviews concerned people who owned or managed a tour agency or organisation. However, the interviews were mostly in a written form. What was important was that participants answered every interview question. Interviews were focused the Albanian capital, Tirana, where the number of this agencies and organisations is higher.

- **Questionnaires**

Questionnaires were split in two parts according to their purpose. The first questionnaire was designed for tour agencies and organisations and took place in two cities of Tirana and Elbasan, due to the number of agencies in these cities. Participants to this questionnaire were people from both genders who worked in this agency in the position of staff, managers, and entrepreneurs. Every participant voluntarily took part in the questionnaire and was free in terms of completing it.

The second questionnaire which was designed for tourists and their travelling behaviour and how effective they found technology usage. This questioning took place in London and it was total free for volunteer participation.

4.4 Analysis of collected data

Analysing and interpreting the collected data is an important stage of the research. According to Cohen *et al.*,(2007), data analysis is considered as the process in which the collected data

is inspected, selected, transformed, and modelled with the purpose to reveal important and useful information regarding a certain topic. In this research, the researcher decided to collect the data through two main instruments which have been discussed earlier. The researcher used univariate analysis which is a form of analysing data in terms of one theme at once by describing and exploring data collected. Furthermore, the researcher has interpreted information of data after each graph or table for each theme.

Reliability test for questionnaire nr 1

Reliability Statistics			
Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items	
.751	.729	14	

Item Statistics			
	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
A	4.1684	.98556	95
B	3.9368	.90871	95
C_R	3.7053	1.34381	95
D	3.7579	.99697	95
E	3.7579	1.20915	95
F	3.3895	1.17866	95
G	3.5895	1.25897	95
H	3.3474	.93135	95
I_R	3.4000	1.29154	95
K	3.7684	.92774	95
L	3.9789	.77155	95
M	4.1053	.60974	95
N	4.4105	.55534	95
J_R	2.8211	1.23752	95

Figure4.1- Reliability statistics for questionnaire 1.

Reliability test for questionnaire nr 2

Reliability Statistics	
Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.700	10

Item Statistics			
	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
SWLS1	3.2121	.52045	99
SWLS2	3.2525	.64434	99
SWLS3	3.1515	.69051	99
SWLS4	3.1818	.64466	99
SWLS5	3.2020	.69956	99
SWLS6	3.0707	.74577	99
SWLS7	3.2121	.57628	99
SWLS8	3.2121	.74605	99
SWLS9	3.3333	.58902	99
SWLS10	3.3636	.54313	99

Figure 4.2 Reliability statistics for questionnaire nr 2

Considering the statistics from both questionnaires, reliability test was used in order to measure the consistency of items that measure in similar scale. For questionnaire 1, Figure 4.1 Reliability test was an overall 0.751 alpha coefficient of 14 items. Whereas for questionnaire 2, figure 4.3, the results of reliability test is overall 0.700 alpha coefficient for 10 items. As the requested value of alpha coefficient is accepted at 0.700, indicates that data can be considered as reliable.

4.4.1 Qualitative data analysis interviews.

Presentation of interview forms.

As mentioned, there were 12 interview forms returned to the researcher and these are used to support this study, 5 of them being telephone based.

Interview form samples and how themes have been extracted.

Based on information collected during the interviews, the researcher considered the questions and decided to analyse them manually rather than using any statistical tools. Extracted themes come from what respondents said and are now analysed.

By considering information received through interview forms located in the Appendix section, it is important to state that the Albanian tourism industry is on a right path towards competing with neighbouring countries. As mentioned in the other sections of this research, technology and ICT do affect the development of the tourism industry as well as other branches to which tourism industry is related.

Based on information collected, the Albanian tourism industry usually uses technology as a tool for promotion and communication with potential tourists. Focusing on different groups of tourists at the same time, the internet has become one of the main frameworks that most tour agencies and operators rely upon regarding development. Online websites and different apps of social media have created an easy and cheaper way for businesses operating in the tourism industry to promote and sell their products to potential customers, as well as communicating with them in a quicker way by sharing the most important information.

Considering the analysis based on the main themes of the interview the following can be concluded:

- ❖ experience in tourism sector – all participants considered their experience in the tourism industry as an important stage of their life when working with people not only brings them profits but enhances their knowledge.
- ❖ global tourism – all participants think that Global Tourism is developing very quickly and this has a positive impact in the global economy and employment as well as investments.
- ❖ impact of tourism industry in the Albanian development – participants agree that the tourism industry is still developing in Albania and this brings a positive impact towards overall development of the country including the economy, investments, infrastructure and so on.
- ❖ tourism industry and internet participants generally agreed that the combination between the two has created easier ways and paths for business in the tourism sector to perform and benefit from it.
- ❖ role of technology and ICT – participants confirmed that the tourism industry has been shaped by using technology and ICT, and the Albanian tourism industry has shown that

technology has become one of the main tools in promotion and overall performance of businesses in the tourism industry.

- ❖ Levels of technology usage considering all 12 interviews – participants confirmed that the level of technology usage in the Albanian Tourism was between 60%-80% adoption. This includes overall performance which these organisations perform during a working day.
- ❖ Promotional activity- considering interviews it is important to mention that participants confirmed that more than 90% of tourism businesses use social media as a main tool for promotion. This is because it saves time while performing work as well as it targets many groups of customers at the same time.

However, it is important to mention that even though technology and tourism industry Albania appear to collaborate quite well together, it is important for Albania as a tourist destination to focus more attention on standards that offers to customers such as professional customer service, accommodation units and infrastructure. Appropriate investment clearly would improve the overall tourism sector.

4.4.2 Analysis of Questionnaire 1

‘Tourism agencies and tour operators’ was conducted in Albania and it related to a sample of 100 questionnaires from which 95 of were completed and returned for analysis. This questionnaire was conducted in two different cities of Albania: Elbasan, and Tirana, where the largest number of tour agencies and tour operators are located. The questionnaire was comprised of three different sections where each one covers a certain subject that helps understanding the objectives of this research.

Question – Gender

		Gender			Cumulative
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Percent
Valid	Female	47	49.5	49.5	49.5
	Male	48	50.5	50.5	100.0
	Total	95	100.0	100.0	

Figure 4.3 Gender

Case Processing Summary

	Included		Cases Excluded		Total	
	N	Percent	N	Percent	N	Percent
Gender	95	100.0%	0	0.0%	95	100.0%
Age	95	100.0%	0	0.0%	95	100.0%

Report

	Gender	Age
Mean	1.5053	2.0000
N	95	95
Std. Deviation	.50262	1.07188

This question was asked to identify the general ratio of male or female employers in the tourism industry. This gives information about the gender ratio of employees who perform tourism jobs. According to the table (based on staff found on the day of running the questionnaire) it is shown that the number of females and males working in the tourism sector, especially tourist agencies and tour operators are similar, and the sector is one of those where there is no gender difference.

Age

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
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Valid	20-30 years old	38	40.0	40.0	40.0
	31-40 years old	31	32.6	32.6	72.6
	41-50 years old	18	18.9	18.9	91.6
	51-60 years old	4	4.2	4.2	95.8
	over 60 years old	4	4.2	4.2	100.0
	Total	95	100.0	100.0	

Figure 4.4 Response to Age

This question was asked to receive clear information about the age of individuals that favour working in the tourism industry, particularly tourism agencies and as tour operators. According to this table it is shown that the age which is more favoured in this industry is 20 to 40 years old. This might come about because of the nature of work such as in some cases it requires travelling to check latest deals and places. According to the table this industry does not exclude the other generations as there are still people of age 50 years old working in tourism agencies.

Question – What is the Size of the business?

Organisation			
Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
<hr/>			

Valid	Small	74	77.9	77.9	77.9
	Large	21	22.1	22.1	100.0
	Total	95	100.0	100.0	

Figure 4.5 Size of the business

Considering the nature of the tourism industry in Albania, which is characterised by slow developing steps, this has affected the size of the tourism agencies and organisations that leads into the fact that most of businesses in tourism industry are small sized businesses which have no more than 4 employers including the owner, manager, and staff. According to INSTAT (2017) a total number of tour operators and organisations that operate in Albania is around 300 tour agencies and only 2 tourism organisations, one of which is ATA –Albanian Tourism Association and National Tourism Organisation. However, this number is split throughout different cities in Albania, but most of these tour agencies are in the capital although still there are large numbers of tour operators operating in seaside cities which in certain seasons attracts large numbers of tourists. The questionnaire focused on two different cities in Albania, Tirana, the capital, and Elbasan. In these two cities the sizes of business which agreed to participate considered themselves to be small businesses 77.9% with a small number of employers. However, 21, or 22.1% of participants considered themselves to be large businesses or companies which operate in the tourism sector and have a larger number of employers and well as a wide variety of products and services.

Question - **What is your position in the company?**

Position

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	entrepreneur	24	25.3	25.3	25.3
	Manager	38	40.0	40.0	65.3
	other	33	34.7	34.7	100.0
	Total	95	100.0	100.0	

Figure 4.6- Position in the Company

Considering that most of agencies that participated in the questionnaire were considered to be small businesses, and the number of employers was low, it makes it possible that in most cases, owners of businesses manage and perform the basic duties themselves rather than ancillary staff. In this case owners are responsible for management and other basic duties such as promotion, marketing, and sales. Furthermore, the results of the questionnaire were split into three sectors such as entrepreneur which contained 25.3% of respondents; managers were 40% of respondents which in most cases were the same people as owners of the business and other were 34.7% of the respondents from a total of 95 participants.

Question- **Of which category is your clientele?**

Customers

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Mainly Albanian Nationals	69	72.6	72.6	72.6

Both	26	27.4	27.4	100.0
Total	95	100.0	100.0	

Figure 4.7 Nature of the customers

Considering the size of organisations that agreed to participate in the questionnaire, it was understood that most participants located in Albania operate mainly inside the country by having a clientele composed mainly of Albanians. Around 69 participants or 77.6% percent of them confirmed that their customers were mainly Albanians. 26 organisations or 27.4% of participants confirmed that their clientele was composed of both Albanian and foreign nationals. This is supported by the size of organisations where large companies and foreign customers chose to ask for information on local companies and their activities. Foreign customers are mostly active on the social media and online to search for and receive information, especially during the popular seasons such as summer and spring or related to any event occurring in Albania.

Question - What type of promotional activity is mostly undertaken by your organisation to attract tourists?

Promotion

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Advertising	18	18.9	18.9	18.9
	Brochures	15	15.8	15.8	34.7
	Sales Promotion	37	38.9	38.9	73.7

Social Media	25	26.3	26.3	100.0
Total	95	100.0	100.0	

Figure4.8- Promotional activity preferred to use

Promotional activity is an important stage of development in any organisation or business, and it is composed of a variety of activities which contribute towards the overall advancement of the business. The variety of activities in promotion are wide and mostly focus on services which aim to target larger groups of customers. Such activities, advertising and brochures, sales promotion and social media have recently demonstrated that a business can use these different techniques to improve their services and products. Considering research in Albanian tourism agencies has concluded that most agencies use sales promotion (38.9%) to promote their activities and business. This is followed by promotional activity through social media which is 26.3%, and this is an activity which aims to target customers with different backgrounds and nationality. Advertising is used by 18.9% of participants and brochures are used by 15.8%. However, in most cases it was confirmed by participants that they usually combine techniques to benefit more from promotion activity of organisations.

Question- **What media does your organisation use for the promotional activity?**

		Techniques			Cumulative
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Percent
Valid	online Sales	36	37.9	37.9	37.9
	Social Media	50	52.6	52.6	90.5
	TV/Radio	3	3.2	3.2	93.7
	Newspaper/magazines	6	6.3	6.3	100.0
	Total	95	100.0	100.0	

Figure 4.9- techniques used for promotion.

It has become a trend now that organisations perform promotional activities by choosing cheaper and easier techniques that can be effective for their business. Promotional activity is important for organisations as this is the way to increase their business performance. As Albania is a small European country and its population is around 3 million people, tour agencies and organisations try to focus not only on the national market, but also target international tourists and customers. Considering the results of 95 agencies that participated

in the questionnaire it is shown that agencies focus mostly in adapting online sales by 37.9% as a technique for promotion. What is most important is that agencies are tending to adopt social media techniques by 52.6%. TV/Radio and newspaper and magazines respectively are used by agencies by 3.2% and 6.3% which most cases are combined with other techniques and used together to reach different groups of customers.

Question - How does your organisation attract tourists?

		Tourist Attraction			Cumulative
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Percent
Valid	Holiday packages	24	25.3	25.3	25.3
	product/services	19	20.0	20.0	45.3
	Season offers	30	31.6	31.6	7
					6.8
	Service quality	12	12.6	12.6	89.5
	Different Events	10	10.5	10.5	100.0
Total		95	100.0	100.0	

Figure 4.10- Tourist attraction

Albania has become a country which is visited throughout the whole year as it offers a wide variety of products and services. From the holiday season in summer, cultural, and historical tourism, nowadays winter tourism such as skiing is attracting more tourists. Adaptation of

different products and services throughout the year has made possible for tourists to consider Albania as a destination that can be visited at any time. According to questionnaire results offers made during peak seasons attract more tourists. This is confirmed by 31.6% of participants which used offers to attract tourists. This is followed by holiday packages by 25.3%, products and services are used by 20% of agencies and then service and different events respectively 12.1% and 10.5%. However, there are opportunities for agencies to use more than one technique at the same time to attract tourists.

Question - Do you think technology plays an important role in promoting tourism products/destinations?

Technology Usage

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	No, it does not matter	1	1.1	1.1	1.1
	Maybe	42	44.2	44.2	45.3
	Yes, it is important	52	54.7	54.7	100.0
	Total	95	100.0	100.0	

Figure 4.11- Role of technology

As mentioned already research technology plays an important role in the tourism industry as it enables information to be spread quicker and easier by targeting more customers at the same time. According to tourism agencies in Albania it is confirmed that 55% of participants find technology important in their everyday routine as well as they consider it as a tool for

further development and faster service. 44 % of participants were in no doubt that technology is important and confirmed at the same time, that advances in technology have made the industry perform faster and better. Only 1% of participants thought that technology was not important so long as the agency knew how to keep their loyal customers happy.

Question- Does your enterprise have access to the Internet?

		Approach			Cumulative
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Percent
Valid	Yes	95	100.0	100.0	100.0

Figure 4.12- Internet access

The internet has affected almost every industry and sector by influencing everyday work and performance. As mentioned, most agencies in Albanian tourism perform their duties and share information about products and offers online. This is supported by results of the questionnaire which shows that all 95 participants have access to internet. This access allows them to do their everyday services such as booking as well as contacting customers and using it for promotional activities.

Question - What frameworks of technology do you use to connect to the internet?

		Technology Techniques			
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Dial-up Modem	7	7.4	7.4	7.4
	ADSL	58	61.1	61.1	68.4

Broadband	15	15.8	15.8	84.2
wireless connection	15	15.8	15.8	100.0
Total	95	100.0	100.0	

Figure 4.13-framework of technology used

Considering that all participants have access to internet leads to the question of which framework they use for allowing internet access. By taking into consideration results, 61.1% of participant use ADSL connections which is like broadband and it comes as a packet with phone numbers as well as internet connections. This connection varies in strength and it is used to spread the information very quickly and easily. This is followed by broadband and wireless connection by 15.8% which is still used for sharing and collecting information as well as operating devices in the offices to perform their duties.

Question - Does your organisation use a computer network for communication?

Figure 4.14 Use of computer for Communication

As already mentioned most tourist agencies already have access to the internet during their everyday work. The results of the questionnaire confirm that 77% of respondents use their computer network to communicate with customers and sometimes to reach new customers through this network. Only 23 % of them do not use a computer network to communicate. The communication is used between the organisation and customers to give information and in some cases, it is used to receive feedback from customers to be used from organisations for improvement if needed.

Question - Does your organisation has a web page?

Figure 4.15- Webpage

Most business have now created websites to be present not only in commercial markets, but to support it by online commerce as well. This phenomenon has spread quickly. According to the questionnaire results it is shown that 91 of the participants have confirmed their business have a website which is mostly used to enhance the performance of the business. Another reason for using a website, it is that sharing information about services and products that the organisation offers and collecting information from the customers and their requirements is an advantage. Only 4 participants confirmed that their business does not own any website, so they do not see any difference in performance or business development.

Question- If you have a website by whom is it managed?

Figure 4.16- Webpage management

Based on the results of the questionnaire in different tourism agencies in Albania it is shown that most of these agencies have a website that they use to promote and contact their customers which is mainly managed by people from inside the organisation, respectively 87 participants manage their own website by their staff. This is perhaps as the best way to deal with customers to keep in continuous contact and everyday needs of the organisation. Only 8 participants confirmed, their websites are managed by individuals that are not in the organisation, which means they are only responsible for management of the website. According to them, this method is better because everyone in the organisation has their own

duties to perform and there is no need for confusion or doing two/ three duties at the same time.

Question - During a normal working day, what percent of work is made through computers?

Figure 4. 17- work performed through Computer

Taking into consideration that nowadays most business perform their duties online and most of the basic services are performed through computers and other similar devices, has made work easier and quicker. Considering the questionnaire that took place in Albania it is shown that most tourism agencies use computers and devices to perform basic duties and services. Work performed through computers is split between 25-49% of overall work that is performed by 39% of participants. 50-74% of daily work is performed by computers by 40% of participants. However, there was a small percentage of participants; around 6% that perform more than 75% of their daily work through computers. This daily work that is performed through computers is mostly basic duties such as bookings, and database issues.

Question- Tick one of the following statements if you agree, disagree, or have a neutral opinion.

Figure 4.18- Results of the Likert Scale

The graph is a combination of all statements relating the last question of the questionnaire that took place in tourism agencies and organisations in Albania. This question is composed of a sum of statements which indicate the importance of technology usage and effectiveness of internet for these tourism agencies. Colours correspond to answers which are split on 1- Do not agree. 2- Neutral. 3- Agree. 4- Strongly agree. On the other side letters correspond to each statement.

A- According to the researcher using Technology and Information and Communication Technology gives more opportunity to enhance the organisational image. By considering the result of the questionnaire 52 participants agreed and 39 have strongly agreed that using technology gives more opportunity to improve organisational image and performance

B- The use of IT and ICT in the organisation can provide valuable information that can help customers to make decisions. According to the results 69 participants agreed and 20 strongly agreed that use of IT and ICT is effective for the organisation and customers, and at the same time as it helps them to take decisions regarding destination. Only 6 participants showed a neutral opinion by stating that this does not affect their organisation in any circumstances.

C- It is thought that technology takes a lot of time to do mechanical actions (performing, data jams) and does not allow enough time to perform other work. In the contrary with the two first statements, participants disagreed that the statement that usage of technology takes more time that usual and most of time does not allow employees to perform any other duties,

respectively. 53 participants think this is wrong, 24 had a neutral opinion and 18 agreed with the statement by admitting that this procedure makes them perform slower than usual. However, this is combined with a variety of duties that are performed at the same time and not only use of technology.

D- The use of IT and ICT allows access, collection, and distribution of information more easily. Most participants respectively 63 of them have agreed and 19 strongly agreed that using IT and ICT allows them to collect information about customers and distribute this information to potential customers without any high costs.

E- The internet allows companies to have a better communication with customers. According to the results this statement was agreed strongly by 79 participants (52-27). Participants found it easier to communicate with customers easier than before and this is a quicker procedure which saves time as well as cutting costs.

F- There is an increased number of customers who visit websites for travel purposes. There was a sizeable number of participants that showed neutral opinions (39 participants) regarding the statement that tourists visit websites for travel purposes. This is because they think that travelling is not the only reasons why tourists visit websites, but as well as for general information such as cultural and historical purposes. On the other side 43 participants agreed and 12 have strongly agreed that the phenomena of customers visiting websites for travel purposes has become their main duty as this influences their decision making.

G- The internet means less marketing and promotional costs compared to traditional methods (direct contacts with sale agents, leaflets, brochures). Since the adaptation of Internet and IT and ICT on tourism agencies and organisations it has become easier to for these businesses to perform their marketing and promotional activities within a low budget and cutting costs. 61 participants agreed that this technique allows them to reach more customers at the same time as well as their market which is expanded globally. However, there were participants that disagreed with this statement as they state that methods of face-to-face marketing is lost, and less contact happens between them and customers as everything is based on online performance.

I- The internet is a way to increase business profit and staff performance. The internet has become a necessity for every type of business as most business is based on the internet. In the tourism industry the internet is effective and has been considered as a tool that contributes to

development of the business and increasing profits. Due to most programs and training that is based online internet, this is also seen as a framework to increase the performance of employers. According to the results, 44 participants agreed, and 9 strongly agreed that the internet is seen as a tool for improvement and increasing staff performance. On the other side 36 participants out of 95 were neutral and 5 disagreed with this statement which means that they see internet as a help for improvement, but not up to the stage that the internet can improve the performance of employers. According to them it needs training and experience to improve performance and overall customer service.

4.4.3 - Analysis of questionnaire number 2.

The purpose of this study was to explore the level of use of information technology from tourism enterprises, focusing on accommodation units, travel agencies and tourist organisations, as well as how IT is used for tourism promotion to develop the sector. The aim of this questionnaire was to identify levels of technology usage and technology effectiveness regarding tourist requirements and requests. The focus of this questionnaire was to identify tourism behaviour, where and how tourists prefer to travel, what do they need to take into consideration before travelling, effects of promotion campaigns as well as recognition of the internet and technology effectiveness. Variables used in the questionnaire are presented as single variables, followed by frequency tables and graphs as well as descriptive analyses. The questionnaire in UK and the sample was chosen randomly to identify these behaviours and influences. To reach the objective and collect information about the topic the researcher used a total of 100 questionnaires that have been used in the analysis.

Variable 1- Gender

		Gender			
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Female	55	55.0	55.0	55.0
	Male	45	45.0	45.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Figure 4.19- Gender

The first variable of the questionnaire is Gender. This information was collected to understand tourists and their preferences based on gender. According to information collected and the graphs it is shown that the highest percentage of participants were females at 55% and male participants were 45 %.

Variable 2 – Age

		Age			Cumulative
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Percent
Valid	20-30 years old	28	28.0	28.0	28.0
	31-40 years old	31	31.0	31.0	59.0
	41-50 years old	19	19.0	19.0	78.0
	51-60 years old	12	12.0	12.0	90.0
	61 years old and over	10	10.0	10.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Figure 4.20- Age

The second variable of the questionnaire is age. This information was collected to receive a variety of information regarding differences in age which influences requirements of participants. According to the table, the researcher split the age into five different age groups. Taking into the consideration these age groups participants aged 20-30 years old were 28%, 31-40 years old 31%, 41-50 years old 19%, 51-60 years old 12% and the last category was 60 years old and over which was 10%. The aim of choosing different age groups was to identify differences between the participant's age regarding their travel behaviour, requirements and how effective is internet and technology for each age group.

Variable 3- Occupation

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Student	25	25.0	25.0	25.0
	Doctor	2	2.0	2.0	27.0
	Teacher	7	7.0	7.0	34.0
	Other	66	66.0	66.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Figure 4.21- Occupation

The next variable of the questionnaire was occupation. This question was asked to participants to collect information regarding their professional background as one of the reasons for mass travelling is work and business. In addition, the aim of collecting occupation information through this questionnaire was to identify the frequency of travel for participants as well as different choices between travellers with different backgrounds.

Variable 4- Travel Frequency

		Travel Frequency			
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Once a year	41	41.0	41.0	41.0
	Twice a year	30	30.0	30.0	71.0
	More than twice	9	9.0	9.0	80.0
	Rarely	20	20.0	20.0	100.0

	100	100.0	100.0	
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Figure 4.22 Travel frequency

Another question was travel frequency. The aim of this question was to understand tourist behaviour towards travelling and the time they spent travelling considering per year. Tourist behaviour is related to their professional background and everyday work. According to data collected, 41 % like to travel at least once a year. The reasons of travelling might differ for each participant even though they travel at least once a year. On the other hand, 30% of participants stated that they usually travel twice a year, and this is for different reasons. 9% of participants travel usually more than twice per year and this might come as a combination of work and leisure which makes them travel more than twice. On the other hand, 20% of participants stated that they travel not even once a year, is very rarely, and this is only when they consider travelling outside their country. By considering this information the researcher asked questions related to having trips within the country during the year. The answer was more than twice or three times per year is why their travel outside the country it is not very often. However, this reason did not apply to all 20% participant.

Variable 5- Preferred Destination

		Preferred destination			Cumulative
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Percent
Valid	Europe	42	42.0	42.0	42.0
	Africa	6	6.0	6.0	48.0
	India	11	11.0	11.0	59.0
	Asia	15	15.0	15.0	74.0
	America	2	2.0	2.0	76.0
	Other	24	24.0	24.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Figure 4.23 Preferred touristic destination

Considering information collected regarding the frequency of travel by participants, the researcher found it important to collect information about their preferred destination, regardless of how many times they travel per year. The researcher did not include certain countries in the list of places where to travel but decided to group them into continents like Europe where participant choice was 42%, Africa – participant choice was 6%, India –choice was 11%, Asia –choice was 15%, America was 2%. The last option - other- includes answers such as new destinations or specific countries or for those travelling more than once a year it

was a combination of destinations which were different. What is important to mention is that in most of the cases the travel choice has to do with the origin and background of participants as in most cases they go back to visit their family and friends.

Variable 6- Promotion Influence

		Promotion Influence			Cumulative
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Percent
Valid	No	12	12.0	12.0	12.0
	Yes	88	88.0	88.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Figure 4.24- Influence of Promotion

Variable 7- Type of Promotion

Type of promotion.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Travel agencies promotion	19	19.0	20.4	20.4
	Friends or relatives	38	38.0	40.9	61.3
	Social Media	30	30.0	32.3	93.5
	Other	6	6.0	6.5	100.0
	Total	93	93.0	100.0	
Total		100	100.0		

Figure 4.25- Type of promotion that influences customers decision making process.

Promotion is one of the most important stages where a company or destination influences the customers and their decision making process. In most cases promotion is considered one of the main factors that changes tourist behaviour as well as the way business operates in the market. Considering information collected by the questionnaire, 100 people participated and this showed that promotion influences tourists’ choices. This includes any type of promotion activity used by business and agencies to promote their products and services. According to collected data it was stated that 88% of participants agreed that they have been influenced by promotional activities when they made decisions. Only 12% of participants stated that they have never been influenced by promotional activities regarding their travelling and decision-making processes.

In terms of the promotional type which have influenced tourist decision making process and their behaviour towards tourist destinations in 7 cases, answers were considered lost or missing because when participants stated they have not been influenced by promotional activity, they preferred not to answer regarding any type of promotion which might influence their behaviour. In terms promotional activity influence, 38% of participants considerer promotion by their friends and relatives as more reliable and trustworthy promotion. Secondly, promotion through social media influences 30% of participants. This comes as a

combination by ease of access of information as well as feedback which is given by other tourists regarding certain destinations or product/services. Thirdly, travel agency promotion was chosen by 19% of participants as a type of promotion which they could rely on and influence their travel behaviour and shape their decisions. However, 6% of participants chose the option other in the types of promotion, but none stated any example of the type of promotion they consider when taking decisions.

Variable 8- **Internet usage to sell products/services.**

Internet_usage_to_sell products

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Yes	71	71.0	71.0	71.0
	No	2	2.0	2.0	73.0
	Depends on the chosen destination	27	27.0	27.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Figure 4.26 Internet usage to sell Touristic products

The tourism industry is one of the industries which is widely using internet and technology to perform in the market. By using the internet, business adapt techniques, software and applications which allow them to have better communication with their existing market, aiming to reach new one as well as to communicate their offers, products, and services. According to questionnaire results, it was shown that 71% think that businesses and agencies that operate in the tourism industry use the internet as a tool for promoting and selling their products and services. 7% of participants think that internet usage for promotion activities and selling products depends on the chosen destination if it is appropriate for the business that operates in the industry. 2% of the participants think that internet is not used in tourist agencies for promotional services as there is no difference in its usage.

The last question was to tick any of the statements by using satisfaction with life scale by using disagree and strongly agree. The statements correspond to each graph and analyses corresponding to each statement. Each statement has been named SWLS and than 1,2,3 and so on for each one.

Statement 1- I think technology has impacted positively on the tourism industry since its introduction.

SWLS1

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Neutral	5	5.0	5.0	5.0
	Agree	69	69.0	69.0	74.0
	Strongly Agree	26	26.0	26.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Figure 4.27 Impact of technology in the tourism industry

For many years, the tourism industry and other sectors have shown that technology has greatly improved them by introducing techniques, methods and new tools which facilitate work, improves work performance as well as improving and developing the whole industry. Technology has become essential in tourism industry because through it business and agencies can easily communicate with costumers by facilitating these communication channels and the services they provide. According to the questionnaire, regarding the statement that technology has positively impacted tourism industry since its introduction was agreed by 69% of participants and 26% of them strongly agreed by stating that technology has built up the tourism sector all over the world. Only 5% of participants stated that their opinion was neutral which means that they consider technology to be a helpful tool in the tourism industry but not essential for its development.

Statement 2 - I think the adaptation of various technologies has facilitated work for tourism and other organisations in the sector

SWLS2

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Neutral	11	11.0	11.1	11.1
	Agree	52	52.0	52.5	63.6
	Strongly Agree	36	36.0	36.4	100.0
	Total	99	99.0	100.0	
Missing	System	1	1.0		

Total	100	100.0		
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Figure 4.28- Technology as a job facilitator (usefulness and ease of use)

Technology has positively impacted tourism industry for years. It is shown in many articles and research that technology has already facilitated work for the business in this industry. With adaptation of this technology, business can reach customers easily and share information with them quickly. According to results from the questionnaire is it shown that most of participants - 52% agree and 36% of participants strongly agree with the statement that the adaptation of various technologies has facilitated work for tourism agencies and other organisations in this sector. This is obvious even for customers/tourists by the variety of products and services they receive in a quicker period than before.

Statement 3 - I think internet and technology usage helps to communicate with customers and vice versa.

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Disagree	1	1.0	1.0	1.0
	Neutral	14	14.0	14.0	15.0
	Agree	54	54.0	54.0	69.0
	Strongly Agree	31	31.0	31.0	100.0
	Agree				
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Figure 4.29 Communication through technology

Considering information collected by the questionnaire, participants agreed by 54% and strongly agreed by 31% with the statement that internet and technology usage helps to communicate with customers and vice versa. Only 1 participant thought that this statement was not true, and usage of internet does not help to communicate with costumers. However, research and different articles have shown that the service has become faster with usage of the internet in tourism industries and communication has become easier and faster.

Statement 4- I think that using Information Technology and Information and Communication Technology gives more oppportunity to reach customers and new markets.

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Neutral	13	13.0	13.0	13.0
Agree	56	56.0	56.0	69.0
Strongly Agree	31	31.0	31.0	100.0
Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Figure 4.30 Technology as a tool to attract customers

According to information collected by the questionnaire, the statement that using Information Technology and Information and Communication Technology gives more opportunity to reach customers and new markets it was stated that 56% of respondents agreed and 31% strongly agreed with this statement and 13 % of participant shared a neutral opinion as technology gives more opportunity to reach the customers. However, considering data regarding this issue it is shown that technology helps the tourism industry and respectively businesses operating in this industry to reach their customers and share with them information regarding products and services.

Statement 5- I think that the use of IT and ICT in tourism can provide valuable information that can help customers to make decisions.

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Neutral	16	16.0	16.0	16.0
Agree	47	47.0	47.0	63.0
Strongly Agree	37	37.0	37.0	100.0

Total	100	100.0	100.0
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Figure 4.31. Technology impacts customers' decision making process

The tourism industry has adopted the latest frameworks and technologies which help in tourism industry to share information with customers. These communication channels have become easier and quicker because of usage of technology and the internet. Now it does not require lots of time to contact a business in the tourism industry and require information regarding their products and services through social media, email or even sometimes customers use the feedback as fastest information for their requirements. According to the results of the questionnaire it was shown that 47% of participants agreed and 37 % of participants strongly agreed that information which is provided the using technology and the internet influences decision making processes.

Statement 6- I think using the website to sell services is clear, understandable, and fair.

SWLS6

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Disagree	1	1.0	1.0	1.0
Neutral	22	22.0	22.0	23.0
Agree	47	47.0	47.0	70.0

Strongly Agree	30	30.0	30.0	100.0
Agree				
Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Figure 4.32. Selling touristic products through websites

Online selling has become common and fast in the market. Selling through online frameworks has become easy and profitable. Tourism industry is one of those industries which is mostly focused on online selling, from where products and services are promoted online and then sold to customers. According to the results from the questionnaires it is shown that according to participants 47% agree and 30% of them strongly agree with the fact that selling through internet is a clear and fast procedure which helps both businesses and customers to save time. 22% of participants shared a neutral opinion which means they find it find and efficient. Only one participant disagreed with the statement and this was followed by an oral explanation at the time of participating that the answer was related to personal experience in processing an online sale.

Statement 7- **I think the use of IT and ICT allows access to collect and distribute information more easily.**

SWLS7

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Neutral	8	8.0	8.0	8.0
	Agree	63	63.0	63.0	71.0
	Strongly Agree	29	29.0	29.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Figure 4.33. Technology usage as communication channel

The tourism industry has been shaped positively by the introduction and adaptation of technology and ICT. There are different ways and techniques that tourist organisation can use to reach customers and distribute and share the information with them. Online techniques such as social media, email, websites, and group chats allows these businesses not only to share information, promote their products/services but they can do it to lots of customers at the same time. Advances in technology has created communication channels between both organisations/businesses and tourists which are endless, quicker, and more effective which saves time. According to results from the questionnaire it was shown that 29% of respondents strongly agreed and 63% of them agreed that technology and ICT allows organisations and customers to access, collect and share the information between them. On the other hand, only 8% of respondents shared a neutral opinion regarding the statement.

Statement 8- **I think the internet is a way to increase numbers of tourists.**

SWLS8

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Disagree	3	3.0	3.0	3.0
	Neutral	11	11.0	11.0	14.0
	Agree	49	49.0	49.0	63.0
	Strongly Agree	37	37.0	37.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Figure 4.34 Internet as a tool for development

Tourists are the main instrument in tourism industry globally. Nowadays, due to market competition, it has become difficult for organisations operating in tourism industries to keep their customers loyal for long periods of time. This indicates that these organisations should use every tool, software, and framework to maintain these loyal customers and at the same time should reach new markets and target new customers as technology has advanced a lot in recent years and as most of the procedures and businesses are performing online, the internet is seen as one of the main frameworks where tourist organisations can reach customers through online databases, electronic mail, and social media.

According to participants, 49% of them agreed and 37 % strongly agreed that the internet can increase the number of customers as well as the organisational performance. 11% of participants shared a neutral opinion which somehow indicates that the internet helps

clientele, but this is not necessarily a main indicator for improvement. 3% of participants did not agree with the statement as according to their experience, the internet in some cases just makes customers realise that this procedure is not always right or fair.

Statement 9- I think promotional activities through internet are effective in targeting new markets.

SWLS9

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Neutral	6	6.0	6.0	6.0
	Agree	55	55.0	55.0	61.0
	Strongly Agree	39	39.0	39.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Figure 4.35 Effectiveness of online promotion

Promotional activities take most of the attention of tourism agencies. Promotion through the internet has become important as it targets more than one customer at the same time. This is followed by the fact that using promotion through online frameworks target new markets and sometimes this market finds these companies and businesses. According to information collected by the questionnaire, 55% of participants agreed and 39% strongly agreed with the statement that promotional activities through internet are effective in targeting new market as well as communicating easily with them.

Statement 10- I think Information Communication Technology allows organisation to use customer feedback for further development.

SWLS10

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Neutral	3	3.0	3.0	3.0
	Agree	58	58.0	58.0	61.0
	Strongly Agree	39	39.0	39.0	100.0
	Agree				
	Total	100	100.0	100.0	

Figure 4.36- Use of Feedback for further development

Considering the positive sides of technology and internet usage, is important to mention that in the tourism industry, businesses usually benefit from feedback of their customers to improve their performance and their products/services. On the other hand, this feedback can be used by the agencies or businesses to attract other tourists to choose their business and their services/products. According to information collected it was stated that 58% of participants agreed and 39%of participants strongly agreed that businesses use feedback from customers for further development and improvement.

To conclude discussion related to the questionnaires, it is important to mention that technology and the internet have been indicators of a positive progress of the tourism industry as well as for the development of the tourist organisations. Tourist agencies and customers have lots of facilities by using alternative frameworks such as online search, information and products/services which saves them time and allows organisations to focus more on their work and improve performance. Customer feedback is a facility which tourist organisations

use as a technique to improve their offers, products and services and learn what tourists are looking for.

4.5 Chapter Summary

Primary data and information collected by the author has been reported to support this research. This concerned the use of questionnaires, which are reported in the appendices and face-to-face interviews. This confirmed the findings which were detailed in tabular and graphical forms, as well as reporting details of pertinent secondary data from the literature search. These findings and their implications are discussed in later chapters, along with appropriate recommendations and suggestions for further research.

The chapter incorporated an outline of the methodology that was used to collect data along with an elaboration of participants that were involved in the questioning process. Analysis of data presented a summary of information through appropriate statistics, graphs, and tables through various means including descriptive and exploratory analyses.

CHAPTER 5 –DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

5.1 Introduction

This chapter consists of evaluating data collected by the researcher to support this research. As mentioned in the previous chapter data was collected through interviews and two different questionnaires, as well as secondary data which was used in the literature review section.

This chapter is split into different themes: evaluation of the current scenario in the Albanian Tourism industry; identifying the level of technology usage in the tourism industry; identifying factors that render effective technology usage in the tourism industry; extraction of data from results of the interviews and questionnaires; analysis and evaluated based on findings; relevance related to the literature review; how effective the research is in terms of enriching the field of knowledge in the tourism and technology field.

Considering all themes, it is important to mention that themes are related to each other and all consist of the main research question on finding how effective technology is in the tourism industry and its component parts in promotion and development of the business in the tourism sector by promoting its products.

The researcher decided to evaluate the current scenario and issues in the tourism industry of Albania. The researcher has chosen this topic to evaluate improvements and development of tourism in the country. Similarly, there not much evidence in the literature related to tour operators comparing to hotels regarding service quality and customer satisfaction. Tourism industry is the sector which has a great impact and contribution to the country's GDP.

The primary focus of the tourism industry in Albania theme was to evaluate advantages technology has brought for the tourism industry worldwide. The adaptation of technology in the tourism sector of a small country like Albania, has facilitated and improved the development of the tourism sector which leads in further improvements in the overall development of the country.

The second theme is the Internet. The researcher decided this theme as one of the most important themes extracted from the research and has evaluated contributions of the internet in the tourism industry for both tourist organisations and customers.

The third theme chosen to be elaborated and evaluated is social media. The focus of this theme is to evaluate the importance that social media has received in the tourism industry from both sides, customers as well as tourist organisations and agencies.

The final theme, that the researcher has decided to include was marketing and promotion. Both are important when doing business, but it attracts more attention in the tourism industry in terms of development through strategic planning of promotion and enhancement of awareness regarding customer needs and wants.

5.2 Evaluation of the Current Albanian Tourism Industry.

5.2.1 Summary of findings

Tourism in Albania is one of the sectors that is continuously improving, and its GDP contribution has been increasing during recent years. Government in Albania is giving attention to tourism due to its contribution to GDP. The global pandemic has impacted overall development of the tourism industry not only in Albania but worldwide. Globally, the tourism industry is an industry that has suffered more due to covid -19 because of travel restrictions.

Before the pandemic, the Albanian tourism industry was slowly developing. However, many issues that are not related to the pandemic were evident. According to the research and secondary data, the use of technology in the tourism industry is evident but its use is basic compared to neighbouring countries. Albanian tour agencies do have a presence in the social media where they can share and introduce products and services. Marketing and promotion through social media cover most online activities through communication. Albanian enterprises have a good level of internet access, but the level of technology usage is low and basic. Similarly, enterprises that operate in tourism industry should seriously consider their webpage designs, as these are the primary contact that customers have regarding destinations, which is where customers are introduced to services and products. It is important to mention that most businesses confuse webpages with their social media accounts. Even though businesses in Albanian use them to promote, sell or use for reservation purposes, it is important that webpages should be updated frequently and be used as a key indicator that pushes purchases.

A further issue in the Albanian tourism industry is customer service. Albania is currently receiving great attention from the international market in terms of investments through Ports Europe (2020).

Even though, lack of customer service is a well-known issue, it affects the image of Albania as a tourist destination. Considering the potential of Albania, customer service is low, and this might be related to issues such as employee educational background, seasonality, and communication skills. There have been cases when tourists have not received the service or product they paid for and this impacts on their experience which is determinantal. Customer service is related to customer satisfaction and loyalty. Hence, tour operators should have a close collaboration with accommodation units in order to provide the best service.

5.2.2 Discussion and Evaluation of Findings

Before starting the analysis of the findings, it is important to mention that Tourism is regarded as a main indicator of profit by people who operate in this sector. Secondly, the tourism industry/sector in Albania is still a sector which is developing quickly and becoming one of the main supporters for local communities and overall income. Contemplating findings from this research, it is shown that tourism in Albania is receiving attention for development and investment from both private and public sectors. The private sector and individuals that operate in tourism are investing in the infrastructure and environment as well as improving and introducing new products or services that might attract customer attention. Bringing new innovations, ideas, and services is important because it will increase customer numbers and customers spread news to the word regarding a new service.

The private sector in Albania depends on the online network such as internet and social media. These are important and crucial for a business operating in tourism in Albania. To have a web page or an account in the social media to connect with customers by introducing offers, products and services is essential. This has become the easiest way of communication because it is rapid and low in costs. There is increased awareness from both sides, from suppliers and customers regarding what is offered and what is required, and competition is one of the main concerns in the tourism industry.

Governmental organisations are working together with UNWTO to create ways to help the tourism industry improve and develop. According to UNWTO (2014) The main point of the government is to create sustainable seasonal tourism in Albania which is gifted by nature with 4 different seasons and the destination offers different products and services based on seasonality. The aim of this collaboration is to integrate the development of sustainable tourism in the country as the way of empowering each area as well as addressing

the issue of seasonality. Organisations are willing to work towards transforming the tourism sector in Albania into a strong economic power that brings growth and integration to the national economy. The Government of Albania is further strengthening its commitment to the sector and giving important recognition to tourism's contribution to Albania's socio-economic development, According to Rifai (UNWTO,2014) it is stated that "Albania is truly blessed with spectacular natural and cultural heritage. The backbone of its tourism sector has shown impressive growth over recent years." This indicates that even though the industry is improved, it means there is still opportunity for improvement and enhancing the tourism sector in Albania.

Another point that government organisations are investing towards tourism industry is by creating means and facilities that would help the sector. This includes opening professional schools and trainings for people who operate in the tourism sector. Furthermore, governmental initiatives for improving the tourism industry include participation in different fairs worldwide and the Albanian tourism organisation participated in the World Tourism Fair in London in November 2019.

According to the official webpage of the Albanian Ministry of Tourism and Environment (2018), there is projected a strategy to develop of tourism for the period up to 2023. Its purpose is to focus on development of destinations, areas, products, and diversification of tourist offers as well as increasing added value of tourism potentials for economic and social development of the country. The aim of the strategy is that Albania should be widely promoted in the international community as a destination worthy of equal competition in the global tourism market. Consequently, the positioning of Albania in this market will be based on two pillars of development:

- Long-term sustainability of public interventions and investments to turn the country's tourist economy as an attraction for being a better place of living as well as at a more profitable potential for tourism ventures.
- Conservation and regular development of geographical space with respect to nature, ecosystems, demographic, and urban development in all areas with potential tourism development.

This strategy intends to give more opportunity to tourism in Albania and increase benefits to the local community. This would create more opportunity for industry overall in order to create a guaranteed level of services, including accommodation to hosting and serving by giving opportunities to organisations to participate in various training programmes.

Individuals with experience in doing business abroad (not necessarily in tourism) are investing in Albanian tourism, especially in attractive areas by building facilities and accommodation units.

5.3- Technology Usage in Tourism Industry

5.3.1. Summary of findings

Based on research conducted and findings it is shown that technology has great impact in tourism sector by creating facilities and ease of work. By considering information received from interview forms which are detailed in the Appendix, it is important to mention that the Albanian tourism industry is on a right path to compete with neighbouring countries. Technology and ICT affect development of tourism industry as well as other branches to which tourism is related.

By taking into consideration information collected, the Albanian tourism industry usually uses technology as a tool for promotion and communication with potential tourists. Focusing on different groups of tourists at the same time, the internet has become one of the main frameworks where most tour agencies and operators rely on regarding their development. Online websites and different apps of social media have created an easy and cheaper way for businesses operating in tourism to promote and sell products to potential customers as well as communicating with them in a quicker way by sharing the most important information. Based on findings, participants confirmed that the tourism industry has been shaped by use of technology and ICT. The Albanian tourism industry has shown that technology has become one of the main tools in promotion and overall performance of businesses in the tourism industry. Moreover, considering all 12 interviews, participants confirmed that the level of technology usage in the Albanian Tourism is between 60%-80% for adaptation and usage of technology. This includes overall performance that these organisations perform during a typical working day.

Even after collecting information of both questionnaires, it was found that technology plays a dual role in the tourism industry. This is because technology is not only important for businesses operating in tourism as a promotional tool, but it is important for tourists as well due to its speed in providing information, communication and so on. According to the questionnaire that was administered to tourism agencies in Albania it was confirmed that 55% of participants found technology important in their everyday routine as well as

considering it as a tool for further development and faster service. 44 % of participants were in doubt, as although technology is important, they confirmed that advances in technology have made the industry perform faster and better. Only 1% of participants thought that technology is not important for as long as agencies know how to keep loyal customers happy.

According to the questionnaire, regarding the statement that technology has positively impacted tourism industry since its introduction was agreed by 69% of participants and 26% of them strongly agreed by stating that technology has built up the tourism sector all over the world. Only 5% of participants stated that their opinions were neutral which means they consider technology as a helpful tool in tourism industry but not essential for its development.

Based on the second questionnaire it was again found that for years, the tourism industry and other sector showed that technology has greatly improving by introducing techniques, methods and new tools which facilitate amounts of work as well as work performance. Technology has become essential in the tourism industry because through it business and agencies can easily communicate with costumers by facilitating communication channels and services that they provide.

5.3.2. Discussion and Evaluation of Findings

As mentioned previously, technology is an important factor in doing business. This is a factor which did not feature strongly in the tourism industry, but it has shown its effectiveness even alongside other industries and sectors such as telecommunication. The focus of this research is the tourism industry, and the researcher has evaluated the effectiveness of technology in this sector. Technology has had a great influence in all the sectors as well as tourism and travel sectors all around the world. Due to its development and improvement, technology has found wide and huge adaptation from the world due to its facilities and benefits provided to tourism industries. Technology has found the need to be developed and adapted because of customer needs, and these must be developed and updated which leads the technology to be even more developed.

Another point is that technology has positively helped tourism is by using technological labour rather than human labour which reduces the costs and at the same time avoids other problems that can be caused by serving customers. Furthermore, technology has shaped and influenced the way customers travel and arrange travelling. According to an article in the world Travel and Tourism Council (2018), it is stated that technological advancements are used nowadays by tourist organisations to promote destinations, products

and services. This helps to ensure that information is more accurate and detailed regarding certain products and destinations. Vidal (2018) shows that technology has changed the way that travelling and other services are enabled. Most customers tend to arrange their travel and accommodation themselves rather than using the services that travel agencies provide. This comes at a point where it is important to mention again that technology impact on tourism industry has become a time saver for customers.

On the other hand, these findings support the body of knowledge as many authors have conducted research and realise how important technology has been and is for the tourism industry, not only in Albania but worldwide. Research regarding technology and its impact in the tourism industry started early and with technology development this research has been continuously updated.

According to various authors and researchers, the term technology finds various definitions considering the sector where it is applied. Zeheer (2011) stated that definitions about technology vary accordingly to the sector where it is used and the reason why it is used. He agrees that the perception of individuals and businesses regarding technology and its usage is currently changing and shifting from its traditional perception such as new computers and mobile phones, television, games, play stations, digital devices and so on to a deeper and convenient perception of technology as a source for information enhancing knowledge. This is supported by Ramey (2013) who considers technology as a wide field full of knowledge which takes account of producing and developing new tools, systems, software and applications towards any issue or problem to improve or solve it.

Vaidya (2018) states that the impact of technology upon tourism is obvious and customers rely on it a lot. This is due to increased numbers of people using the latest technologies and because it has become a trend that everything is shifting from computers to other mobile applications, and this demonstrates the impact that technology has provided. Based on article by Entre (2018), it is stated that technology has helped tourism sectors in different aspects such as reducing costs, improving efficiency of operational services as well as improving customer service and experience.

Similarly, in the tourism sector the use of ICT is sometimes considered as an advantage that needs to be adapted as a strategic tool for further improvements and promotional activity indicators. According to Buhalis (2003) such advantages come from the level of contribution that ICT brings, and such determinants consist of transforming operational practices by providing more opportunities for tourist agencies and tour operators to improve and expand their businesses. The use of ICT indicates that by providing strategic tools in industry

networks add more value to products that are presented to tourists as well as improving interactions between organisations. It is a competitive advantage to use ICT in tourism mostly in countries such as Albania where the tourism sector is still in the development process and it protects destinations as they all compete in a market where it is essential to have competitive advantage and ICT combined with traditional ways of advertising, means destinations achieve this advantage. Furthermore, it reduces costs, which means that use of ICT has an impact on the reduction of costs to help the tourism industry to take advantage through competition as it offers opportunities for further development of the destination by reducing costs and increasing profits and numbers of tourists that come and spend time in the destination. This makes it possible that the sector of tourism creates advantages by being unique in different ways of promotion, presenting better value and unique products and activities that reduce costs and increase profits.

5.3.3 - Internet usage for further development

In recent years, the letter "E" has taken on great importance in world information and communication technologies (ICTs), virtual businesses, research on the internet and in the tourism sector. It has become an important component for research fields including electronic marketing, e-business, e-finance, e-commerce, e-learning and distance, electronic markets. The revolution in information technology and communication (ICT) has changed not only our lives, but also the way people do business. In recent years there has been an increase in the number of tour operators who use the internet and other electronic media to carry out their marketing efforts, thereby prioritizing electronic marketing as a philosophy.

There is no doubt that the internet today represents one of the major challenges for the tourism sector, and world wide web content is an important element for millions of users. This is demonstrated in the Albanian tourism industry which has been impacted by the internet as much as technology and together have improved overall operations. The internet has brought new space for businesses regarding the way they operate and contact customers and introduce products or services.

5.3.3.1 Findings

Based on research findings it is important to mention that most tour agencies and organisations have access to the internet as well as creating a web page for their business. According to findings it has become a trend that most business nowadays have created

websites to be present in the commerce market. This phenomenon has spread quickly to the Albanian tourism industry.

According to questionnaire results it was shown that 91 of participants confirmed their business has a website which is mostly used to enhance the performance of the business. Another reason for using a website, it is sharing information about services and products that organisations offers and in collecting information from customers and their requirements. Only 4 participants confirmed that their business do not own any website, as they do not see any difference in performance or business development. Furthermore, based on results of the questionnaire that took place in different tourism agencies in Albania it was shown that most agencies that have a website use it to promote and contact their customers and this is mainly managed by people from inside the organisation, respectively 87 participants manage their website using their staff. Social media accounts for such businesses now have increased activity communicating with customers worldwide. This is a good way to deal with customers to keep in continuous contact and see to their everyday needs. Only 8 participants confirmed that their websites are managed by individuals that are not in the organisation, which means they are only responsible for management of the website. According to them, this method is better because everyone in the organisation has their own duties to perform and there is no confusion doing more than one duty at the same time. Research has shown that the internet allows better communication with costumers. According to results this statement was agreed and strongly agreed by 79 participants (52-27). These participants found it easier to communicate with customers than, before as it is a quicker procedure which saves time as well as cutting costs.

There are increased numbers of customers who visit websites for travel purposes, but some showed a neutral opinion (39 participants). This is because they think that travelling reasons are not the only requirement for tourists to visit websites, but they use it for general information such as cultural and historical purposes. On the other side 43 participant agreed and 12 strongly agreed that the phenomena of customers visiting websites for travel purposes has become their main duty and this influences them when making decisions. The internet is a way to increase business profit and staff performance. Nowadays, the internet has become a necessity for every type of business as most work is based on the internet. Due to most programs and training being based online, the internet is seen as a framework to increase performance of employers. According to questionnaire results, 44 participants agreed, and 9 strongly agreed that internet is seen as a tool for improvement and increasing staff performance. On the other hand, 36 participants out of 95 were neutral and 5 disagreed with

this statement which means that they see the internet as a help for improvement but not up to the stage that the internet can improve the performance of employers. According to them it is needed for training and experience exchange to improve performance and overall customer service.

The internet has less marketing and promotional costs compared to traditional methods (direct contacts with sale agents, leaflets, brochures). Since the adoption of the internet and IT and ICT by tourism agencies and organisation it has become easier to for these businesses to perform their marketing and promotional activities with a low budget and cut costs. 61 participants agreed that this technique allows them to reach more customers at the same time as their market is expanding globally. However, there were a few participants that totally disagreed with this statement as they state the methods of face-to-face marketing is lost and less contact is happening between them and customers as everything is based on the online performance.

Considering the findings that the researcher has found it is important to mention that the researcher agrees with the review of previous materials and articles related to the internet usage in the tourism Industry. The Internet represents a technological innovation whose effects range from communication to in interaction. However, its potentials have not yet been fully explored and studied.

According to Visser (2004), considering the variety of studies that have been conducted on the topic of importance of using internet in the tourism sector and elsewhere, is clearly understood that internet since it has been introduced to people have been impacting hugely in the everyday life of individuals as well as improving businesses and also developing new ones.

According to Standing et al (2014) has stated that internet has a two side impact, on both customers and supply side. As mentioned above, Internet does facilitate the procedures and makes it easier for both customers and supply to get what they require. In the supply side internet gives the opportunity to share information about the products and services, what they provide. Also, it allows the suppliers to get feedback from their potential customers after they reach them through the internet. On the other side, potential customers get informed on what is available in the market, getting informed about is needed to be accessed in case of destination. By becoming informed they get to know the potential risks and securities of the place by getting in touch with other customers that might have visited previously.

Cristiana (2008) states that the tourism sector has been one of the first sectors to go online and use the internet for its services and goes further by mentioning functions that the

internet has brought into the travel industry, such as online booking, ticket reservations, accommodation and so on what is most important to mention is the fact that communication is the crucial facility that is brought into the Tourism Sector by the internet and its online software and applications.

According to the findings, internet usage consists in some points that specify the importance of internet usage and its effectiveness. The internet allows companies to have enhanced communication with the costumers. According to findings, this statement has been agreed and strongly agreed by 79 participants (52-27). These participants find it easier to communicate with their customers easier than before and it is a quicker procedure which saves time as well as cuts costs.

The internet allows organisations to have less marketing and promotional costs compared to the traditional methods (direct contacts with sale agents, leaflets, brochures). Since the adaptation of Internet and IT and ICT on the tourism agencies and organisation has become easier too for these businesses to perform their marketing and promotional activities within a low budget and cutting costs. 61 participants agreed that this technique allows them to reach more customers at the same time as well as their market is expanded globally. However, there were a few participants that totally disagreed with this statement as they state the methods of face-to-face marketing is lost and less contact is happening between them and customer as everything is based on the online performance.

5.3.4 Social media

Social media is considered as one of the main tools which is well used worldwide for different purposes. Social media is becoming an important strategic tool for businesses which use it to promote and to contact potential customers. Usually, state organisations have their websites and social media that they update. On the other hand, private organisation such as tour agencies or tourism offices use their social media accounts to contact potential customers by using different offers, presenting their services and products as well as creating a communication bridge where this information is shared.

Based on findings in both interviews and questionnaires it is shown that social media finds a huge field of usage in the Albanian tourism industry. This helps organisations to contact customers and to sell their products or services. Considering interviews, it is important to mention that participants have confirmed that more than 90% of tourist

businesses use social media as a main tool for promotion. This is because it saves time while performing the work as well as targeting lots of groups of customers at the same time.

Albania is characterised as a small European country and its population is around 3 million people, so tour agencies and organisations try to focus not only on the national market but target international tourists and customers. Considering the results of 95 agencies that participated in the questionnaire it is shown that agencies focus mostly in adapting online sales by 37.9% as a technique for promotion. What is most important is that agencies are tending to adopt social media techniques by 52.6%. In most cases these techniques are combined with other techniques and used together to reach different groups of customers.

5.3.4.1 Evaluation of findings.

In the case of Albania, social media has found great usage in most sectors. Tourism sector private and state administrated organizations use social media for promotion and improvement of their businesses. Through social media, tourist destinations promote their name, products, services and target potential customers, and most of them have an account on social media. As a destination, Albania has been promoted through social media by different platforms. Some examples are Albanian tourism, welcome to Albania, visit Albania, Albanian beauty. Furthermore, there are clues and pages that are specific to different types of products such as skiing or studying or adventurous products.

These finding are in accordance with materials the researcher came across while studying this topic. Different authors and individuals bring various emphasis of social media definition but is difficult to define it exactly. Safko and Brake (2009) defined this as a group of individuals who interact, participate, and discuss on the online world by liking, tweeting, posting, and sharing various information about different topics. As interaction and number of cases are large, social media has great impact on businesses. However, it is important to mention that in most cases the impact of social media differs from one sector to another. In the case of tourism sector, social media is playing a key role in the development of organizations and destinations. According to Koplou and Haenlein, (2010) social media is described as the use of digital means for different reasons. The main purpose of social media is communication, but nowadays it is widely used as an advertising and promotional tool of tourism destinations, organisations, and sites where individuals sell goods, tourism products and services. Heinonen, (2011) states that being active in the online network has become a trend and an obsession for most individuals which most of the time interact with different

activities, exchange information and materials, as well as participating in different discussions and sharing opinions regarding different topics. According to Hysi *et al* (2015), social media influences the way the tourism sector, organizations and destinations improve sales. Social media are turning into important marketing tools for the management of tourist destinations and have a great impact on tourism markets. Organizations from all over the world can exchange valuable information, videos, images, consumer reviews, forums. and discussions. (UNWTO,2013).

According to Sterne (2010), there are six different social media tools: forums and message boards, review sites (Yelp), social networks (Facebook), Blogs, micro-blogs (Twitter), bookmarking (Digg, Reddit) and media sharing (YouTube). Almost all these sites enable users to interact with each other. This comes in different forms such as asking questions or expressing opinion or giving feedback on products for instance (Sterne 2010.). Concurring with Picincu (2018), it is clearly stated that social media plays an important role in the tourism industry by facilitating work in this industry. Nowadays, it has become easier to arrange travelling from one place to another by considering social media and receiving information through social media regarding tourist destinations, products, or services.

Continuously, this performance in online networks, especially social media has increased and improved marketing activities of destinations. Marketing and promotion through social media have become a trend nowadays as it is easier for organizations and destinations to reach customers through online platforms. This has become popular, affecting the tourism sector and there are advantages and disadvantages of using social media for promotion of tourism products, services, or destinations. According to Zimmerman and Sahlin (2011), advantages of using social media as a promotion would consist of reducing cost on advertising, targeting big numbers of social media users, increasing the business ways to expand, improve and increase brand image and so on, whereas disadvantages consist of insufficient trained staff needed to maintain social platforms. Not every individual or potential customer is a user of social media which leads for a need for further advertising and requires continuous time and commitment to maintain and update the information provided.

5.3.5 Implication for stakeholders

The interconnected nature of the web has become part of the market space and offers opportunities large communication resulting from size and rapid technological development.

However, organizations now have a balanced view of opportunities and limitations that the internet offers. According to Sterne (2010), the company's online presence is for two reasons:

First, the perceived need to be in touch with consumers in terms of image design and analysis of strategic movements of competitors. Second, the internet is a vital tool for the organization's marketing activities. On the other hand, tour operators play an important role in and the world economy and are one of the major contributors to growth and economic development. Tour operators can be classified as small business.

5.4 Online marketing and promotion

Marketing and promotional activity are important in doing business in the tourism industry or any other field. Both terms, sound common but they have certain meanings and roles of their own.

5.4.1 Findings

Considering findings from the research it is shown that tourism industry in Albania it is connected closely with online promotion and online marketing especially through social media.

Online marketing has become a crucial tool in business development due to impact of the online world has upon people. This allows businesses to reach bigger groups of people easier and cheaper than before. In most cases marketing goes along with promotion and for most businesses this function is an activity that uses marketing and promotion at the same time. It has become a trend nowadays that organisations perform their promotional activities by choosing cheaper and easier techniques that can be effective for their business.

Promotional activity is important for organisations as this is the way they increase their performance. As Albania is characterised as a small European country and its population is around 3 million people, tour agencies and organisations try to focus not only on the national market but as well targeting international tourists and customers. Considering the results from 95 agencies that participated in the questionnaire it was shown that agencies focus mostly in adapting online sales by 37.9% as a technique for promotion. What is most important is that agencies tend to adopt social media techniques by 52.6%. TV/Radio and newspaper and magazines are used by agencies by 3.2% and 6.3% which in most cases are combined with other techniques and used together to reach different groups of customers.

Moreover, online promotion does not include social media, but also includes website that businesses use to improve their companies and increase profits. This is the case for Albanian tourist organisations. These organisations have created a website parallel with

social media activity to promote their products and services. According to findings most business nowadays have created websites to be present not only in the commerce market but support it by online activity. This phenomenon has spread quickly throughout the Albanian tourism industry. According to the questionnaire results it was shown that 91 of participants confirmed their business has a website which is mostly used to enhance the performance of the business. Another reason for using websites, is to share information about services and products that organisation offer and collect information from customers and their requirements. Only 4 participants confirmed that their business does not own any website as they do not see any difference in performance or business development.

Considering that the researcher used two different questionnaires to find the information it is important to mention that promotional activity has influenced customer decision making processes for a long time and this should continue. Promotion influences and perceptions help customers to take decisions. Based in these research findings it is important to mention that according to collected data it was stated that 88% of participants agreed that they have been influenced by promotional activities when they made decisions. Only 12% of participants stated that they have never been influenced by promotional activities regarding travelling and decision-making processes.

In terms of promotion types which have influenced tourist decision making processes and their behaviour towards touristic destinations, in 7 cases answers were considered lost or missing because when participants stated they have not been influenced by promotional activity, they preferred not to answer questions about any type of promotion which might influence their behaviour. In terms of promotional activity influence, 38% of participants considered promotion by their friends and relatives as more reliable and trustful promotion. Promotion through Social media influences 30% of participants. This comes as a combination of ease of access of information as well as the feedback which is given by other tourists regarding a certain destination or product/service. Travel agency promotion was chosen by 19% of participants as a type of promotion which they could rely on and influence their travel behaviour and shape their decisions. However, there were 6% of participants that chose the option. but none stated any example of the type of promotion they considered when they take decisions.

5.4.2 Evaluation of the findings .

According to many authors, marketing can be defined in various ways such as an activity that businesses can increase the awareness of the needs and wants of customers to provide a

service or product at the right time and place (Kotler and Armstrong 2010, 2018). Similarly, marketing is also defined as a function that helps the business to create a relationship with the customer and fulfil the goals that business has set.

On the other hand, promotion is seen as the process of reaching and contacting costumers in different ways. Tourism industry is influenced more and more from online promotion especially through social media. As mentioned in the social media section, organisations and companies now tend to promote and create a communication channel through social media. Considering that numbers of social media users keep increasing, it makes sense to invest more in online promotion. From there it is know that the targeted market is bigger, and profits are better. It is important to mention that promotion in the tourism sector is considered difficult due to what is requested to promote. In product fields, product that can be seen and touched, whereas in tourism what it is promoted is either a destination or a service.

Marketing and promotion have always been important instruments in doing business, not only in tourism industry. According to Lui (2000) it is important to mention that promotion is part of the marketing mix and as such is used for promotion through online means and this has its own advantages for both customers and businesses. This includes different aspects such as ethics and legal issues being taken more into consideration and information that is given is more accurate and more details are included as there is no limitation on the amount of information provided. Since the tourism industry introduced online marketing, everything became easier and cheaper. Business target larger groups of customers at once and this has made their job easier and profits higher. Based on different articles about promotion in the tourism industry, Mill and Morrison (2009) state that promotion in the tourism industry plays the role of the attractor for customers, it shapes and affects their behaviour towards decision making process and state that there are three types of promotion: informative, persuasive and reminder promotion which in the tourism industry helps and influences customers when buying different tourist products or services.

According to Andrew (2010), promotion through the internet and online sites have benefits such as: cost effectiveness which means that organisations can avoid of paying high bills for traditional marketing campaigns and storage costs. Because these costs are avoided, companies can give more attention to create better portals where potential customers feel more comfortable. Another advantage is exploration of the market. Organisations that promote through the internet can explore and expand their market because customers can be targeted all at the same time from every part if the world and products can also be sold in the

same way. Continuous communication and lower costs create profits and benefits for organisations, to communicate explain and recommend to customers. Through email, social media and so on it is easier and cheaper to keep customers updated and with whatever is needed.

Another advantage of promoting online is that organisations and tour agencies can have a clearer idea for their sites and customers which helps them to understand how well they are performing and what they need.

Furthermore Linton (2017) suggests a few benefits, similar to those proposed by Andrew but in other aspects such as convenience where organisations using online marketing and promotion do not worry about time limitations, in terms of opening and closing shops and storage by allowing the process to be 24/7 without concern about customer location. Personalisation or creating more opportunities for members or loyal customer by bringing special offers and clearance makes online promotion benefits, and more attention can be paid to worldwide customers. Whilst benefiting from this positive aspect of internet/online promotion it is important for business and customers to consider potential negative aspects which might be due to neglecting third parties. Such kinds of negative characteristics are typified by the fact that attraction of customers is a process which is as easy and difficult at the same time. Reaching the market is a different issue, as through an application or website you can reach many individuals and customers but to make these customers check your website and buy from it is a difficult process, because there are millions of websites that might sell similar products and services.

Difficulty in transactions online might be a problem as sometimes customers are not totally sincere and there is no face-to-face communication, which might create a loss of business. A further issue that is seen as a disadvantage of promoting through online sources and the internet is time and effort involved because of a need to keep the website continuously updated. Such effort involves the need to learn about technology, techniques and methods of online marketing and promotion to bring about a successful website.

Considering both positive and negative aspects of online promotion it is important to mention that businesses need to avoid the disadvantages and improve profits by targeting and producing new customers while keeping loyal ones.

5.4.3 Development models of improving website design for advertising and promotion.

Considering the research of Noti (2014) it was stated that there are two models related to online promotion/advertising: AIDA Model and model 2QCV3QV Meta Model. Both models have been used to help advertising in the tourism industry and have been used to advertise/promote through online means. The researcher here has combined both these models to present a more facilitated model to design websites with the main purpose to advertise and promote tourist products. The model includes five main components and different to previous research it takes into consideration the customer satisfaction component which is important to create and maintain loyal customers. For instance, the tourist organisation needs to take into consideration several steps to reach customers and make them purchase their products. Except simply providing presentable and attractive advertisements, the website needs to be practical and frequently updated.

Figure 5.2 Development of the Website model ACIAS

Source: The author.

5.4.4- Implication to stakeholders

This section relates to the implication of themes mentioned to and by stakeholders. Considering research findings from both questionnaires and interviews it is important to mention that both private and state organisations that operate in the tourism industry in Albania are impacted by use of appropriate technology. Governmental organisations such as ATA (Albanian Tourism Agency) and respective ministry are the main organisations responsible for promoting the Albanian tourism industry nationally and internationally.

Similarly, there is the private sector which might be a tour agency or an accommodation unit. Both parties of stakeholders benefit by the adaptation and use of technology, use of the internet and social media. Benefits include ease of usage and facilitated communication with potential customers, more efficient and quicker everyday tasks. This applies to both sectors, in consideration of their budgets, size of the organisation and groups of customers they provide services/products for.

Considering research findings, it is important to mention another point that connects both sectors and this is promotional activity which has lately shifted to an online basis. This comes through the internet, social media, and official websites. The only difference between the private and state sectors is that state organisation and ministry is more focused in promoting the destination, and the image of our country by providing statistics and information regarding the tourism industry in Albania. On the other hand, private organisations tend to promote more online, but this relates more to their products and services. Furthermore, private organisations focus on targeting markets and customers who intend and are willing to buy services/products and not simply to become informed.

5.5. Technology in the Tourism Industry

5.5.1 Summary of findings

The literature review and primary research have identified the effects of technology in the tourism industry in Albania. Adaptation of technology has been identified as a great improvement with the introduction of expedients to services that can be provided due to technological improvements. The positive effect of technology consists of the way businesses operate during everyday work, including communication, marketing, promotion, and selling products and services.

Considering data from the primary research questionnaire, it was found out that 69% of participants agree that technology has positively impacted tourism in Albania. Similarly, it was found out that 52% of participants agreed and 36% strongly agreed that technology is useful and has facilitated everyday work and operations. Other aspects considered are that technology has made it possible that communication is quicker and clearer between customers and enterprises. Similarly, due to technology advancements it was found easier to receive information regarding products, services, or tourist destinations. It is important in the tourism industry that enterprises need to be responsive and respond to customer requirements quickly, especially when online operations apply. Enterprises that operate online should have a back-up plan to respond to customers speedily by combining their contact details with

social media accounts. This activity is common in Albanian enterprises. Due to the nature of the tourism industry, it was identified that adaptation of technology in the tourism industry has reduced costs of advertising and promotion. At the same time, enterprises use online promotion and advertising to reach a bigger number of potential customers worldwide. Furthermore, adaptation of technology has been identified as a purchase pusher combined with online customer feedback. According to primary data it was shown that 58% of participants agreed that technology has given the opportunity to enterprises to use customer feedback for further development. Similarly, from a customer point of view, they can use this feedback as an indicator for purchase, especially when feedback is positive.

5.5.2. Discussion and evaluation of findings

The following section combines data from primary research and the literature review to better understand the effects of technology in the tourism industry in Albania by using the seven components that have been identified as factors that decide the efficiency of technology usage in the Albanian Tourism industry.

USEFULNESS

Introduction of technology has facilitated the way the tourism industry operates. Considering data from the questionnaire it was found that 52% of participants agreed and 36% strongly agreed that technology has facilitated work the workload of the tourism industry, especially from an organisational or supply side. Adaptation of technology is useful in tourism as businesses can reach more customers at lower costs and it is much quicker as customers are able to research more information regarding their requirements which include destinations and products.

However, it is important to mention that technology does not always have a positive effect on the tourism industry. In some cases, due to the nature of online sources, products and services are not as they are intended to be, and adaptation of technology can indicate the negative aspects off online promotion which leads to customers making wrong decisions.

EASE OF USE

Considering the nature of the tourism industry, it is easy to access and use their products. Use of Google to research product or services, indicates ease of use in the tourism industry. For instance, customers mostly access information about tourist destinations only by typing its name. Technology has made it possible for customers to be able to share information which is easy to use.

According to the questionnaires and participant opinions they regard how easy it is to check certain destination and products. Using technology in the tourism industry has given opportunities to save time and costs in checking destinations/products, requesting information and communicating with providers/sellers.

Businesses use technology in different aspects, such as database, customer information, marketing, advertising, booking and so on. Similarly, it is easier for business to connect with customers in a quicker and costless way.

However, not everyone can easily adapt to these technological advancements. This might require investments from business such as training staff and providing customers with clear instructions.

According to the findings, 52% of participants agreed and 36% strongly agreed that adopting technology has facilitated work and it has created easier methods to check customer information. Customers can use different platforms to check information regarding tourist destinations/products.

RELIABILITY

In the tourism industry, reliability is considered crucial due to the online nature of selling intangible products/services. According to Blery *et al.* (2009) reliability is considered as the ability to provide to the customers with products/services at the same level as when they were introduced. Reliability is considered crucial due to the nature of the tourism industry. Tawinunt *et al.* (2015) Khan and Fasih (2014) and Ibrahim *et al.* (2015) suggest that reliability is closely related to the service quality and consequently it is unequivocally related to customer satisfaction and loyalty.

The Albanian Tourism industry has been indirectly part of events that have negatively impacted Albania as a tourist destination. Similarly, reliability is related to website design,

security, and trust. If customers do not feel secure and do not have a feeling of trust towards a certain website or destination, it is more likely that the purchase will not happen. Enterprises and tourist destinations need to provide reliable information, secured databases and transactions and be responsive to improve performance and increase customer satisfaction.

Figure 5.3 Model of Improving Customer Satisfaction

Source: The author

By taking into consideration three components for improving reliability, security and trust, enterprises should be able to improve their service quality. If THE quality services can be improved, then customers will be satisfied, resulting in loyal customers. There is evidence in the literature review regarding service quality in the tourism industry in Albania, but this is believed to be a general impact on customer satisfaction in the hotel industry, and there is little evidence of the impact of service quality in tour operators in terms of customer satisfaction. Similarly, there is little evidence in the literature related to the impact that employee satisfaction has upon service quality and consequently upon customer satisfaction. However, this aspect has not been investigated in this research, it would be a useful and interesting topic for further research.

RESPONSIVENESS

Responsiveness and response time are similar factors that assist technological usage, when considering the nature of the tourist industry in which customers require information regarding destinations/products that include support that customers obtain from staff and if their requirements or issues have been dealt with. According to Rahman *et al.* (2017) it is stated that responsiveness in using technology is related to customer satisfaction. Businesses

operating in the tourism industry have found the need for continuous communication with customers. Being active in websites, frequent updates of information and efficient response time are important factors to support customers. Considering that services provided in the tourism industry are intangible until lived or experienced, communication and information sharing requires specific attention.

According to the findings, 54% agreed and 31% strongly agreed that use of technology helps organizations to communicate with customers on regular basis and provides a quicker service. However, literature found that many businesses that have a website do not update information regularly which mean that it lacks responsiveness.

ASSURANCE/SECURITY

Tourism industry is characterised by products and services which are intangible for customers until the experience take place. Businesses need to make sure that what they sell is what is really being offered to customers and assurance is linked with other factors such as trust, satisfaction, security. And efficiency. Online marketing has increased awareness about different frauds from the online environment. Businesses that operate in such environments need to ensure that products they offer are of high quality and are truly what are advertised. In some cases, advertisements have shown a product or service which is high in quality and when the customers purchase the reality is quite different.

Security is important when dealing with services because of the intangible nature of products or destinations. When considering the tourism industry, security is related to transactions, payment, and purchases. Customer data or and personal information, according to UNWTO (2018), affirmed that security can be combined from two aspects such as destination security which is related to how secure the destination is for customers and online security which referrals to when customers decide to share their personal information with businesses and how secure is the website when customers decide to purchase products or services. Singh (2013) states that in the online world it is difficult to understand when it comes to security due to multiple hacking or fraud. Businesses need to transmit to their customers the feeling of a secured business which takes care of their customer needs, their purchases and privacy. Considering findings from the questionnaire it can be concluded that the environmental security or destination security is one of the key factors that positively affects the development of a tourist destination.

TRUST

Trust is an important factor that influences the tourism industry based on improvement of the latest technologies. As a key component, trust has been studied by several researchers like Cohen *et al.* (2013) who state that trust is closely related to the security factor. When businesses communicate safety, security, efficiency, and effective customer services, they create a feeling of trust in customers which is important in the tourism industry as it is closely related to customer satisfaction and customer loyalty which is referred as the belief of individuals who supply, or a business that is reliable and able to deal with risks or threats. Similarly, Wang *et al.* (2014) suggest that trust helps customer mitigate vulnerabilities in the online environment and alter their online behaviour. Furthermore, Song *et al.* (2012) refers to trust as being a key determinant in pushing a purchase to happen especially in the tourism industry.

COST EFFECTIVENESS

In the tourism industry, adaptation of certain technologies can be expensive to start up. However, this issue is less than the contribution of technology to the tourism industry. From a business point of view, technology has reduced costs for business in terms of promotion and advertising. Most businesses have shifted promotional activity and advertising towards digital sources. Reaching wider groups of customers in a short time, communicating, and answering customer requirements has saved a lot of money for businesses.

According to research findings, technology has created the opportunity to reach more customers and new markets at lower costs. 54 % agreed that technology has allowed businesses to develop and improve with lower budgets. 17% of participants strongly agreed that development costs less and is more likely to happen. 16% showed a neutral opinion and 6% stated that technology is costly due to frequent updates that are required.

Businesses should be able to continuously update and follow technology advances to create competitive advantage in the market.

EFFECT OF TECHNOLOGY MODEL

This model shown in in Figure 5.3 focuses on the effect of technology in the Albanian tourism industry. When technology is adopted, tour agencies can consider this model to maximise the positive effects of technology in the tourism industry and minimise negative effects.

Figure 5.3 Effect of Technology Model

Source: the author

5.5.3 Impact of factors to be used as strategic tools for Albanian tourism development.

Considering the model in Figure 5.4, the researcher suggests that enterprises in the tourism industry need to consider certain components to improve their overall development. The model can be used by the tour operators as well as the Albanian tourism organisation to improve the image of Albania as a tourist destination. The seven components have been split into different modes to improve the website model, service quality and customer satisfaction to initiate a new model to help improve and enhance the Albanian tourist industry. The model consists of 4 main points that include enhancing service quality mainly by tour operators, enhancing customer satisfaction and website design and the provision of clear and updated information. Improvement of security regarding transaction and customer information also

forms part of this model. Considering aspects of primary and secondary data it is evident that lack of security, poor service quality, inadequate customer satisfaction and unclear webpages that are badly planned and not updated increase the possibility that customers will not purchase as they are unconvinced of the company's products and services. Hence, businesses in the Albanian tourism industry should consider serious investment in the components that are cited in Figure 5.4 to progress and attain competitive advantage.

Figure 5.4 Model for enhancing the Albanian tourism industry.

Source: The author

5.6 Chapter summary

It is important to conclude several viewpoints like the importance and benefits of technology usage, internet activity, and social media, to ascertain their impact on promotional activity in the tourism industry.

To conclude these findings, it is imperative to mention that modern technology has become an important tool in doing business in the tourism industry and elsewhere. This research has been supported by different methods of primary data collection like interviews and two types of questionnaire which were directed and targeted to different people from different backgrounds. The researcher used a mixed research method which means that data and information collected through primary means was both qualitative and quantitative. Qualitative data was mostly received from interviews and quantitative information mostly came from questionnaires and secondary means of research.

Tourism in Albania is characterised by the country's natural beauty and historical-cultural edifices. However new products and services have recently been introduced like medical tourism and culinary tourism. Private and state organisations work toward promotion of a destination image and the country's natural resources. This includes messages aimed at national and international markets. By targeting large groups of customers and markets, it has now become beneficial for the economy and development in a general sense. However, the local economy is directly affected because this is where tourism resources are sold and consumed.

Based on these research findings, the tourism industry in Albania has shifted and still ever-changing from its traditional forms of advertising and promotion into the online world. The adaptation of latest technologies, including devices, software and apps brings more appropriate amenities to this industry. Facilitates or benefits relate to the ease of everyday work, faster tasks, faster spread of information, easier promotional activity, and operational work. However, these benefits come with their costs, such as continuous training for staff and time constraints, as online databases need to be continuously updated. The spread of internet connections through most of buildings has created a straightforward and uncomplicated way of doing business and promotion, both of which are important in both the tourism industry and for business in general.

Social media, including appropriate apps such as Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, Snapchat and so on, are social networks that plays the role of information distributors, communication channels and for promotional activity. Tourist agencies and operators use social media by creating accounts where they introduce, promote, and target wide groups of customers. Extensive numbers of users in social media provides businesses with better opportunities to find potential customers and sell their products or services, as well as extending specific elements of information.

Models have been articulated and recommended that relate to the enhancement of service quality and as a result these should increase customer satisfaction. It was found that both components are crucial in the tourism industry, especially when it is related to intangible products or services. Similarly, it was found that webpages play an important role in introducing products and services to customers and throughout this process the most important information needs to be provided clearly and must be frequently updated. Furthermore, security is another component that influences customer behaviour towards a destination or service. Providing secured transaction, retaining customer information, and transmitting security for certain destinations is crucial in the tourism industry. Hence, such

aspects have been elaborated and evaluated, along with considering the findings that the author has recommended in terms of a model that should help the Albanian Tourism Industry to develop in a practical and meaningful manner.

CHAPTER 6 - CONCLUSIONS, CONTRIBUTION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

6.1 Introduction

This chapter concludes and summarises material that the researcher collected and evaluated. The researcher conducted this research to understand and evaluate usage of technology in the tourism industry, its effectiveness and how technology can be used as a strategic tool for promotional purposes.

Processes and the way objectives have been achieved and the outcome have been deliberated along with contributions to the body of knowledge by analysing factors that decide how use of technology in the tourism industry can be used for further development. After considering positive and negative effects of technology and analysing the impact service quality has in the tourism industry, recommendations have been made. Limitations of this research have been discussed and areas for further research identified.

6.2 Achieving objectives

Considering the nature of this research, it had difficulties and limitations. Research objectives consisted of four different issues:

1. The current state of the tourism industry,
2. Levels of technology usage in tourism in Albania,
3. Factors that render effective usage of technology in the tourism industry of Albania,
4. Recommendations regarding further development of tourism in Albania.

6.2.1 The current situation of tourism globally and in Albania

Tourism industry has become one of the fastest growth industries that has impacted the global economy. It contributes towards the development of distinct new destinations each year.

Considering the researcher's findings from primary and existing material, the tourism industry is important, not only in Albania, but also globally for several reasons such like the positive impact it has upon the economy, contribution to GDP, employment, and its impact on social and cultural lifestyle issues. Technology has helped the tourism industry to develop even faster as demonstrated by positive impacts and growth of the tourism industry over recent decade. This growth has been slow but significant and beneficial for Albania and its image, and it is demonstrated that tourism always requires innovation in term of technology to satisfy customer requirements.

Online promotion and social media advertising are widely used by tour agencies and operators nowadays in Albania, as they can target extensive groups of customers at the same time to promote their products and services more rapidly.

6.2.2 Levels of technology use in the Albanian tourism industry

As already mentioned, technology is now an important part of tourism development. Customer demands for more opportunities and choice combined with market competition has increased the need for innovation and value adding tools that can help tourism businesses to increase profits and productivity.

These research findings report that technology has impacted tourism in Albania by building a confident market for business and facilities to reach customers as well as communication channel between agencies and customers which results in faster trustworthy information.

An important point of technology usage is use of web2.0 software which allows communication to be fair and competitive and organisations can add products by augmenting pictures along with appropriate script. Customers can exchange experiences and thoughts regarding tourist products in Albania. The use of technology and ICT is lower than in neighbouring countries, but this is forecast to change in the coming years. Online promotion is a component of technology which has shaped the tourism industry. By advertising tourist products through social media applications, this has been beneficial and at a low cost for tour agencies and operators. Social media promotion results attract more attention compared to traditional ways of promotion because products/services have superior presentational measures. Interaction between customers and tourist agencies is quicker and this quickens decision-making processes which are more transparent and accurate.

6.2.3 Factors rendering effective usage of technology in the Albanian tourism industry.

Considering findings from current literature and primary data, factors that render the use of technology have been identified that include ease of use, reliability, assurance/security, trust, and cost effectiveness. The use of technology has created multiple methods to attract customers at lower costs in a shorter time.

The researcher isolated factors which contribute to effective usage of technology in the tourism industry. Some are related to the benefits of using technology by tour agencies and operators. Adaptation of technology can facilitate everyday work and tasks, create

stronger connections between agencies and customers, give opportunities for development and advantages in the market, that helps to reach customers easier.

The adaptation of technology and effective use of databases to keep customer details is useful. Use of devices, software, apps, and websites facilitate everyday duties in tourism agencies. Technology has changed marketing campaigns and the way agencies reach customers. For instance, on-line promotion and social media has given agencies opportunities to reach different markets at the same time. Tourist products/services can be reached by multiple means at the same time.

Adaptation of technology can be expensive, especially in market where most businesses are small enterprises that need to pay for training of programs and staff. However, these costs are small compared to opportunities that technology gives to tourism.

6.2.4 Recommendations regarding further development of tourism in Albania.

Considering research results it is important to mention the benefits that technology usage has upon Tourism Industry in Albania. The components of technology such as usefulness, ease of use, reliability, security, trust, and cost effectiveness are factors that facilitate the tourism industry in Albania. Similarly, internet and online promotion are currently used as crucial part for promotion and advertisement in the tourism industry.

Considering the above factors that render the technology usage it is important to mention that tourism industry in Albania has considered online promotion crucial due to its benefits and facilities. In the Albanian tourism industry internet, ICT, social media and online promotion has resulted to be one of the important strategic tools that is used for marketing purposes. However, it is important to mention that agencies try to achieve competitiveness by introducing fascinating and unique services/ products which would result in profits and loyal customers. The researcher's recommendation regarding these factors it's that businesses should hire people who are skilled and experienced in the field. This would realise as a strategy for these businesses in order to be credible, trusted, to attract attention and use the right methods to be competitive in the market.

The researcher is going to elaborate and suggest more changes in the below sections. Those recommendations are related to different issues that Albanian tourism industry and respectively agencies and businesses can improve and develop even more.

6.3 Research contribution

The aim of conducting research in any field is to add value and enhance existing information regarding a certain topic, issue, or destination. Research contribution is the main reason why a certain topic must be observed to create new perspectives, knowledge and give recommendations for future enhancement and development. Research contribution has been split based in two aspects, namely theoretical contribution, and practical contribution.

6.3.1 Theoretical contribution

This research consists of presenting models to improve website design, and customer satisfaction through customer service by improving trust, responsiveness, and security. A model that contributes to theory is a model that shows how Albania can use technology and its components to improve its destination image as well as to gain competitive advantage in the international market.

A model was introduced in Chapter 5 (Figure 5.2) to assess relationships that customers have with certain websites in the tourism industry. This model provides valuable information about how businesses that operate in tourism should treat information that they share on their websites and the impact this will have on customers. This model contributes to the body of knowledge to understand that website design and content is important in the tourism industry as it is the first contact customers have with certain destinations. By combining two models that were discussed in Chapter 2, it was found that website content is one of the main indicators that impel decision-making processes. This contribution is an evaluation of findings that can be used in similar types of organisation or tourist destinations that have similar characteristics.

A measurement scale model to assess the effect of technology on customer satisfaction was introduced in Chapter 5 (Figure 5.3) to assess the relation between service quality and customer satisfaction through technology and responsiveness factors, security factors and trust. It was identified that lack of these factors could affect customer satisfaction and retention. Theoretical contribution of this model consists of analysing factors that significantly affect customer satisfaction through service quality. Since the tourism industry is characterised by services and intangibility, it is important for customers to receive unsurpassed service. The theoretical contribution of this model is useful for researchers when assessing responsiveness, security, and trust factors as indicators to improve service quality and to increase customer satisfaction. This model can be applied in different businesses to provide outcomes which share similar characteristics as tour operators.

A model was introduced in Chapter 5 (Figure 5.4) concerning a combination of different technological effects such as usefulness, ease of use, reliability, responsiveness, assurance and security, trust, and cost effectiveness. Different effects of technology in the tourism industry have been identified after reviewing existing literature. Combined with literature, research findings identified that such effects positively impact tourism. The model is significant as it was developed from the literature and was designed based on the pilot study. Qualitative and quantitative analyses were used to analyse findings after the data was collected and Cronbach's alpha was used to assess the reliability of findings. This model contributes to the body of knowledge by combining various effects of technology in the tourism industry to understand the impact of promotion. The model can help researchers to understand effects of technology and can be used in different studies. The model provides an indication for further research to measure different dimensions like customer satisfaction, retention, or loyalty in the tourism industry.

6.4 Practical contribution

Tourism industry is a field that has received great attention from many researchers who have been looking into different means and models to solve problems and open ways for further development.

In terms of Albania as a tourist destination, researchers should understand where it stands and how it can gain competitive advantage in the global tourism market. In relation to this research, the main contribution consists of an evaluation of the current situation of tourism industry in Albania, as well as identifying levels of technology usage. Previous research considered different aspects of tourism in Albania, including technology impact and its role in the tourism industry, but its focus concerned identification of levels of technology in businesses that operate within tourism and its role as a strategic tool for marketing and promotional with an emphasis on improving overall performance of the tourism industry.

This research contributes to the body of knowledge by raising awareness regarding benefits of the technology and ICT adaptation for development purposes even though it can be costly and includes staff training and customer service. This research raises awareness that there is the need for professionals and educated staff to deal with customer in all human aspects from first contact to final sale.

Considering this research and experiences of interviewed participants it is important to mention that promotion and its influence in the tourism industry can be seen as an effect

of technological adaptation in the Albanian tourism industry. Investment is needed to improve the destination image to achieve competitive advantage. Adaptation of appropriate technology gives opportunities for tour agencies and other businesses to enrich promotional activity due to unlimited opportunities that technology offers.

6.5 Recommendations

Albania is a developing country, and the tourism industry is improving quickly. This positive aspect influences overall development in Albania. Albania was a Communist regime for a long time with connotations as being a dangerous destination, and this has affected tourism development until recently. Even though Albanian tourism industry is improving, there is need to mention that there are aspects which Albania needs to improve to achieve better results and benefits from the industry. Recommendations are not all connected to tourism, but their development influences the industry. Due to economic reasons and lack of information large numbers of Albanians do not have many holidays during the year. This phenomenon modifies how the government works towards increasing living standards.

Furthermore, there is lack of information regarding tourist destinations and products in Albania from Albanians themselves. The Albanian tourism industry is characterised by a lack of infrastructure. Some tourist destinations are difficult or impossible to access even though they provide wonderful potential. In the case of Albania, infrastructure does not mean only roads or access to certain destinations, but it includes lack of certain excursions and information regarding destinations.

Another recommendation is related to academic institutions which should obtain more attention for producing skilled professionals for the tourism industry. There are universities that offer tourism and hospitality courses, but mostly this education is followed in professional schools. These schools should receive more attention from Government to include more profound programs to study in Hospitality and Tourism. There is a demand for skilled people in business as well as the tourism industry, and this should provide more opportunities for employment.

It is suggested that this profession should be commended to people as tourism is expanding and market requirements for professionals is high. Even though the hospitality and tourism industry has improved in the sense that promotion is easier through the internet and online booking and reservations, there are still problems with service levels that customers receive. This is a result of untrained staff who cannot maintain a standard that satisfy customers. Due to the nature of tourism, it is important that agencies, tour operators, and

accommodation units should focus more to improvement of customer service. In this way businesses can add value to their business and increase profits. Albania is one of those countries whose tourism sector needs to be improved to respond to international market requirements.

In tourism an 'all inclusive' sale is an opportunity to sell more services in one sale such as flights, accommodation, culinary services, as well tourist products. In the case of Albania, only a few businesses offer such services. On the other hand, tourist agencies in Albania offer this service globally, but Albania flights are costly and accumulative prices for all services are high and customer unwilling to pay so much. Government should consider facilitating procedures to help the tourism industry improve and develop more.

6.6 Limitations of the research

Based on personal experience, the researcher faced difficulties in some areas when completing the research owing to the area of study, the case study destination, and the location where the research was processed. The researcher studied in London and the research was processed there although the case study involved the tourism industry in Albania where the research was conducted with participants from tour agencies and operators. Even though Albania is not far from UK, travelling there to do fieldwork is costly for a student. Time was another limitation as data was collected over three months because of the nature of the study that had set starting and finishing points.

Another limitation relates to the sample which was not large as it represented a relatively small percentage compared to the total population. Taking into consideration the nature of participants it was felt that this was adequate as sometimes it was felt that they avoided sharing their honest opinions related to certain destinations or issues and simply provided an unspecific perception. More poignantly perhaps, Albania is still characterised by a mentality from the Communist period and people do not trust anyone asking questions about the work they do, and this applies particularly to tourist agencies.

The researcher followed university guidelines in terms of advice relating to matters of trust to enable the researcher to convince participants that this was an academic research project, and their information would be strictly protected. Despite these difficulties, the researcher managed to fulfil the objectives and use collected information and data to complete the research.

6.7 Further research

This research has added to the body of knowledge by presenting distinctive models that comprise website design, customer satisfaction and service quality related to how to improve tourism in Albania through utilising technological impacts. By applying such models this can help the tourism industry to improve. Further research could make these models stronger, and potentially give different meanings and ideas for the tourism industry and provide better opportunities for research in other areas.

Based on information regarding the function of technology and ICT, this research has contributed to a rising degree of awareness regarding the importance of using and adapting new technologies in the tourism industry. In certain cases, technological adaptations can be costly, but considering the benefits of accepting them, it is judicious to make such investments.

Reflecting on research findings and from the literature review, different effects of technology have been identified and discussed. The proposed model can be adopted and tested based on experiences of customers to understand the scale of how these outcomes can be used in promotional activities in the tourism industry. Since the model encompasses tour operator issues, it is important that the model should have the ability to be applied to different business such as accommodation units or restaurants. Likewise, the model has been conceived from a general point of view of promotion, so it is important that future research is focused, in terms of utilising a variety of technological tools used for promotion, such as social media or mobile application promotion to understand the consequences of technology and to appreciate the quantity and quality of service through the application of such technologies.

This model was identified and discussed in chapter 5. The component elements that are used to measure the service quality were identified, based on an elaboration of the literature that considered general aspects of security and reliability from customer requirements.

Considering that the model reflects an increase of customer satisfaction through service quality, it is important that it can be adapted and adopted from different perspectives such as from the business aspect rather than the customer side. Adaptation of such model would highlight the effects that satisfied employees have upon tourist experiences as well as their satisfaction with services provided. If the model can be tested, it might be improved and developed further in other areas. Website design is important as it is the first contact that customers/tourists have with a particular destination.

The model can be tested against the experiences of customers when using tourist websites to understand how the model can be improved and be used as an indicator for further development in the tourism industry. The model that has been discussed covers a general perspective of the tourism industry and it is important that it can be applied to different sectors such as hospitality. Another point is that the model needs to be tested and that it is focused on the explicit aspect of having a website for development. The adaptation of the model would shed light in relation to the effect that websites have on customer retention in the tourism industry.

During the research process, the author was unable to find much information in relation to seasonality aspects and customer loyalty. Further research that can combine such factors should evaluate the relationship between seasonality and the variety of products, and to understand how such factors can be used for further development on the destination image of Albania.

6.8 Summary

This research has used both qualitative and quantitative findings to analyse the impact of technology in the tourism industry in Albania. By evaluating existing literature and primary findings, factors that render the usage of technology have been identified and analysed. Primary data has been used to understand the level of technology usage in Albania, as well as its influence on the improvement of the Albanian tourism industry through technology enhancement. Considering evaluation of the literature and existing models, various components were identified and applied to the Albanian tourism industry to use these components as factors for further development of the industry.

Results from the findings have identified that customer satisfaction is a key indicator which enhances opportunities for further development in the tourism industry. Hence, it was observed that reliability, security, and trust play a crucial role in terms of increasing customer satisfaction.

This research has made a significant contribution to the body of knowledge by introducing several models related to improvement of website design of tourist destinations and organisations, by enhancing customer satisfaction through improving service quality and by increasing levels of security, reliability, and trust. The research has contributed to the body of knowledge through modelling effects of technology in the tourism industry and how it can be used for further development.

Suggestions relating to further research have been provided to strengthen the outcome of this research and to broaden the area of study where these models can be applied.

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APPENDIX

Appendix A

Questionnaire 1- understanding the level of technology usage in the Albanian tourism agencies.

TOPIC: CRITICAL EVALUATION OF USING TECHNOLOGY AND INFORMATION COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGY AS STRATEGIC TOOL FOR PROMOTION IN THE TOURISM INDUSTRY IN ALBANIA

Hello, I am Gesanta Berdufi and I am conducting a study on the use of information technology in the tourism industry in Albania, as part of the doctoral process. The purpose of this study is to explore the level of use of information technology from tourism enterprises, focusing on accommodation units, travel agencies and touristic organisations, as well as how IT is used for tourism promotion in order to develop the sector. Your participation is voluntary. In this study, the anonymity of the participants will be preserved, so please sincerely answer all of the following statements.

If you would prefer not to take part of this project, then I thank you for your time and you need not to complete the questionnaire. If you are happy to participate, please complete the questionnaire. All the given information will be treated confidentially.

I am very grateful for your assistance

Section 1. General Information

Name of Entrepreneur: _____

Completed Location: _____

Gender

- Female
- Male

Age

20-30

31-40

41-50

51-60

60 and over

1- Type of organisation:

- A) Small
- b) Large

2- What is your position in the company?

- A) Entrepreneurs
- b) Managers
- c) Other, please specify_____

4- Of which category is your clientele?

- A) Mainly from foreign nationals
- b) Mainly by Albanian National
- c) Both

5- What type of promotional activity is mostly undertaken by your organisation to attract tourists ?

- A. Advertising
- B. Brochures
- C. Sales Promotion
- D. Social Media
- E. Other (Please specify_____)

6- What media does your organisation use for the promotional activity ?

- A. Online sales
- B. Social Media
- C. Tv/ Radio
- D. Newspapers/ Magazines
- E. Other (Please specify_____)

7- How does your organisation attracts tourists ?

- A. Holiday packages
- B. Products / services
- C. Season offers
- D. Service quality
- E. Leisure events
- F. Other(Please specify_____)

Section 2. Usage of Information Technology in Tourism Industry.

1. Do you think technology plays an important role in promoting tourism products/ destinations?
 - No, it does not matter
 - Maybe
 - Yes, it is important

2. Which factors determine the effectiveness of using technology in tourism sector?

Please specify _____

Section 3 . Infrastructure of Information Technology and Communications

1. Does your enterprise have access to the Internet?
 - A) Yes
 - b) No
2. What frameworks of technology do you use to connect to the internet?
 - A) Dial-up modem
 - b) ADSL (digital internet via telephone line)
 - c) Broadband via cab
 - d) Wireless connection
 - e) Other Yes / No. If you specify _____
3. Does your organisation use a computer network for communication?
 - A) Yes
 - b) No
4. Does your organisation has a web page?
 - A. Yes
 - B. No
5. If you have a website from whom is it managed?
 - A) From your in-house staff Yes / No
 - B) From Individuals / Outsourcing Yes / No
 - C) Other Yes / No. If so please specify _____
6. How do you think, during a normal working day, what percent of the travel is made through the computer?
 - A) 75% or more
 - b) 50-74%
 - c) 25-49%
 - d) 0-25%
- 7- What software does your organisation use for tourism purposes?

Please specify _____
 Section 4. Please tick on the following.

	Strongly disagree	Do not Agree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree
I think that using Technology and Information and Communication Technology gives more opportunity to enhance the organisational image.					
I think the use of IT and ICT in the organisation can provide valuable information that can help customers to make decisions.					
I think that technology takes a lot of time by doing mechanical actions(performing , data jams) and does not allow enough time to perform other work.					
I think the use of IT and ICT allows to access, collect and distribute information more easily.					
The internet allows to have a better communication with the costumers.					
There is an increased number of customers who visits the website for travel purposes.					
The internet allows to have less marketing and promotional costs compared to the traditional methods(direct contacts with sale agents, leaflets, brochures).					
The internet is a way to increase business profit and staff performance .					
The initial cost of creating a website is high for the organisations.					
The skills required to sell tourist services through a website are very difficult.					
Integrating the web into daily work Is					
Using the website to sell services is clear, understandable and fair.					
Do you think the internet is widely used by touristic service providers to promote/sell services?					
Promotion of tourist services through websites is largely widespread in Albania					
The organisation has a website promoting its activity in social media.					

Promotional activities through internet are very effective in targeting new market.					
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THANK YOU FOR YOUR PARTICIPATION

APPENDIX B

Questionnaire 2- Understanding the tourists perception of Information technology.

TOPIC: CRITICAL EVALUATION OF USING TECHNOLOGY AND INFORMATION COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGY AS STRATEGIC TOOL FOR PROMOTION IN THE TOURISM INDUSRTY IN ALBANIA

Hello, I am Gesanta Berdufi and I am conducting a study on the use of information technology in the tourism industry in Albania, as part of the doctoral process. The purpose of this study is to explore the level of use of information technology from tourism enterprises, focusing on accommodation units, travel agencies and touristic organisations, as well as how IT is used for tourism promotion in order to develop the sector . Your participation is voluntary. In this study, the anonymity of the participants will be preserved, so please sincerely answer all of the following statements.

If you would prefer not to take part of this project, then i thank you for your time and you need not to complete the questionnaire. If you are happy to participate , please complete the questionnaire. All the given information will be treated confidentially.

I am very grateful for your assistance

Section 1. General Information

Gender

- Female
- Male

Age

- A. 20-30
- B. 31-40
- C. 41-50
- D. 51-60
- E. 60 and over

1- What is your occupation?

- A. Student
- B. Doctor
- C. Teacher
- D. Other
(_____)

2- How often do you travel?

- A. Once a year
- B. Twice a year
- C. More than twice
- D. Rarely
- E. Other
(_____)

3-Where do you mostly prefer to travel?

- A. Europe
- B. Africa
- C. India
- D. Asia
- E. America
- F. Other (_____)

4- Have you ever chosen a tourist destination influenced by promotion ?

- A. No
- B. Yes

5- What type of promotion has influenced your choice?

- A. Travel agencies promotion
- B. Friends or Relatives
- C. Social Media
- D. Other (_____)

6- Do you think the internet is widely used by touristic service providers to promote/sell services?

- A. Yes
- B. No
- C. Depends on their chosen destination.

Please tick one of the following statements.

Statement	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strong Agree
I think technology has been impacting positively Tourism Industry since its introduction.				
I think the adaptation of various technologies has facilitated work for tourism agencies and other organisation in the sector.				
I think internet and technology usage helps to communicate with customers and vice versa.				
I think that using Technology and Information and Communication Technology gives more opportunity to reach customers and new markets.				
I think that the use of IT and ICT in the tourism organisation can provide valuable information that can help customers to make decisions.				
I think Using the website to sell services is clear, understandable and fair.				
I think the use of IT and ICT allows to access, collect and distribute information more easily.				
I think internet is a way to increase number of tourists.				
I think Promotional activities through internet are very effective in targeting new market.				

I think Information Communication Technology allows organisation use the customer feedback for further development.				
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THANK YOU FOR YOUR PARTICIPATIO

Appendix C

Interview form

Question 1 - Can you tell me about your experience in the Tourism sector. What spotted your interest for this industry ? Do you enjoy your participation in this sector?

Question 2- What do think about Global Tourism Industry ? What can you tell me about the Albanian Tourism Industry ?

Question 3- Do you think Tourism Industry impacts Albanian Development ?

Question 4- What do you think about the combination of Tourism Industry and internet? Do you think the internet usage and social media are helpful for touristic developments?

Question 5- Do you think technology and ICT plays an important role in tourism industry ?

Question 6- Would you please identify some of the factors that make usage of technology more effective in the Albanian Tourism Industry? How can this factors be used as a strategy for further development ?

Question 7- What is the impact and the level of technology usage in the Albanian Tourism Industry ?

Question 8- Would you please tell me , in what promotional activity is Albanian Tourism mostly focused ?

Question 9 –According to your opinion , what changes in the technology usage would give more development on the Albanian Tourism Industry ?

Question 10- Do you have any recommendation regarding tourism Industry in Albania?

APPENDIX D

Interview theme transcript

Question	Answer 1	Answer 2	Theme extracted
Can you tell me about your experience in the Tourism sector. What spotted your interest for this industry ? Do you enjoy your participation in this sector?	I am currently working for the Kalemi tour agency and according to my experience in tourism sector , there is a great pleasure to work in a sector as Albanian tourism , as it is a destination that still has natural beauties which still needs to be explored and promoted to tourists.	I am currently working for Bravo Tours Albania and this is an amazing experience for me	Experience and pleasure
What do think about Global Tourism Industry ? What can you tell me about the Albanian Tourism Industry ?	Tourism as a sector is a very wide and it gives a great opportunity in getting introduced with different natures, states, places and so on. I personally think that tourism sector in other countries has more investments comparing to the same sector in Albania.	Considering tourism globally in would say that tourism worldwide is more advanced and improves but in Albania the industry has been slower and its development as well. However this is coming into a change as during the last 4 years the development and improvement in the tourism industry has changed with faster steps towards improvement following the neighbouring countries.	Knowledge regarding nature, less investments in Albania
Do you think Tourism Industry impacts Albanian Development ?	Yes, I personally think that if there would have been more investments in the Albanian tourism sector , there would be better developed Albania.	Of course yes. One of the main reasons why Albania is known and remembered by the tourists is because of the improvements in the tourism sector .	More investments , faster development

		considering that Albania is one of those touristic destinations that brings curiosity to tourists due to its natural beauties, cultural, historical and social premises.	
- What do you think about the combination of Tourism Industry and internet? Do you think the internet usage and social media are helpful for touristic developments?	Nowadays , social media is getting a very important tool for the tourism industry, especially playing the role of expanding knowledge and exploring new places or products. This important tool is having an impact on the helping to develop tourism sector.	I need to say that internet is the key of the improvements in the tourism industry in Albania. Promotion of the Albanian natural beauties through social media has created more communication channels with tourists	Strong impact of social media
- Do you think technology and ICT plays an important role in tourism industry ? Do you think these impacts or influences the Industry and how ?	Yes I personally think that technology has an important role in tourism industry which has an impact on the development and improvement of the sector in terms of service, products and presentation of the destination.	I think technology plays a very important role and has great impact in the tourism sector because if technology develops it means that its adaptation helps in development of the whole Tourism Industry. As well as , by using different technological techniques ,the number of tourists increases and the infrastructure improves at the same time. So it brings a positive impact on the services as well as wellbeing of tourists.	Technology affects tourism development

<p>Would you please identify some of the factors that make usage of technology more effective in the Albanian Tourism Industry? How can these factors be used as a strategy for further development ?</p>	<p>One of the main factors is the ego to develop the business in the tourism industry. At the same time technology is not only developing the sector but as well is contributing to the economic sector which brings loads of benefits and incomes from the tourism industry</p>	<p>Different advertising and introduction of the whole touristic places and services makes it more interesting as a destination and it attracts the tourists attention.</p>	<p>Technological effect in economy-benefits to tourism</p>
<p>What is the impact and the level of technology usage in the Albanian Tourism Industry ?</p>	<p>Albania, as other neighbour European countries , consider technology as one of the main factor that impacts the development of the tourism industry . According to my work experience in tourism industry I have understood that in Albania , technology is used in more than 80% of the organisations through the sector.</p>	<p>70% of the touristic organisations and agencies in Albania uses technology as one of the main factors and indicators to promotion and other advertisement. It is the high requirements and expectation that makes possible that agencies in tourism sector increase their technological usage in order to be competitive and to fulfil the requirements of the market</p>	<p>-</p>
<p>Would you please tell me , in what promotional activity is Albanian Tourism mostly focused ?</p>	<p>Albania is mostly focused on the promotion through online and social media, especially instagram is used as a main tool for touristic promotion , where individuals or agencies promote their products or services.</p>	<p>I think Albania is mostly focused on the promotional activities through the online websites and social media which makes it more attractive and</p>	<p>Social media promotion</p>

		interesting being said for the price as well as the places or destinations chosen for promotion.	
According to your opinion , what changes in the technology usage would give more development on the Albanian Tourism Industry ?	According to my opinion , tourism industry would develop even more if technology is used even more . There would not be any problems or difficulties regarding selection, choice and orientation of the tourism sector.	According to my opinion , I think that except technology , tourism needs more investments, different trainings, in relation to tourism sector and technology including training in customer service which are very important and essential in the Albanian tourism sector. Adaptation and application of technological tools and latest apps would bring more development and improvement in the Albanian tourism sector	Helps in selection and decision making process

Appendix D

Nr. _____

PARTICIPANT CONSENT FORM

University of West of Scotland, London Campus

Participant's name: _____

Title of the Research :

Name of the Researcher : Gesanta Berdufi

- 1- I confirm that I have read and understood the information sheet about this research.
- 2- I understand that my participation is voluntary and I am aware that I can stop participating at any time .
- 3- I agree to participate in this research.
- 4- I agree that interview can be audio /visual recorded.
- 5- I am aware that this information is going to be for academic purposes and I am aware of the confidentiality of the information, as well as who are the people that are going to have access this information.
- 6- I confirm that I have read all the above statements.

Signature of the participant _____

Date _____

Name and Signature
of the person taking consent _____

Date _____

Gesanta Berdufi
B00301153

14 August 2017

School of Business
and Enterprise
Paisley Campus
Paisley PA1 2BE
Scotland

Tel 0141 848 3000
Direct 0141 848 3932

Dear Gesanta

Ethics Application Number: B&E198

Title of Study: Critical evaluation of using technology and information communication technology as strategic tool for promotion in the tourism industry in Albania

The School of Business & Enterprise Ethics Committee has considered your application and we are pleased to inform you that your application has been successful. Therefore approval to conduct the research as outlined in your application has been given.

We wish you well in your DBA research.

Yours sincerely

Dr A Kourouklis
Chair
School of Business & Enterprise Ethics Committee

Professor Malcolm Foley
Dean of the School

APPENDIX F

Reliability test coding – what letters are standing for. (questionnaire 1, figure 4.1).

A	I think that using Technology and Information and Communication Technology gives more opportunity to enhance the organisational image.
B	I think the use of IT and ICT in the organisation can provide valuable information that can help customers to make decisions.
C	I think that technology takes a lot of time by doing mechanical actions(performing , data jams) and does not allow enough time to perform other work.
D	I think the use of IT and ICT allows to access, collect and distribute information more easily.
E	The internet allows to have a better communication with the costumers.
F	There is an increased number of customers who visits the website for travel purposes.
G	The internet allows to have less marketing and promotional costs compared to the traditional methods(direct contacts with sale agents, leaflets, brochures).
H	The internet is a way to increase business profit and staff performance.
I	The initial cost of creating a website is high for the organisations.
J	The skills required to sell tourist services through a website are very difficult.
K	Using the website to sell services is clear, understandable and fair.
L	Do you think the internet is widely used by touristic service providers to promote/sell services?
M	Promotion of tourist services through websites is largely widespread in Albania
N	The organisation has a website promoting its activity in social media.

Reliability test coding – what letters are standing for. (Questionnaire 2, figure 4.2).

SWLS1	I think technology has been impacting positively Tourism Industry since its introduction.
SWLS2	I think the adaptation of various technologies has facilitated work for tourism agencies and other organisation in the sector.
SWLS3	I think internet and technology usage helps to communicate with customers and vice versa.
SWLS4	I think that using Technology and Information and Communication Technology gives more opportunity to reach customers and new markets.
SWLS5	I think that the use of IT and ICT in the tourism organisation can provide valuable information that can help customers to make decisions.
SWLS6	I think Using the website to sell services is clear, understandable, and fair.
SWLS7	I think the use of IT and ICT allows to access, collect and distribute information more easily.
SWLS8	I think internet is a way to increase number of tourists.
SWLS9	I think Promotional activities through internet are very effective in targeting new market.
SWLS10	I think Information Communication Technology allows organisation to use the customer feedback for further development.